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CHAPTER 1

NONLINEAR OPTICS AND ITS APPLICATIONS

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1.1 Introduction

Laser is certainly one of the greatest inventions in the history of science and technology. Its arrival created many fascinating new fields, among which nonlinear optics undoubtedly has the broadest scope and the most influential proponent. The field originated with experimental work of Franken and his co-workers [1] on optical second harmonic generation in 1961, and the theoretical work of Bloembergen and co-workers [2] on optical wave mixing in 1962. After this, the field of nonlinear optics has grown at such a prodigious rate that today it has already found applications in nearly all areas of science.

Nonlinear effects in electricity and magnetism have been known since Maxwell's time. Saturation of magnetization in ferromagnet, electrical gas discharge, rectification of radio waves and electrical characteristics of p-n junctions are just a few of the familiar examples. In optical region, however nonlinear optics became a subject of great common interest only after the laser was invented. This is because nonlinear electromagnetic phenomena in optical region normally occur with high intensity laser beams.

Numerous nonlinear optical phenomena have been discovered since 1961, which created a revolutionary change in optics technology. Each nonlinear optical process may consist of two parts; (i) the intense light first induces a nonlinear response

in a medium, (ii) and then the medium modifies the optical field in nonlinear way. The former is governed by the constitutive equations and the later by Maxwell's equations.

It is surprising to know that all media basically nonlinear ! Even the vacuum is no exception, because photons can interact through vacuum polarization. The nonlinearity is however so small that the photon - photon scattering and other nonlinear effects in vacuum can be regarded as linear [3]. In presence of medium, the nonlinearity is greatly enhanced through interaction of light with matter because photons can interact much more efficiently through polarization of the medium.

Nonlinear optics is expected to play a major role in the technology of photonics. Photonics is the analog of electronics in that it describes the technology in which photons instead of electrons are used to acquire, store, transit and process information. Photonics is emerging as a multidisciplinary new frontier of science and technology that is capturing the imagination of scientists and engineers world wide because of its potential applications in too many areas of present and future information and image processing technologies.

With the advent of high intensity lasers, much progress has been made in the field of nonlinear optics. The strong oscillating electric field of laser beam creates a polarization response that is nonlinear in character which can act as a source of new optical fields with altered optical properties. Among them the frequency doubling or second harmonic frequency

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generation is more important one. This process can provide for conversion of near-infra-red laser light from diode lasers into deep blue light in the field of optical information storage. Since the size of focussed spot of light is inversely proportional to its wavelength, the second harmonic generation (SHG) can increase the capacity of stored information on optical disks. Using related phenomena, one can also build devices such as frequency mixers that can act as new light sources or as amplification schemes, light modulators for controlling the phase or amplitude of a light beam, optical switches, optical logic, optical limiters and numerous ways of processing the information content of data images [4].

The most appealing applications of photonics are optical processing of information and optical computing. The major potential advantages are gain in speed in certain types of switching functions and the reconfigurable connectivity of light sources and detectors with little interference or cross-talk between adjacent channels. Photonic switching can take place with femto second speeds, thus providing a gain in speed that is many order of magnitude over that of electronic processes. Working at optical frequencies provides a tremendous gain in the bandwidth of information processing. These optical processing functions are generally free of interference from electrical and magnetic sources. On the other hand, the weak interactions of optical fields with each other have necessitated the development of materials wherein these interactions can be maximized, thus the need for considerable new fundamental understanding of the

interaction of light with matter.

Using nonlinear optical effects, analogs of transistors or optical bistable devices with which light controls light have been demonstrated. Integrated optical circuits, which are counter-parts of electric circuits but where optical fibers or channels in wave guides conduct photons, can provide for various logic memory and multiplexing operations. Based on the prospect of three dimensional interconnectivity between sources and receptors of light, concepts of optical neural networks, that mimic the fuzzy algorithms by which learning takes place in the brain have been proposed and experimentations have begun.

Apart from the field of photonics, there are other potentially interesting and important applications of nonlinear optics. Some of them are the use of light intensity dependent transmission properties of materials that might serve useful functions as eye or optoelectronic sensor protection from unwanted or stray sources of laser radiation. Here the medium would become not transparent at critical light intensity. The nonlinear optical processes are highly sensitive to many of the microstructural aspects or interfacial characteristics of the medium that exhibits the effects. They may therefore, be suitable for sensor applications to probe structural relaxations in materials, chemical stimuli of various sorts, pressure, temperature, electric fields, magnetic and acoustic fields and so on [5].

These things reveal that the nonlinear optics is a new

frontier of science and technology that is to play a major role in the emerging technology of optoelectronics and photonics, which has been labelled as the technology of 21st century, for which nonlinear optical processes provide the key functions of frequency conversion and optical switching.

1.2 Nonlinear susceptibilities

A dielectric medium when placed in an electric field is polarized, and each constituent molecule acts as a dipole with a dipole moment P_i . The dipole moment vector per unit volume P is given by

$$P = \sum P_i \quad \text{-----(1)}$$

where the summation is over the dipoles in unit volume.

The orienting effect of the external field on the molecular dipoles depends both on the properties of the medium and on the field strength. Thus we can write

$$P = \epsilon_0 \chi E \quad \text{-----(2)}$$

where χ is called the polarizability or dielectric susceptibility of the medium [6]. When the field strength is very high, we enter into the nonlinear region where the relation between P and E is no longer linear but has higher order components as well [7].

Thus

$$P = \epsilon_0 (\chi^{(1)}E + \chi^{(2)}E.E + \chi^{(3)}E.E.E + \dots) \quad \text{-----(3)}$$

where $\chi^{(1)}$ is the same as χ in eqn. (2) and coefficients $\chi^{(2)}$, $\chi^{(3)}$,etc define the degree of nonlinearity and are known as nonlinear susceptibilities. If the field is low, as it is in case of ordinary light sources, only first term of the equation (3) can be retained. It is for this reason, the pre-laser optics is known as linear optics. Higher the value of electric field, more significant becomes the higher terms. It may be noted that the optical characteristics of a medium, such as dielectric permittivity, refractive index etc, which depend upon susceptibility also become functions of the field strength E , if it is sufficiently high. The medium in which the polarization is described by a nonlinear relation of the type in eqn.(3) is called a nonlinear medium.

If we combine all nonlinear terms ($\chi^{(2)}$ and higher terms) in equation (3) and call them the nonlinear polarization, we can write

$$P = \epsilon_0 \chi^{(1)} E + P_{NL} \quad \text{-----(4)}$$

where $\epsilon_0 \chi^{(1)} E$ is the linear term relevant to conventional optics. With the advent of intense lasers, the nonlinear term has become relevant and given rise to a whole range of phenomenon related to frequency conversion [8,9] and other nonlinear effects such as self focussing [10,11], bistability [12,13], intensity dependent refractive index [14,15], phase conjugation [16,17] etc. The susceptibilities are complex quantities having in phase as well as quadrature components.

Since $(\chi^{(1)} E + \chi^{(3)} E.E.E)$ can be written as $(\chi^{(1)} +$

$\chi^{(3)}E^2$, we can infer that due to third order term, the refractive index governed by $\chi^{(1)}$ gets modified by term $\chi^{(3)}E^2$ such that the refractive index now depends on the light intensity (proportional to E^2). Similar effects on refractive index are produced by $\chi^{(5)}$ etc, so that nonlinearity leads to a functional dependence of refractive index on the light intensity.

Some of other well known effects due to $\chi^{(2)}$, $\chi^{(3)}$, $\chi^{(5)}$ etc resulting in frequency conversion are listed in table 1.1.

Table 1.1 : Some nonlinear processes.

Nonlinear Susceptibility	Mixing process
$\chi^{(2)}$ (2 ω ; ω, ω)	Second harmonic generation
$\chi^{(2)}$ (0 ; $\omega, -\omega$)	Optical rectification
$\chi^{(2)}$ (ω ; $\omega, 0$)	Pockels effect
$\chi^{(2)}$ ($\omega \pm \omega$; $\omega \pm \omega$)	Parametric mixing
$\chi^{(3)}$ (3 ω ; ω, ω, ω)	Third harmonic generation
$\chi^{(3)}$ ($\omega \pm \omega \pm \omega$; $\omega, \omega, \pm \omega$)	Four wave mixing
$\chi^{(3)}$ ($\omega \pm \Omega$; $\omega, -\omega, \omega \pm \Omega$)	Raman Scattering
Re $\chi^{(3)}$ (ω ; $\omega, \omega, -\omega$)	A C Kerr effect
$\chi^{(3)}$ ($\omega \pm \Omega$; $\omega, -\omega, \omega \pm \Omega$)	Brillouin Scattering
Re $\chi^{(3)}$ (ω ; $\omega, 0, 0$)	D C Kerr effect
Im $\chi^{(3)}$ (ω ; $\omega, -\omega, \omega$)	Two photon absorption
$\chi^{(3)}$ (2 ω ; $\omega, \omega, 0$)	D C induced SHG

1.3 Harmonic Generation

Suppose an electro magnetic field incident on a medium has the form

$$E = E_0 \cos \omega t \quad \text{-----(5)}$$

substituting this in equation (3), we have

$$P = \epsilon_0 \chi^{(1)} E_0 \cos \omega t + \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E_0^2 \cos^2 \omega t + \epsilon_0 \chi^{(3)} E_0^3 \cos^3 \omega t + \dots \quad \text{-----(6)}$$

using trigonometric relations,

$$\cos^2 \theta = (1 + \cos 2\theta)/2 \quad \text{and} \quad \cos^3 \theta = (\cos 3\theta + 3 \cos \theta)/4 \quad \text{--(7)}$$

We can transform equation (6) to the form

$$P = (1/2) \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E_0^2 + \epsilon_0 (\chi^{(1)} + (3/4) \chi^{(3)} E_0^2) E_0 \cos \omega t + (1/2) \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E_0^2 \cos 2\omega t + (1/4) \epsilon_0 \chi^{(3)} E_0^3 \cos 3\omega t + \dots \quad \text{-----(8)}$$

The first term is a constant term. It gives rise to a dc field across the medium. The second term follows the external polarization and is called the first or fundamental harmonic of polarization, the third term oscillates at frequency 2ω and is called second harmonic of polarization, the fourth term is called the third harmonic of polarization and so on.

1.3.1 Second Harmonic Generation

A polarization oscillating at frequency 2ω radiates an electromagnetic wave of same frequency, which propagates with the same velocity as that of incident wave. The wave thus produced has the same characteristics of directionality and monochromaticity as the incident wave and is emitted in same direction. This phenomenon is known as the second harmonic generation (SHG). In most crystalline materials, the nonlinear polarizability $\chi^{(2)}$ depends on the direction of propagation, polarization of electric field and the orientation of the optic axis of the crystal. Since in such crystalline materials, the vector P and E are not necessarily parallel, and hence the coefficients χ must be treated as tensors. The second order polarization therefore may be represented by the relation of the type

$$P_i^{(2)} = \epsilon_0 \sum \chi_{ijk}^{(2)} E_j E_k \quad \text{----- (9)}$$

where i, j, k represents the co-ordinates x, y, z . Most of the coefficients χ_{ijk} however are usually zero we have to deal only with one or two components [18].

It must be mentioned here that the second harmonic generation represented by equation (9) occurs only in certain types of crystals. In case of isotropic crystals, χ_{ijk} is independent of direction and hence is a constant. If we reverse the direction of the axis ($x \rightarrow -x, y \rightarrow -y, z \rightarrow -z$) leaving electric field and dipole moment unchanged in direction, the sign of these two must change. Therefore

$$-P_i^{(2)} = \epsilon_0 \sum \chi_{ijk}^{(2)} (-E_j)(-E_k) = + P_i^{(2)} \quad \text{-----(10)}$$

which means $P_i^{(2)} = 0$ and hence $\chi_{ijk}^{(2)} = 0$

Second harmonic generation therefore can not occur in an isotropic medium such as liquid, gas or in a centrosymmetric crystal. Only the crystals that lack inversion symmetry exhibit SHG. In case of noncentrosymmetric materials, for example anisotropic crystals such as uniaxial crystals, both quadratic and cubic terms are present. However generally, the cubic term is substantially smaller than the second order term and may be ignored [19]. For such materials we can write

$$P = \epsilon_0 \chi^{(1)} E + \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E^2 \quad \text{-----(11)}$$

and the medium is said to have second order nonlinearity.

1.3.2 Third Harmonic Generation

In case of centrosymmetric materials, the expression (3) will lack terms in the even powers of E and it will reduce to

$$P = \epsilon_0 \chi^{(1)} E + \epsilon_0 \chi^{(3)} E^3 + \dots \quad \text{-----(12)}$$

The third harmonic generation (THG) is therefore possible in crystals that exhibit inversion symmetry. The development of Q-switched lasers had made it possible to generate third harmonic in crystals [20,21]. However, the energy conversion efficiency in such cases is very small. For example, in calcite, the maximum

energy conversion efficiency in the third harmonic was 0.01%. An efficient third harmonic generator can however be constructed by having two nonlinear crystals in series [22]. Here the first crystal generates a second harmonic beam. The transmitted fundamental beam and the second harmonic output beam are then combined in the second crystal to yield third harmonic output by sum - frequency generation.

Experiments for observation of the third harmonic frequency of incident light were performed by Maker and Terhume [23] using giant pulse lasers. Zwernemann and Becker [24] have observed experimentally THG at $9.33 \mu\text{m}$ in carbon monoxide.

Since $|\chi^{(3)}|$ is usually small ($\approx 10^{-12}$ to 10^{-15} esu as compared to $|\chi^{(2)}| \approx 10^{-7}$ to 10^{-9} esu typically) and the laser intensity is often limited by optical damage in crystals, the conversion efficiency for this third order nonlinear process is small. Also phase matching is more difficult to achieve.

Third harmonic generation can occur in gases also. Because of much lower atomic or molecular density in gases than in liquids or solids, the third order nonlinear susceptibility $|\chi^{(3)}|$ for a gas medium should be much smaller than liquids and solids and the efficiency would be very low. Third - order nonlinear optical interactions yield a rich variety of phenomena that can provide useful fundamental information on the structure and dynamics of molecules and polymers and can be utilized for device concepts.

There are numerous third order processes that can be

distinguished on the basis of frequencies of the output and input waves as well as the nature of any material resonance encountered. As in second harmonic processes, third order interactions can give rise to sum and difference frequency mixing. The third order processes can, in general, be viewed as resulting from four wave mixing which is coupled with electronic and vibrational resonances yielding phenomena such as two photon absorption and coherent Raman effects. Furthermore, like second order processes, the intensity dependent refractive index of medium in third order process also gives rise to a large number of phenomena such as self - focusing or defocusing, four wave mixing, optical bistability and optical Kerr gate effect.

1.4 Phase matching

The intense development of research on the mechanism of generation of optical harmonics in crystals and media in which such generation is effectively realizable, has indicated the importance of phase relation between the fundamental and generated harmonics [25,26]. It was observed that the efficiency of generation of harmonics depends not only on the intensity of the exciting radiation, but also on its direction of propagation in crystals.

Suppose a plane wave at frequency w and the second harmonic wave at frequency $2w$ driven by it are propagating in the z direction through a material of length L as shown in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1 : Propagation of w and $2w$ in nonlinear material.

The expression for the intensity (I) for SHG at the exit surface of the material [27]

$$I \propto \sin^2 [(2k_1 - k_2)/2] L / (2k_1 - k_2)/2)^2 \quad \text{----- (13)}$$

This will be maximum when $L = (\pi / (2k_1 - k_2)) = (\pi / \Delta k)$

$$= \lambda / [4 (n_w - n_{2w})] \quad \text{----- (14)}$$

where Δk is called phase mismatch and n_w , n_{2w} are the refractive indices at w and $2w$ respectively. Increasing L more than equation (14) will not result in any increase in I . The magnitude of L given in equation (14) is called the coherence length for the second harmonic radiation.

The intensity of second harmonic wave is sharply peaked about $[(2k_1 - k_2)/2] L = (\Delta k/2) L = 0$

$$\text{that is possible when } k_2 = 2k_1 \quad \text{----- (15)}$$

Hence for efficient frequency doubling, this relation must be satisfied. This requirement is known as phase matching criterion.

$$\text{Since } k_2 = (2w n_{2w})/c \quad \text{and} \quad k_1 = (w n_w)/c$$

The equation (15) reduces to

$$n_{2\omega} = n_{\omega} \quad \text{-----(16)}$$

Thus the phase matching criterion becomes a refractive index criterion. It is rather difficult to fulfil this requirement because most materials show some sort of dispersion in the refractive index. A birefringent material has different refractive indices for different polarization of light. In uniaxial crystal, the ray corresponding to the wave whose refractive index is independent of the direction of propagation is called ordinary ray. The ray corresponding to the other light wave whose refractive index depends on direction of propagation is called extraordinary ray. The behaviour of refractive index is usually described in terms of refractive index surface or index ellipsoid. In case of ordinary ray, it is a sphere and in case of extraordinary ray, it is an ellipsoid. Therefore, we have to choose a material (crystal) in which refractive index for extraordinary ray (n_e) at 2ω is equal to that of ordinary ray (n_o) at ω . Thus the effective frequency conversion in the second harmonic is possible only in a limited number of crystals.

There are generally two types of phase matching conditions [28] viz., type 1 phase matching and type 2 phase matching.

Type 1 phase matching condition :-

In this case, the linearly polarized incident wave and second harmonic wave propagate in the same direction of the wave vector k , that makes an angle θ (phase matching angle) with the

optic axis. For negative uniaxial crystals, $n_o(\omega) = n_e(2\omega)\theta$ i.e. the incident beam is an ordinary wave and the second harmonic is an extraordinary wave, both propagating in the direction k at the same velocity (in phase).

For positive uniaxial crystals, $n_o(2\omega) = n_e(\omega)\theta$

i.e. the incident beam is an extraordinary wave and the second harmonic is an ordinary wave, both propagating in the direction k at the same velocity (in phase).

Type 2 phase matching condition :-

Here, two incident pump beams with orthogonal linear polarizations are used : one is an ordinary wave, the other, an extraordinary wave. The generated second harmonic is an extraordinary wave, all the waves propagating in the same direction k making an angle θ with respect to the optic axis. The condition is achieved by passing first the incident beam through a half wave plate which makes it polarized at 45° with respect to the vertical axis (e - axis in the crystal). In entering the second harmonic medium, the incident wave is decomposed into the ordinary and extraordinary waves. These two waves thus fulfil the two incident pump beam condition. At the output, there are three waves, the two pump waves (now phase shifted with each other) and the second harmonic wave polarized vertically. The output waves of frequencies 2ω and ω can be separated either by using a prism or a thin film dichroic beam splitter that transmits preferentially one frequency and reflects the other.

1.5 Optical Mixing

The nonlinear polarization equation (3) shows that the second term containing the factor E^2 is the product of electric field developed internally through the nonlinear medium. However, such a nonlinear polarization term may also result from the interaction of two fields with different frequencies. Suppose two coherent light wave trains of unequal frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 are traversing the material, the effective field inside is

$$E = E_1 \cos \omega_1 t + E_2 \cos \omega_2 t \quad \text{----- (18)}$$

substituting this in equation (3) the second order term becomes

$$\begin{aligned} P^{(2)} &= \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} (E_1 \cos \omega_1 t + E_2 \cos \omega_2 t)^2 \\ &= \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} (E_1^2 \cos^2 \omega_1 t + E_2^2 \cos^2 \omega_2 t) \\ &\quad + 2\epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E_1 E_2 \cos \omega_1 t \cdot \cos \omega_2 t \quad \text{----- (19)} \end{aligned}$$

Using the trigonometric relation

$$2 \cos \alpha \cos \beta = \cos (\alpha + \beta) + \cos (\alpha - \beta)$$

We can express the last term as

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E_1 E_2 \cos \omega_1 t \cos \omega_2 t \\ = \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E_1 E_2 [\cos (\omega_1 + \omega_2)t + \cos (\omega_1 - \omega_2)t] \quad \text{----- (20)} \end{aligned}$$

This shows that the nonlinear polarization and therefore, emitted radiation contains frequencies $\omega_1 + \omega_2$ and $\omega_2 - \omega_1$.

The energy conversion between the beams can take place over sufficient distances only if the beams travel in the same

direction and at the same velocity.

The sum and difference frequencies can be observed experimentally. Optical mixing of the emission of two ruby lasers with different frequencies was first observed by Franken and coworkers [29]. Sum of frequencies from two ruby lasers held at different temperatures was observed by Bass et al [20] and from a ruby and a neodymium laser by Miller and Savage [30].

Similarly, if we substitute equation (18) in equation (20) with higher order terms like E^3 , E^4 etc, results into the expression containing terms with frequencies $w = mw_1 + nw_2$, where m and n are integers. This shows that in addition to the sum and difference of frequencies, other type of frequency mixing is possible.

The optical frequency mixing in crystals thus uncovers additional possibilities for optical frequency conversion. It has provided a source of narrow band coherent radiation in various regions including those in which there are no primary lasers available. Currently, optical mixing is only source of coherent radiation in XUV. Also frequency mixing is an optical method of producing ultrasonic waves, because sometimes the frequency $w_1 - w_2$ may fall into the range of acoustic frequencies. The phase matching condition in frequency mixing is also important, as in case of second harmonic generation. In the case of sum or difference frequencies, three waves must be matched. If $w_3 = w_1 \pm w_2$ then the condition to be satisfied is $k_3 = k_1 \pm k_2$.

1.6 Nonlinear optical materials

As explained earlier, all materials exhibit nonlinear optical phenomena. The power of the optical fields required to observe these effects varies over many orders of magnitude, depending on the detailed nature of electronic structure of the atomic and molecular constituents of the medium, their dynamic behavior, as well as the symmetry and details of their geometrical arrangement in the medium. From the device point of view, the important nonlinear optical materials are generally in solid forms and must meet a wide variety of ancillary material requirements for practical use. In general, they will require extraordinary stability with respect to ambient conditions and high intensity light sources. They should meet many processing requirements for pattern or shape definition and integration with additional dissimilar materials. Mainly, there are two types of nonlinear materials which usually appear in the field of application. They are molecular materials and bulk materials.

Molecular materials consist of chemically bonded molecular units that interact in the bulk through weak Vander Walls interactions. Many organic crystals and polymers belong to this class of materials. For these materials, the optical nonlinearity is primarily derived from the molecular structure. The expression for the nonlinearity is highly dependent on the geometrical arrangement of the molecules in the condensed medium in the case of second - order nonlinear process, but much less for third order nonlinearities. The primary step in optimizing optical

nonlinearities in this class of materials is at the molecular structure level, which then requires a detailed understanding of the relationship between molecular electronic structure and the nonlinear polarization that can be induced in a molecule.

In case of bulk materials, the nonlinearities are thought of as arising from electrons not associated with individual nuclei, such as those in metals and semiconductors. The optical nonlinearity in this class is determined by the electronic characteristics of the bulk medium and thus requires different theoretical frame works to account for the origins of nonlinear optical effects. Examples of materials in this category are quantum well structures derived from GaAs and II - IV semiconductors such as CdSe. Inorganic crystals such as potassium dihydrogen phosphate(KDP), Potassium titanyl phosphate (KTP), LiNbO_3 , BaB_2O_4 , SrB_2O_4 etc are also regarded as bulk materials because no single molecular unit in the ionic lattice can be identified. However, in these systems, the nonlinear responses are related to individual bond polarizabilities.

The history of organic nonlinear optical materials is quite new compared to the more traditional inorganic nonlinear optical materials. Organic and other molecular materials are increasingly being recognized as the materials of the future because of their molecular nature combined with the versatility of synthetic chemistry which can be used to alter and optimize molecular structure to maximize nonlinear responses and other properties.

The advantages of organic nonlinear materials over classical inorganic nonlinear materials are summarized below.

1) Organic structures can be grown into large crystals, their crystalline layers, fabricated into structures that can be deposited into thin films, layer by layer as in the Langmuir - Blodgett technique, or incorporated into polymers for deposition and processing as highly oriented thin - film structures. The resulting structure can exhibit optimized orientations for many types of nonlinear behaviors especially those of interest for wave guide formats.

2) Many organic materials especially high performance polymers, have high mechanical strength as well as excellent environmental and thermal stability. Recent developments have produced materials with thermal stabilities in excess of 350°C. In contrast to misconceptions about the fragility of organic materials, the optical damage threshold for polymeric materials can easily be greater than 10 GHz/cm² with pico and nano second pulses. In contrast, multiple - quantum well structures derived from GaAs will undergo optical damage at power densities many order of magnitude lower.

3) The dielectric constants of organic crystals are considerably lower than those of inorganic crystals. This feature has important implications for electro-optic devices in which a low frequency ac field is used to modulate the refractive index. The low dielectric constant yields a low RC time constant, thus permitting a large operating band width (> 10 GHz) modulation. Furthermore, for organic materials, the dielectric constants at

low frequency are comparable to those at optical frequencies, which leads to minimization of phase mismatch between electrical and optical pulses in high speed traveling wave photonic devices.

4) Because of their unique chemical structures (π - bonding), organic molecular materials exhibit the largest nonresonant (non absorptive) optical nonlinearities. For many device applications, such as in all - optical signal processing, the nonlinear optical response time is an important consideration. But a nonresonant electronic optical nonlinearity, in organic materials by its nature, would have the fastest response time limited only by the width of the deriving laser pulse. For inorganic systems, the higher nonlinear optical effects are resonant (absorptive). Thus, heat dissipation tends to limit the response time of devices derived from these materials. Other disadvantages of inorganic materials associated with resonant optical nonlinearities are beam depletion due to absorption and thermal damage. Further complications arise from thermally induced nonlinearities associated with refractive index changes, which often can dominate the intrinsic electronic optical nonlinearity.

From above discussion, it is clear that organic molecular materials and polymeric system have emerged in recent years as a new class of promising nonlinear optical materials.

1.7 Survey on nonlinear optical crystals

The first crystal used for SHG experiment in 1961 was quartz [2]. Because of phase matching property and large conversion efficiency, ADP and then KDP replaced quartz [31,32]. During

1965, the first major advance in the development of nonlinear materials came with announcement of the properties of LiNbO_3 [33], which became interesting due to its nonhygroscopic and taking readily polishable nature. For a brief period, it looked as almost an ideal material for NLO in visible and near IR regions [34]. However, when really good quality crystals became available, it was discovered that the crystal suffered from hitherto unknown damage effect [35]. Following lithium niobate, a host of related ferroelectric niobate crystals were grown and studied. Thereafter, a number of inorganic materials were grown in the form of crystals for SHG applications. These include rubidium hydrogen arsenate, ammonium dihydrogen arsenate, lithium iodate, beryllium sulphate, some formates, some borates like barium meta borate, lithium triborate, KTP, rubidium titanyl phosphate, potassium titanyl arsenate, GaAs etc. A survey on inorganic NLO crystals studied till 1990 is reported by Dmitriev et al [36] and Nikogosyan [37].

The approach towards material optimization in the field of organics runs surprisingly parallel with that of inorganic materials. Molecular features responsible for the enhancement of three-photon effects were initially identified after scanning a large number of organic compounds [38 - 40] using the SHG powder test [41]. It has helped to show the basic features of nonlinear molecules namely (1) the presence of highly conjugated and polarizable electronic systems, either linear, cyclic, or a combination of both, and (2) the occurrence of intermolecular charge transfer, which could be modulated by a suitable choice of

donor and acceptor substituents. Moreover, one can in similar way adjust the transparency of the system.

Certain classes of organic molecules have been identified for their interest in NLO such as (1) disubstituted aromatic molecules : exemplified by meta-dinitro benzene (m-DNB), meta-bromonitro benzene (m-BNB), and nitroaniline derivatives like m-NA, p-NA, MAP, NPP and NPAN ; (2) Pyridine family : POM ; (3) Stilbene family : AMA [42]. Some of other potential organic materials reported recently are 2-methoxy-nitro phenol [43], p-toluene sulphonate [44], CMHB [45], MBANP [46], MNA [47], sulfonyl group compounds [48], organometallic compounds [49], organic polymers [50,4], 5-nitro-uracil [51], APDA [52], indole-3-aldehyde [53], LNNL [54], DAD [55] etc. Even though the polymers became an interesting candidates in second order NLO active materials, the general problem in NLO active polymeric system is the decay of orientational order with time.

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(3) Parametric amplification

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(6) Third harmonic generation

It is already mentioned that third harmonic generation can be obtained by using two nonlinear crystals in series. This third harmonic generation provides a mechanism for light control

The advantages of organic nonlinear materials over classical inorganic nonlinear materials are summarized below.

1) Organic structures can be grown into large crystals, their crystalline layers, fabricated into structures that can be deposited into thin films, layer by layer as in the Langmuir - Blodgett technique, or incorporated into polymers for deposition and processing as highly oriented thin - film structures. The resulting structure can exhibit optimized orientations for many types of nonlinear behaviors especially those of interest for wave guide formats.

2) Many organic materials especially high performance polymers, have high mechanical strength as well as excellent environmental and thermal stability. Recent developments have produced materials with thermal stabilities in excess of 350°C. In contrast to misconceptions about the fragility of organic materials, the optical damage threshold for polymeric materials can easily be greater than 10 GHz/cm² with pico and nano second pulses. In contrast, multiple - quantum well structures derived from GaAs will undergo optical damage at power densities many order of magnitude lower.

3) The dielectric constants of organic crystals are considerably lower than those of inorganic crystals. This feature has important implications for electro-optic devices in which a low frequency ac field is used to modulate the refractive index. The low dielectric constant yields a low RC time constant, thus permitting a large operating band width (> 10 GHz) modulation. Furthermore, for organic materials, the dielectric constants at

low frequency are comparable to those at optical frequencies, which leads to minimization of phase mismatch between electrical and optical pulses in high speed traveling wave photonic devices.

4) Because of their unique chemical structures (π - bonding), organic molecular materials exhibit the largest nonresonant (non absorptive) optical nonlinearities. For many device applications, such as in all - optical signal processing, the nonlinear optical response time is an important consideration. But a nonresonant electronic optical nonlinearity, in organic materials by its nature, would have the fastest response time limited only by the width of the deriving laser pulse. For inorganic systems, the higher nonlinear optical effects are resonant (absorptive). Thus, heat dissipation tends to limit the response time of devices derived from these materials. Other disadvantages of inorganic materials associated with resonant optical nonlinearities are beam depletion due to absorption and thermal damage. Further complications arise from thermally induced nonlinearities associated with refractive index changes, which often can dominate the intrinsic electronic optical nonlinearity.

From above discussion, it is clear that organic molecular materials and polymeric system have emerged in recent years as a new class of promising nonlinear optical materials.

1.7 Survey on nonlinear optical crystals

The first crystal used for SHG experiment in 1961 was quartz [2]. Because of phase matching property and large conversion efficiency, ADP and then KDP replaced quartz [31,32]. During

1965, the first major advance in the development of nonlinear materials came with announcement of the properties of LiNbO_3 [33], which became interesting due to its nonhygroscopic and taking readily polishable nature. For a brief period, it looked as almost an ideal material for NLO in visible and near IR regions [34]. However, when really good quality crystals became available, it was discovered that the crystal suffered from hitherto unknown damage effect [35]. Following lithium niobate, a host of related ferroelectric niobate crystals were grown and studied. Thereafter, a number of inorganic materials were grown in the form of crystals for SHG applications. These include rubidium hydrogen arsenate, ammonium dihydrogen arsenate, lithium iodate, beryllium sulphate, some formates, some borates like barium meta borate, lithium triborate, KTP, rubidium titanyl phosphate, potassium titanyl arsenate, GaAs etc. A survey on inorganic NLO crystals studied till 1990 is reported by Dmitriev et al [36] and Nikogosyan [37].

The approach towards material optimization in the field of organics runs surprisingly parallel with that of inorganic materials. Molecular features responsible for the enhancement of three-photon effects were initially identified after scanning a large number of organic compounds [38 - 40] using the SHG powder test [41]. It has helped to show the basic features of nonlinear molecules namely (1) the presence of highly conjugated and polarizable electronic systems, either linear, cyclic, or a combination of both, and (2) the occurrence of intermolecular charge transfer, which could be modulated by a suitable choice of

donor and acceptor substituents. Moreover, one can in similar way adjust the transparency of the system.

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and hence can be used in optical switching, optical bistability, sensor protection, optical phase conjugation, four wave mixing, self focussing, stimulated Raman scattering, optical Kerr effect, DC Kerr effect, two photon emission /absorption /ionization and coherent anti stokes Raman scattering.

The third harmonic process is a source of optical bistability, in optical gyroscopes that may be of value in sensing small change in rotation. Third harmonic nonlinear interactions involving three frequency degenerate input waves have been the field of active research and are used in problems of generating holographic images which is developing rapidly and is called real - time holography.

References

- [1] Franken P, Hill A E, Peters C W and Weinreich G ; *Phys. Rev. Letts*, 7, (1961) 118
- [2] Bloembergen N ; *Nonlinear Optics*, Benjamin, Reading, Massachusetts, 1965
- [3] Heisenberg W and Euler H ; *Z. Phys.* 98, (1936) 714
- [4] Prasad P N and David J W ; *Introduction to Nonlinear Optical effects in molecules and Polymers*. John Wiley and Sons Inc. Newyork. 1991
- [5] Krohn D A ; *Fiber Optics Sensors - Fundamental and Applications*. Instrument Soc. America, 1988
- [6] Laud B B ; *Electromagnetics*. (2nd Ed), Wiley Estern Ltd. 1987
- [7] Bloembergen N and Shen Y R ; *Phys Rev.* 133, (1964) A 37
- [8] Shen Y R ; *The Principles of Non-linear Optics*, Wiley Chap-2, 1984
- [9] Shen Y R ; *Nonlinear Infrared Generation*, Springer Verlag, 1977
- [10] Sodha M ; "Theory of Non-linear refraction, Self focussing of laser beams," *J.Phys.Educ (Ind)*. 1, (1973) 3
- [11] Rampal V V ; *Photonics Elements and Devices*, Wheeler Publishing. (I ed.) 1992 CHA 3, 71
- [12] Wadstone J A ; *Optical bistability in lasers*, Handbook, vol. 4, Stick M and Bass M, eds. North Holland, Amsterdam, 1984
- [13] Boeden C M ; *Optical Bistability*, Clenum Press, 1981

- [14] Kaminow I P and Turner E H ; *Appl. Optics*, 5 (1966) 1612
- [15] Chen F S ; *Proc IEEE* 58, (1970) 1440
- [16] Fisher R A ; ed. *Optical Phase Conjugation*, Academic Press 1983.
- [17] Pepper D M ; ed. *Opt. Eng (Spl.issue on OPC)* 21 (1982)
- [18] Land B B ; *Lasers and Non-Linear Optics II* ed. Wiley Eastern Limited (1991) 179
- [19] Zernike F and Midwinker J E ; *Applied Non-linear Optics*. Wiley Series in pure and applied optics. (1973) 26
- [20] Bass M, Franken P A and Hil A E ; *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 8, (1962) 18
- [21] Reintjes J F ; *Nonlinear Optical Parametric Process In Liquids and Gases*, Academic, Newyork, 1984
- [22] Pistin R ; *Laser Focus* 14(7) (1978) 66
- [23] Maker P D and Terhune R W ; *Phys. Rev.* 137A (1965) 801
- [24] Zwernemann S M and Becker M E ; *App. Opt.* 18 (1979) 728
- [25] Bloembergen N ; *Proc. IEEE* 51 (1963) 124
- [26] Chang K K and Bloembergen N : *Phys. Rev.* 144 (1966) 775
- [27] Yariv A ; *Introduction to Optical Electronics*, IInd Ed, Halt, Rinehart and Winston, New York (1976) 210
- [28] Chin S L ; *Fundamental of Laser Optoelectronics*, Series in Optics and Photonics, Vol II, World Scientific. Publishing (1989) 293
- [29] Franken P A and Ward J F ; *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 35 (1963) 23
- [30] Miller R C and Savage A ; *Phys. Rev.* 128 (1962) 2175
- [31] Jona F, Shirane G ; *Ferroelectric Crystals*, (Pergamon, Oxford 1962)

- [32] Muravev A A and Rubinov A N ; *JETP Lett.* 37 (1983) 713
- [33] Miller R C ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 5 (1964) 17
- [34] Hobden M V and Warner J ; *Phys. Lett.* 22 (1966) 243
- [35] Ashkin A, Boyd G D and Nassau K ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 9 (1966) 72
- [36] Dmitriev V G, Gurzadyan G G and Nikogosyan D N ; in *Handbook of Nonlinear Optical Crystals*, Springer Series in Optical sciences. Vol-64 (1991)
- [37] Nikogosyan D N ; *Sov. J. Quantum Electron.* 7 (1977) 1
- [38] Davydov B L, Derkacheva L D and Somakhina M A ; *JETP Lett.* 12 (1970) 16
- [39] Jerphagnon J ; *IEEE J. Quant. Electron.* QE-7 (1971) 42
- [40] Chemla D S, Oudar J L and Jerphagnon J ; *Phys. Rev.* B12 (1975) 4534
- [41] Kurtz S K and Perry T T ; *J. Appl. Phys.* 39 (1968) 3798
- [42] Badan J, Hierle R and Vidakovic P ; in *Nonlinear Optical Properties of Organic Molecules*, Vol.1, CH-4, (Edited by Chemla and Zyss) 1987
- [43] Nagasawa Y and Takeuchi Y ; *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* 1, 32, 12A (1993) 5549
- [44] Lawrence B L, Cha M and Stegeman G ; *Electron. Lett.* (UK), 30, 5 (1994) 447
- [45] Ide T and Yano S ; *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* 2, 33, 8B (1994) L1189
- [46] Halfpenny P J and Sherwood J N ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 128, 1-4 (1993) 970
- [47] Fukuda T and Yoon D H ; *Cryst. Res. Technol.* (Germany), 29, 7 (1994) 971

- [48] Ulman A and Handley L ; in *Materials for Nonlinear optics - chemical perspectives*, Symposium series, (Edited by Marder S R), Ammerican Chemical Society (1991), CH-10.
- [49] Marder S R and Marsh R E ; in *Materials for Nonlinear optics - chemical perspectives*, Symposium series, (Edited by Marder S R), Ammerican Chemical Society (1991), CH-11.
- [50] Wudl F and McBranch D ; in *Materials for Nonlinear optics - chemical perspectives*, Symposium series, (Edited by Marder S R), Ammerican Chemical Society (1991), CH-46.
- [51] Puccetti G, Badan J and Zyss J ; *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B, Opt. Phys. (USA)*, 10, 4 (1993) 733.
- [52] Kagawa K, Sagawa M, Kakuta A and Ishii K ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 139 (1994) 309
- [53] Youping and Jang Rihong ; *J. Cryst. Growth (Netherlands)*, 130, 3-4 (1993) 444
- [54] Ukachi T and Sugiyama T ; *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B, Opt. Phys. (USA)* 10, 8 (1993) 1372
- [55] Sasaki K and Umegaki S ; *J. Phys. D, Appl. Phys. (UK)* 26, 8B (1993) B-217
- [56] Miyata S ; *J. Illum. Eng. Inst. Jpn.* 77, 1 (1993) 33
- [57] Fainman Y, Ma J and Lee S H ; *Mater. Sci. Rep. (Netherlands)* 9, 2-3 (1993) 53
- [58] Zang Y, Choi Y S and Sasabe H ; *SPIE - Int. Soc. Opt. Eng. (USA)* 1775 (1993) 289
- [59] Bailey R T and Sherwood J N ; *J. Phys. D : Appl. Phys. (UK)* 26, 8B (1993) PB208

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- [60] Ledoux I, Zyss J ; *Int. J. Nonlinear Opt. Phys (Singapore)* 3, 3 (1994) 287
- [61] Shu Shi ; *Contemp. Phys. (UK)* 35, 1 (1994) 21
- [62] Geusic J E, Levinstein H J, Singh S and Uitert L G ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 12 (1968) 306
- [63] Armstrong J A ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 10 (1967) 16
- [64] Maier M, Kaiser W and Giordmaine J A ; *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 17 (1966) 1275
- [65] Tatsuno K ; *Rev. Laser. Eng. (Japan)* 22, 4 (1994) 371
- [66] "Squeezed states of the Electromagnetic Field" ; *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, B4 (1988) 1450
- [67] Min Xiao, Ling-An Wn and Kimble H J ; *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 59 (1987) 278
- [68] Grangier P and La Porta A ; *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 59 (1987) 2153
- [69] Slusher R E and Tai K ; in *Nonlinear Optics Organics and Semiconductors*, Proceedings of International Symposium Tokyo, Japan, 1988
- [70] Ho I T and Siegman A E ; *IRE Trans. Microwave Theory Technol.*, MTT-9 (1961) 459
- [71] Kaminow I P ; in *An Introduction to Electro-optic Devices*, Acadmic Press, New york, cha.(ii) (1974) 40
- [72] Ashkin A and Ballman A A ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 9, (1966) 72
- [73] Kalashnikov V L and Poloiko I G ; *Quantum Electron. (UK)*, 24, 10 (1994) 880

2.2 Theories of Crystal Growth

Crystal growth generally involves a sequence of processes :

- 1) Diffusion of the molecules of the crystallizing substance through the surrounding medium to the surface of the crystal.

2.1 Introduction

The study of growth & characterization of single crystals is receiving increasing importance due to their various applications in solid state technology and laser technology, which forms the back bone of modern scientific developments.

Modern solid state electronics and photonics are based on a crystal growth revolution which have now made possible the growth of large dislocation free crystals of silicon and GaAs, the production of laser crystals like ruby, sapphire, Nd-YAG and nonlinear crystals. Crystal growth will play a key role in the coming years of science & technology [1], which requires pure perfect crystals in bulk.

In the fields of conversion of solar energy, information storage & manipulation in large capacity digital computers, crystal bubble memories, improved artificial sensors and improved communications, single crystals may find extensive applications. As a result, an enormous amount of labour and care have been lavished on the development of different growth techniques each having its own importance and potentialities.

Ritzel [8], Kossel [9], Stranek [10], Wagner [11]

2.2 Theories of Crystal Growth

Crystal growth generally occurs by means of the following sequence of processes :

- 1) Diffusion of the modules of the crystallizing substance through the surrounding environment (or solution) to the surface of the crystal.
- 2) Diffusion of these modules over to the surface of the crystal to special sites on the surface.
- 3) Incorporation of modules in to the crystal at the sites.
- 4) Diffusion of heat of crystallization away from the Crystal surface.

The rate of crystal growth may be limited by any of these four steps. The initial formation of the centres from which crystal growth proceeds is known as nucleation. There is available voluminous literature on the various existing theories of crystal growth. These have been extensively covered by Buckley [2], Verma and Krishna [3], Strickland constable [4] and others.

In the first quantitative theory of crystal growth given by Gibbs [5] based on thermodynamic grounds, an analogy is made between the growth of a water droplet in a mist and growth of a crystal. Curie [6] calculated the shape and form of the crystal in equilibrium with solution or vapour consistent with the condition of possessing a minimum surface free energy. This theory is further extended and modified by Wulffs [7]. Mare and Ritzal [8], Kossal [9], Stranski [10], Volmer [11] and others

build up a conventional theory on the mechanism of crystal growth. Here the growth proceeds by the addition of modules at the so called kink sites. Both these theories suggested that growth occurs by spreading and piling up of layers of constant thickness across the face.

During crystal growth, the crystal faces may possess a different surface chemistry and can grow by a number of different interface kinetic mechanisms which depend, in turn on additional factors including supersaturation, solvent, additives etc. The seminal work of Burton, Cabera and Frank (BCF) [12] in 1951 laid the foundation for our understanding of the structure of the crystal growth interface and enabled the definition of three mechanistic regimes of crystal growth which defines the relation between the surface growth rate (R) and supersaturation σ , thus

- 1) At low supersaturation, the BCF mechanism requires screw dislocations to provide crystal surface attachment sites to enable growth at the crystal - liquid interface. Here the growth rate law becomes $R \propto \sigma^2$.
- 2) At moderate supersaturation, surface integration can take place by 2D surface nucleation via a birth and spread (BS) mechanism [13]. Here the growth rate law becomes $R \propto \sigma^{5/6}$.
- 3) At high supersaturations, we have a rough interface growth (RIG) model. Interface roughening [14] takes place and growth can proceed without the need to form any well-defined surface layers at the interface. Here the growth rate law becomes

$R \propto \sigma$.

The simple rules for the selection of likely growth forms were first proposed by Bravais (1866) and Friedel (1907) and later improved by Donnay and Harker (1937) [15]. This approach was referred as the BFDH method [16], which suggested the importance of a crystallographic form $\{hkl\}$ which is directly dependent upon the corresponding inter planar spacing d_{hkl} after making allowance for space group symmetry. In 1955, Hartman and Perdok [17] using their periodic bond chain theory (PBC) were amongst the first to attempt to quantify crystal morphology in terms of the interaction energy between crystallizing units. Burton et al [12] calculated that a large supersaturation of atleast 25% - 30% is necessary to obtain an observable growth rate in order to have the layer by layer growth of an ideal crystal. Hence the probable role of screw dislocation on the growth process was pointed out by Frank [18]. Accordingly, the emergence of screw dislocation on a crystal face produces a ledge or permanent step. As the growth proceeds on the surface, the ledge winds up to a spiral centered on the dislocation itself. Such dislocations have been revealed by electron microscopy and in other ways on the surface of many crystals [19]. Jagodzinski [20,21] suggested that high energy is required for screw dislocation and hence it cannot come from the crystal structure until the crystal has grown to a considerable volume. The screw dislocation will therefore play a role only in the later stages of growth, thereby determining the surface structure but not the crystal structure.

2.3 Different methods of crystal growth

The enormous flow of information related to the growth of single crystals can be broadly classified into the following groups.

1. Solution growth
2. Melt growth
3. Vapour growth
4. Solid state growth

These four groups can be further classified into various subgroups.

2.3.1 Growth of Single Crystals from Solution :

If a suitable solvent is found, crystals can be grown at temperature below the melting point of the crystal. Growth from solution is the only alternative, if the substance decomposes below its melting point or undergoes a phase change. The choice of solvent is very important, which should have low viscosity and should not react with the container or the atmosphere. The volatility of the solvent must be controllable, over a wide range. It is easier to grow large perfect crystals if the solute has solubility, exceeding 5 mole percent. The growth rates by this method are much smaller than the growth rates from the melt. It is extremely difficult to produce spontaneous nucleation in a solution in such a manner that only a single or even a very few nuclei are formed. If large crystals are to be grown from

solution, seeding is essential. Almost 80% organic and inorganic optical, non-linear crystals are grown by this method.

(a) Crystal growth from evaporation/ slow cooling of solution :

A saturated solution contains the maximum amount of material which can be dissolved. The solubility of a material depends upon the temperature at constant pressure.

The solubility may be influenced by the impurity in solute and pH value of the solvent.

Any crystal growth process from aqueous solution involves 3 stages.

- (i) Attainment of Supersaturation
- (ii) Formation of critical nucleus &
- (iii) Growth of a Crystal

The state of supersaturation is an important factor of crystal growth. The formation of nucleus in the absence of any defect requires a supersaturation of about 25 to 50 percent. Supersaturation may be obtained by cooling, evaporation, or rarely by the addition of other materials. For most solution techniques, 2 stage growth process is used. First, by allowing slow evaporation or cooling of a saturated or supersaturated solution, small crystals are obtained. Secondly, some of these crystals are selected and used as seeds to grow larger ones.

The seed crystals are inserted in a saturated or slightly supersaturated solution of same material. In one technique, the

temperature is lowered slowly as to reduce the solubility which produces crystallization. In another technique, the temperature is held constant but the solvent is permitted to evaporate. The seed crystals may be rotated if necessary during the growth.

Using this method, large, inorganic nonlinear crystals like NaNO_2 , ADP, KDP, KTP, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, BST, lithium formate, Strontium formate, Sodium formate etc [22 - 31] and organic nonlinear crystals like POM, MBA-NP, DAD, COANP, m-NA, DAN, MNA, MAP, MMONS, Benzophenone, Urea, NPPA, PNP, LAP, NMBA, NPP, NMBA, APDA, Indole 3-aldehyde [32 - 50] etc are grown.

(b) Flux growth :

Flux growth is the term most commonly used to describe the growth of crystals from molten salt solvents at high temperatures.

The crystals like BaTiO_3 [51], YIG, GGG, $(\text{Pb}_2\text{CoWO}_6)$ [52], (KTP) [53], (PbTiO_3) (Most of oxides), (KTA) [55 -56], $(\text{Fe}_2\text{ZnO}_4)$, $(\beta\text{BaB}_2\text{O}_4)$ [54], (LiB_3O_5) are grown using this method.

(c) Hydrothermal Growth :

This method is commonly used to grow "quartz" single crystals as these crystals can not be grown by any other crystal growth techniques. Since the process of hydro thermal growth of crystals is similar to the quartz growth in nature, it provides information about the conditions under which this naturally occurring material might have grown.

The various other types of crystals grown in this method are diamond [57], CaCO_3 [58], AlPO_4 , ZnO [59], Al_2O_3 , Quartz [60-63], $\text{Y}_3\text{Fe}_5\text{O}_{12}$ [64], ZnS [61], KTP [62] etc.

(d) **L.P.E. growth :**

Liquid phase epitaxial growth is most widely used now a days for the preparation of GaP, GaAs, GaAlAs, YIG, YAG, GGG etc., materials for the fabrication of a variety of solid state devices including light emitting diodes, bubble memory devices and solar cells [65-68].

2.3.2 Growth of single crystals from melt :

In this case the material to be grown as a crystal is placed in a suitable container and heated in a furnace above the melting point. To initiate the growth, the melt is cooled from above the equilibrium melting point and there is a rapid transition from a state in which the substance is completely molten above the melting point to a state such that the system is completely solid below the melting point. The crystal growers problem is to control this transition in such a way that good quality single crystals are formed. This is achieved by permitting at a time, a small volume of the melt to pass through transition temperature to crystallize. Usually, the crystal growth from pure melt is successfully controlled by controlling the thermal gradient. The important types of melt growth methods are

(a) Czochralski crystal pulling method :

Crystal pulling or the Czochralski technique (1917) is a popular method of crystal growth from the melt because it can produce large (up to several inches) dislocation free crystals in a relatively short period of time.

The inorganic crystals like Ruby, Sapphire, group III - IV compound semiconductor crystals like GaAs, GaP etc. [69 - 72], and organic crystals like benzophenone, urea [73, 74] are among the many crystals that are routinely grown by this technique.

(b) Bridgman - Stockbargar technique :

In this technique, directional solidification is carried out in a crucible to produce a single crystal from melt.

The technique is best suited for low melting point materials. Several organic NLO crystals like NPAN [75], DAN [76], NMBA [46], MNA [77], benzil [78] and m-NA, MAP, NPP [80] etc., and inorganic crystals like alkali halides, LBO [79] and some semiconductors like GaAs etc are grown using this technique. This method cannot be used to grow single crystals of various shapes and size.

(c) Zone melting and zone refining techniques :

Zone melting is the name of a family of methods for purifying elements and compounds and for preparing materials of desired composition. In this method, a short liquid region or zone travels slowly through a relatively long charge or ingot of

solid. As the zone travels, it redistributes impurities (solutes) along the charge.

Zone refining is the most important zone melting method. In zone refining, a number of molten zones are passed along the charge in one direction. Each zone carries a fraction of the impurities to the end of the charge, there by purifying the remainder. Zone refining was introduced in the early 1950's to purify germanium and silicon for the transistors. The zone melting methods are reviewed by Pfann [81].

2.3.3 Growth of single crystals from vapour :

In the case of the materials which decompose or sublime before melting at atmospheric pressure and for which a suitable solvent is not available, crystal can be grown conveniently from the vapour phase. It is generally more difficult to grow large crystals from the vapour than from the melt or from the solution. However the process does offer some advantages. In this case, the degree of supersaturation is more easily controlled than during the growth from melt. The important types of vapour growth methods are

(a) Sublimation - condensation technique :

In this method, a substance is directly converted from the solid into the gas and back again to the solid without the intermediate liquid step. High vacuum assists the process and heating or cooling the said crystal or the area where the growth

initiation is desired, is often required. Using this method, single crystals of Cd, Zn, Au, Ag, Fe, ZnS, etc. can be grown.

(b) Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD) :

The chemical vapour deposition describes a very broad group of processes all of which use a chemical reaction between gaseous reagent at or near a heated surface to deposit the material on the surface. The volatile chemical compounds are used to transport materials. The actual deposition is achieved by a chemical reaction such as reduction or thermal decomposition. Several authors have reviewed the CVD technique [82-86].

(c) Metal - organo CVD (MOCVD) :

MOCVD is a very promising crystal growth technique which uses metal alkyls and hydrides as source materials in a cold walled reactor [87,88]. This method is more advantageous than other vapour phase growth techniques because the reactions are irreversible, very abrupt transitions in composition of epitaxial structures are possible [89].

(d) Molecular Beam Epitaxy (MBE) :

In this process, the epitaxial films are deposited from molecular or atomic beams on a heated substrate under ultrahigh vacuum (UHV) conditions. The MBE growth process involves adsorption of the constituent atoms or molecules, surface migration and dissociation of the adsorbed molecules and incorporation of the atoms to the substrate resulting in nucleation and growth.

2.4 Crystal growth in gel media

2.4.1 General considerations

Gel growth in aqueous solution is now a wide spread technique for production of high quality crystals in a large range of solubilities and temperature [90-96]. Thermodynamic considerations reveal that since the growth proceeds at near ambient temperature, the grown crystals would contain relatively lesser concentration of non equilibrium defects. The growing crystals are held in the gel in a strain-free manner, thus limiting effects due to impact on the bottom or the sides of the container [97]. In addition, in this method almost complete suppression of large scale movements like convection is achieved which otherwise can be harmful to the crystal perfection. The presence of a gel does not effect considerably the rate of diffusion of crystallizing species [98] and the related crystal growth kinetics. Hence mass transfer occurs only by diffusion. For mineral materials, it had been demonstrated that some defects are related to the presence of convection in the solution growth [99]. But in gel method, the diffusion rate can be controllable since, the gels are net-work of cavities of several tens to several hundreds of angstroms in diameter, communicating through slightly smaller orifices [100]. Further more, gels are likely to capture, dust and other solid particles which when present in solution during their formation can be engulfed in the growing crystal and give rise to dislocations [101].

2.4.2 Gel preparation and properties

A gel is a highly viscous two component system rich in liquid and having fine pores in it. Hence it can be regarded as a loosely inter linked polymeric chains either rectangled in the case of physical gel or cross linked in the case of chemical gels. For physical gels the gelling process is achieved through variation of physical parameters. For chemical gels, the gelling process results from a polymerization reaction. There are various types of physical and chemical gels. But silica hydrogel is most commonly used due to its better stability than all organic gels [102,103], though in certain specific cases gelatin gel [104], agar gel [105] and polyacrylamide gel [106] have been preferred. In some other cases, both inorganic and organic gels have been found equally good for crystal growth.

The silica hydrogel is prepared by mixing aqueous solution of sodium meta silicate with mineral or organic acid of appropriate strength. The pH of gel medium is maintained by adjusting the density of the sodium metasilicate solution and the acidity of the resulting solution which determines the course and rate of polymerization. As like other gels, silica hydrogels are also mechanically and optically isotropic except when under strain.

The gelling process itself takes an amount of time which can vary widely, from minutes to many days, depending on the nature of the material, its temperature and history. Care should however

be taken while mixing the silicate solution and the acids in order to prevent the formation of air bubbles inside the gel. If these air bubbles get fixed, they grow larger and lenticular in shape during the period of gel setting and it is impossible to knock them away from the growth medium. Since such bubbles have a degree of long range order, they always tend to hinder the growth of the larger crystals [107].

The mechanical properties of fully developed gels can vary widely, depending on the density and on the precise conditions during gelling. The internal surface area of the gel depends on the detailed circumstances during gel preparation [108] like silica to water ratio. It is often reported that reagents diffuse as rapidly through very dilute gel as through water but it depends on the pore size of the gel and the amount of interaction between the solute and internal gel surfaces. But there is no evidence that the diffusion constants of small atoms and ions are greatly influenced by the silica gel density, as long as the density is low. Most gels are mechanically and optically isotropic except under strain. However, according to Thiele and Micke [109], the presence of high ion concentrations can bring about the formation of unstrained non isotropic gels by the alignment of nonspherical sol particles.

2.4.3 Gelling mechanism and structure of silica hydro gel

Gels are formed from suspensions or solutions by the establishment of a three dimensional system of cross linkages

between the molecules of one component. The second component permeates this system as a continuous phase. A gel can thus be regarded as a loosely inter linked polymer. When the dispersion medium is water, the material should be called as "hydro gel" to distinguish it from the brittle solids which are often obtained by subsequent drying. Silica hydro gel structures depend significantly on the method of preparation and thus depend in particular on whether the gels are made by neutralization of sodium metasilicate or by the hydrolysis of siloxanes. Lefauchaux et al [110] has suggested that when sodium metasilicate goes into solution, monosilic acid is produced in accordance with dynamic equilibrium.

Monosilic acid can polymerize with the liberation of water.

This can happen again and again until a three dimensional network of Si-O links is established as in silica.

The above network shows the continuous polymerization process by which water accumulates on top of the gel surface. This phenomenon is known as syneresis. Much of the water formed during gelatination is believed to have its origin in the above condensation process and some may arise from purely mechanical factors connected with a small amount of shrinkage. The gelling process is more complicated than the above equations suggest. This is mainly because the time required for gelatination is very sensitive to pH. Thus the role of acid (organic or mineral) used to neutralize NaOH formed to obtain desired pH [111,112]. It is found that during the gel formation process, two types of ions are produced H_3SiO_4^- and $\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_4^{2-}$ which depend on the hydrogen ion concentration. H_3SiO_4^- is favored by moderately low pH values and is held to be responsible for the initial formation of long chain polymerization products [113,114]. In due course, cross linkages are formed between these chains and these contribute to the sharp increase of viscosity that signals the onset of

gellation. The linkage process produces sol particles which then continue to associate to form a gel. Very high as well as very low pH values evidently lead to high surface charges (negative or positive respectively) which inhibit gelation. However, the pH of gelling solution can not remain constant during gelling process. The pH may change due to the presence of other ions also. Greenberg and Sinclair [114] also reported on the fact that the gelling rate is rather sensitively temperature dependent.

Under X-rays, the patterns of silica hydrogel are same as those structures which are occasionally observed for silica glass, except for the more intense background which indicates that gel is less homogeneous [115,116]. By observing the progressive sharpening of the interference lines, structural changes which take place during gel aging can be followed. The gravimetric determination of nitrogen absorption [117,113] and subsequent calculation of the internal surface area from the absorption isotherms, leads to the establishment of models of the internal structure and to estimate the average pore size. Such estimates yield effective pore diameters of the order 50 - 160 Å for silica gel of varying density. In this way, it has also been possible to show that syneresis has little effect on the average pore size. The basic gel structure which depends on the nature of materials used, pH, temperature etc, affect the crystal growth characteristics including nucleation, growth rate and ultimate crystal size.

2.4.4 Different methods of crystal growth in gel

The enormous flow of information related to crystal growth in gel has been divided into the following four basic parts, each one of these having special advantages.

- 1) Crystal growth by reaction
- 2) Crystallization by complex dilution method.
- 3) Crystal growth by reduction of solubility.
- 4) Crystal growth by chemical reduction.

Arora [118] Patel and Rao [119] have reviewed the existing information on the different methods of growth of single crystals in gel.

(i) Crystal growth by reaction

Most of the work on crystal growth in gels has been done by reaction method. It has a special advantage of growing single crystals which are mostly insoluble (or slightly soluble) in water and which decompose before reaching their melting point. The requirements to grow single crystals by this method are (1) the reactants employed here must be soluble in the solvent (usually water) and product crystal must be less soluble [120] (2) The gel must remain stable in the presence of the reacting solutions and must not react with these solutions or with the product formed. (3) Some solubility of the product crystals is required in order to grow crystals of any size [121].

In this method, two aqueous solutions of soluble salts suitably chosen are allowed to react by the process of diffusion through gel, so that there occurs a slow and controlled segregation of ions and molecules resulting in the precipitation of an insoluble phase as the crystal.

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(ii) Crystallization by complex dilution method

Crystal growth by complex dilution method was first reported by O'conner et al [122]. The general feature of this method is the existence of some soluble material which itself increases the solubility of the material of interest in a nonlinear manner with concentration of the soluble material by complex formation in solution or by formation of a soluble double salt. In the crystal growth process, the concentration of the combined solution is reduced by diffusion in to the gel. Because, the solubility of the material is a nonlinear function of the concentration which may reappear.

PHD
535
N96/AIT; 1

In this variant of the method pioneered by O'conner et al [122] and Armington et al [123,124] for the growth of cuprous chloride crystals, the material is first complexed by means of another reagent (hydrochloric acid) and allowed to diffuse into a gel free of active reagents. Decomplexing sets in, with increasing dilution and leads to the high supersaturation necessary for crystal growth. Cuprous chloride is interesting as a possible laser modulator in which the modulation can be achieved by transverse electro-optic effect [125]. The method has been successfully used to grow silver iodide [126], silver

bromide and silver chloride [127]. The decomplexing procedure is thus a versatile and valuable addition to the repertoire of gel growth method. A general discussion on complexing and decomplexing as suitable procedure of crystal growth in gel is provided in the papers of Nicolau [128,129] and Nicolau and Joly [130].

(iii) Crystal growth by reduction of solubility

This method is particularly suitable for growing single crystals of highly water soluble substance. Glocker and Soest [120] first reported the growth of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (ADP) single crystals by this method. The substance to be grown is dissolved in water and incorporated with the gel forming solution. After the setting of gel, a solution which reduces the solubility of the substance is added over the gel to induce crystallization. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KDP) crystals have been grown by adding ethyl alcohol over the gel, containing a saturated solution of KDP [131,132]. The formation of the crystals is due to the reduction of solubility of KDP in the liquid phase by diffusing alcohol.

The single crystals such as Triglycine sulfate [133], antimony sulphur iodides [134] have been grown by different crystal growers using this method.

(iv) Crystal growth by chemical reduction

This method is advantageous only to grow crystals containing metal ions. The gel is prepared by adding the complex solution of crystalline substrate on which new crystals are grown.

the metal to the gelling solution. A reducing agent is added from the top of the set gel, hence the name chemical reduction method. The first report by this method has been described by Hatschek and Simon [135, 136]. They grew gold crystals by adding 8 % oxalic acid solution over the gel which containing gold chloride solution. Krotochvil and coworkers [137] grew gold crystals of triangular and hexagonal habits. Selenium [138], lead [139], nickel and cobalt [140] etc have been grown by this method.

2.4.5 Nucleation and growth mechanism

Gel media supports the crystal and at the same time yields to its growth without exerting major forces upon it. Crystallization in gel can be regarded as a two stage process - nucleation and growth. A complete understanding of the crystal growth would require the knowledge of many disciplines such as equilibrium thermodynamics, irreversible thermodynamics, chemistry of surface sciences, heat transfer, mass transfer, crystallography etc.

Crystal growth in gel is evidently a variant of growth in solution with additional complications arising from the presence of gel. The application of dislocation theory to the problem of crystal growth [141-143] shows that the crystals continue to grow, once growth has started. Two basic nucleation mechanisms have been recognized : Homogeneous nucleation which does not fundamentally call for the presence of foreign substances and heterogeneous nucleation, which demands a preexisting foreign crystalline substrate on which new material can be deposited from

the vapour, the melt or the solution. In any reasonably well optimized gel system, only a few crystals grow to macroscopic size and the identification of their nucleation mechanism is not a simple matter. The heterogeneous nucleation has been demonstrated by the deliberate addition of foreign nuclei [144]. The problem is as certain whether homogeneous nucleation which depends on the formation of a native nucleus of critical size, as governed by thermodynamic consideration, is possible in gels. The observations of Halberstadt and Henisch [145] support this belief that homogeneous nucleation can and does occur in gels.

All theories of homogeneous nucleation involves the concept of the critical nucleus. It is investigated that as a result of statistical accident a number of atoms or molecules can come together and form a rudimentary crystal. Simple energetic considerations show that this crystal is likely to dissolve again unless it reaches a certain critical size. Beyond that size the energy relations favour continued growth. It means that the assembly is stable under the prevailing conditions. If the conditions change, the growth rate will adjust itself accordingly and may even become negative.

The physical reality of critical nucleus was first demonstrated by Ostwald [144,146]. The success of Volmer's theory [147] of nucleation in condensation lead to the early attempt of its application to solids.

To suppress nucleation, whether it is homogeneous or heterogeneous and to stabilize the concentration gradients in the

neighbourhood of growing crystals by suppression currents are the two principle functions of gel. In all gel systems, crystals become increasingly scarce and more perfect with increasing the distance from gel interface as the slow diffusion leads to more perfect crystals.

As far as the mechanism by which crystals grow in gels, there have been evidences to two dimensional pilling and spreading of growth layers, predominantly taking place [148] from one or more initiation centers. One is therefore tempted to make a logical comparison with solution growth. When single crystals of slightly soluble salts are grown from highly supersaturated solution which just remain stable over long period by slow evaporation or cooling, the crystals never grow larger, because the supply of solute to crystal surface is still extremely feeble. The fact that large crystals are obtained in gels proves that the supersaturation near the surface of these crystals must be much higher in gel than in solution. This suppression prevents the development of heterogeneous nuclei, so only homogeneous nucleation is left which is known to occur at high supersaturation only.

Gels are obviously permeable, but the fact that the convection currents are suppressed can easily be verified. In absence of convection, the only mechanism available for the supply of solute to the growing crystal is diffusion. According to Fick's law,

$$J = - D \text{ grad } C \quad \text{-----}(2.61)$$

and

$$(dC/dt) = D \nabla^2 C \quad \text{-----}(2.62)$$

where J is the quantity of matter transporting in the direction of concentration gradient per unit area perpendicular to ΔC .

Assuming that the precipitates are not too close to one another as is true in gel growth, the concentration in space around the crystal of radius R is the function of distance ' x ' from the center, and the boundary conditions become

$$C(x, 0) = C_{\infty}$$

$$C(R, t) = S \quad \text{-----}(2.63)$$

$$C(\infty, t) = C_{\infty}$$

The solution of diffusion equation (2.61) and (2.62) gives the radius ' R ' as the function of the speed ' V ' of the advancing growth fronts in gel.

$$R = [D V (C_{\infty} - S) t]^{1/2} \quad \text{-----}(2.64)$$

where t is the time.

Since each particle is to be treated independently, the factor $V (C_{\infty} - S)$ is small and hence equation (2.64) reduces to

$$R = (Dt)^{1/2} \quad \text{-----}(2.65)$$

This equation is typical of one dimensional diffusion process and has been experimentally verified by Blank [149], Liaw

and Faust [150], Patel and Arora [151] and Patel and George [152]. Once new solute has been brought to the surface by diffusion, growth takes place either via screw dislocation or via two dimensional surface nucleation. The ultimate size of the crystal depends on two factors, one due to the progressive exhaustion of the reagents and other due to pH and related considerations.

2.4.6 Advantages of the gel techniques

When single crystals are grown from melt, vapour or solution at high temperature, usually crystalline imperfections will occur due to lattice disruptions by thermal vibrations. Also point defects and lattice strains are frequently introduced in to the growing matrix during the range of cooling cycle. Among all methods of crystallization at room temperature, the gel method has following advantages:

- 1) The crystals can be observed practically during all stages of their growth.
- 2) The gel medium prevents convection currents and turbulence.
- 3) Crystals are not altered by temperature and pressure. Therefore, products of this technique are of high perfection.
- 4) By remaining chemically inert and harmless, the gel framework acts like a three dimensional crucible in which the crystal nuclei are delicately held in the position, thereby preventing damage, if any, due to impact with their bottom or the walls of the container.

- 5) The gel is soft and yields no mechanical strains to the growing crystals.
- 6) Crystals with different morphologies and size can be obtained by controlling diffusion rates and nucleation probability.
- 7) The method is simple, inexpensive and most suitable even in smaller laboratories.
- 8) Since the gel reduces the speed of chemical reaction, crystals could be made to grow much larger than those grown by a similar reaction in water or molten state.

Various sort of crystals - ionic, organic, metallic even biological crystals have been grown by the gel method.

2.5 Objectives and scope of the present work

The importance of growth of nonlinear single crystals and various techniques for the growth of these crystals have been already emphasized in the earlier sections. The growth of these crystals in bulk, in a most perfect form by a simplest, easy and low cost method is essential. In this regard, it is found that gel technique is a better method for the growth of single crystals compared to other methods, due to its simplicity and low cost. This is proved to be the only suitable method for the growth of materials which are sparingly soluble in water or decompose at higher temperature.

The aim of present work is two fold, one is to investigate new colour of centered row crystals for the application of optoelectronic devices which include memory devices, colour

centered lasers and for third harmonic applications and the new nonlinear organic crystals which have good SHG efficiency, low cut-off wavelength and better crystalline properties. The second is to increase the versatility of the gel technique of crystal growth by growing these optoelectronic and some nonlinear single crystals of both inorganic and organic materials using silica hydrogel and to test the wider suitability of this technique. In this attempt, it is planned to add several variations to gel technique, to grow good quality, large size electro-optic and nonlinear single crystals which include, gel incorporation, solubility reduction cum chemical reaction, gel-solution techniques etc.

Further, it is proposed to study the gel set conditions, influence of various parameters such as gel pH, gel density, gel aging, concentration of feed solutions, temperature of the systems etc on crystal growth.

The characterization includes, the study of purity of grown crystals by means of chemical analysis, atomic absorption spectroscopy, powder X-ray diffraction, IR spectroscopy, mass spectroscopy, NMR spectroscopy and single crystal structural analysis.

For efficient nonlinear crystals, for device fabrication, the electrical conductivity and dielectric constants must be as low as possible. Thus the dc, ac conductivity and dielectric properties of the grown nonlinear crystals along different crystallographic directions are studied at different frequency

and different temperatures. Also it is planned to study the behaviour of these crystals under intense magnetic field.

In order to use any NLO crystal in device fabrication, their mechanical and thermal behaviour must be in favourable level. In this respect the present work also includes the study of microhardness of nonlinear crystals along different directions and the process of thermal decomposition and phase transition of these crystals by means of TG, DTA and DSC studies.

For conversion of semiconductor laser light into UV region by means of SHG, the transmission of these crystals must be very good in the UV region. Thus the low wavelength transparency is important in a good NLO crystal. Hence it is also planned to study optical absorption properties of grown crystals to examine their suitability for UV conversion.

In case of optoelectronic colour centered crystals it is proposed to study the nature of colour center excitations by means of X-ray irradiation and emissions of these crystals by means of thermoluminescence.

Another important part of this work is to study the SHG efficiency of some of the grown crystals as a function of increase in input intensity of the laser light. It is also planned to study the electro-optic modulation of light by means of an applied half-wave voltage in some of these nonlinear crystals and the suitability of fabrication of device using them for electro-optic amplitude and phase modulation. The ultimate and wider application of these crystals in photonics and optical

communication mainly requires the ability of confining light beam in these crystals, which is also planned to achieve by means of an attempt on the possibility of the fabrication of waveguide

- structure, by heavy ion irradiation.
- [1] Lauder R A ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, **4**, 23 (1967)
 - [2] Buckley H A ; *Crystal Growth*, Chapman and Hall, London (1952)
 - [3] Verma A R and Krishna P ; *Polymer Physics and Crystal Growth* (John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1976)
 - [4] Strickland constable R F ; *Kinetics and Mechanism of Crystallization* (Academic Press, London) (1965)
 - [5] Gibbs J W ; *Collected works* (London, New York, 1878)
 - [6] Curie P ; *Bull. Soc. France, Phys.*, **8**, (1878) 171
 - [7] Wulff G ; *Z. Krist.*, **34**, (1901) 419
 - [8] Mare R and Ritzel A ; *Z. Physik*, **76**, (1911) 304
 - [9] Kossel W ; *Lachr. Ges. Wiss. Göttingen Nachr. Phys. Math. Kl.*, (1927) 135
 - [10] Stranski I N ; *Z. Physik*, **136** (1938) 209
 - [11] Volmer M ; *Kinetic der Phasenbildung* (Zurich, Leipzig, Berlin and Leipzig (1939)
 - [12] Burton M K, Cabrera N and Frank F C ; *Phil. Mag.*, **6**, (1951) 243, (1951) 299
 - [13] Bleier B H and Jackson K A ; *Crystal Growth*, ed. E. Kaldic and H T. Schwan, (New York, North-Holland) (1977) 80-114
 - [14] Jackson K A ; *Liquid Metals and Solidification*, ed. J. Crayevitch (Clarendon ; American Nuclear Society, London) 174-186

References

- [1] Laudise R A ; *J. Crystal Growth* 24-25 (1974) 32
- [2] Buckley H A ; *Crystal Growth* (John Wiley and sons New York) (1952)
- [3] Verma A R and Krishna P ; *Polymer Phisms and Poly typism in crystals* (John Wiley and sons New York) (1968)
- [4] Strickland constable R F ; *Kinetics and Mechanism of Crystallization* (Academic Press, London) (1968)
- [5] Gibbs J W ; *Collected works* (Longmans Green and Co. London) (1878)
- [6] Curie P ; *Bull. Soc. France. Mines*, 8, (1885) 145.
- [7] Wulff G ; *Z. Krist.* 34, (1901) 449.
- [8] Mare R and Ritzel A ; *Z Physi. Chem.* 76, (1911) 584
- [9] Kossel W ; *Lachr. Gus. Wiss. Goettingen Maths Phys. KI*, 11a (1927) 135
- [10] Stranski I N ; *Z. Phys. chem.* 136 (1958) 259
- [11] Volmer M ; *Kinetic der Phasen Building steickopff Dresden and Leipzig* (1939)
- [12] Buton W K Cabrera N and Frank F C ; *Phil. Trans. R. Soc.* 243, (1951) 299
- [13] Glmer G H and Jackson K A *Crystal growth and materials*, ed. E Kaldis and H T School (Amsterdam : North Holland) (1977) 80-114
- [14] Jackson K A ; *Liquid Metals and solidification*. Ed. A. Craievitch (Claneland : American Society of Metals) (1958) 174-186

- [15] Donnay J D and Harker D ; *Am. Mineral* 22 (1937) 446
- [16] Phillips F C ; *An Introduction to crystallography* 3rd Ed.
(London Longmans green)
- [17] Wartman P and Perdok W G ; *Acta Crystallagr.* 8 (1955) 49
- [18] Frank F C ; *Discuss Faraday Soc* 5 (1949) 67
- [19] Verma A R ; *Crystal Growth and Dislocations* (Butterworth, London) (1953)
- [20] Jagodzinski H ; *Acta. Cryst.* 8 (1954) 279
- [21] Jagodzinski H ; *Never. Iaharb. Miner Monatah* 3 (1954) 49
- [22] Hoffman B and Vogt H ; *J. Phys C*, 6 (1973) 543
- [23] Holden A N ; *Disc. Faraday Soc.* 5 (1949) 312
- [24] Sasaki K ; *J. Crystal Growth* 99(1990) 820
- [25] Bordui P F, Jacco J C and Zola J J ; *J. Crystal Growth* 84 (1987) 403
- [26] Defan C, and Zhengtang Y ; *J. Crystal Growth* 79 (1986) 974
- [27] Maiwa K, Tsukamoto K and Sunagawa I ; *J. Crystal Growth* 102 (1991) 43
- [28] Youping H, Gembo S, Feng P and Rihong J ; *J. of crystal growth* 113 (1991) 161.
- [29] Singh S, Bonner W A and Van Viter L G ; *Appl. Phys Lett* 17 (1970) 292
- [30] Deserno U ; *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* QE-8, (1972) 608
- [31] Hiromasa I, Hatsuhiko N and Humio I ; *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* QE-10, 2, (1974) 247

- [32] Hirele R, Badan J and Zyss J ; *J. Crystal Growth* 69 (1984) 545
- [33] Hooper R M, McArdle B J, Narang R S and Sherwood J N ; *Crystal Growth*, ed B Pumphin (Newyork Peramon) (1985)
- [34] Bao Tomono, Lyong Sun Pu and Shinsuke U ; *J. Phys D: Appl Phys.* 26 (1993) b 217.
- [35] Gunter P, Boss hard K, Sutter and Arned H ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 50, 9, (1987) 486.
- [36] Southgate P D and Hall D S ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 18, 10 (1971) 456
- [37] Baumert J C, Twieg R J, and Dirk C W ; *Appl. Phys. Lett* 51, 19 (1987) 1484
- [38] Lenine B F, Bethea C B and Bernstein J L ; *J. Appl. Phys.* 50, 4 (1979) 2523
- [39] Oudar J L and Hierle R ; *J. Appl Phys.* 48, 7, (1977) 2699
- [40] Bierlein J D, Cheng L K, Wang Y, and Tam W ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 56, 5, (1990) 423.
- [41] Klapper H ; *Chracterization of crystal Growth defects by X-ray methods*, ed. B K Tanner (Plenum, N.Y. 1980) 133
- [42] Tachibana M, Wang J S and Kojima K ; *J. Phys D: Appl. Phys* 26(1993) B 145
- [43] Sutter K, Gunter P, Petter W ; *J. opt. soc. Am.B*, 8,7, (1991) 1483
- [44] Hulliger J, Wang W S and Ehrensperger M ; *J. crystal growth* 100 (1990) 640
- [45] Xu D, Jiang M and Tan Z ; *Acta Chem. Sinica* 41 (1983) 570.

- [46] Shepherd E A, Sherwood J N, Simpson G S and Yoon C S ; *J. Crystal Growth* 113 (1991) 360
- [47] Youping H, Bochang W, and Rihang T ; *J. Crystal Growth* 113 (1991) 157
- [48] Bailey R T, Sherwood J N, Simpson G S and Varma K B R ; Proceedings of *Emerging Opto-electronic Technology Symposium*, Indian Institute of Science, (1992) 91
- [49] Kagawa K, Sagawa M and Ishi K ; *J. Crystal Growth* 139 (1994) 309
- [50] Jouping H, Genbo S and Rihong J ; *J. Crystal Growth* 130 (1993) 444
- [51] Belruss V, Kalnajs J, Linz a and Folweiler H C ; *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 6 (1971) 899
- [52] Sun B N, Bouterllier R and Schmid H ; *J. Crystal Growth* 112 (1991) 71
- [53] Shen H Y, Jiang A D, Shen D Z ; *IEEE J. of Quantum Electron* 28, 1 (1992) 48
- [54] Cheng L K, Bosenberg W and Tang C L ; *J. Crystal Growth* 89 (1988) 553
- [55] Cheng L K, Cheng L T, Morris P A and Bierlein J D ; *J. Crystal Growth* 137 (1994) 107
- [56] Cheng L K, Cheng L T, Morris P A and Bierlein J D ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 62 (1993) 346
- [57] Kuznetsov V A and Lobachev A N ; *Soviet Phys. Cryst.* 17 (1973) 775
- [58] Hirano S and Kikuta K ; *J. Crystal Growth* 94 (1989) 351
- [59] Sakagami N ; *J. Crystal Growth* 99 (1990) 905

- [60] Brown C S ; *Min. Mag* 29 (1952) 858
- [61] Nielsen J W and Foster F G ; *Am. Miner.* 45 (1960) 299
- [62] Laudise R A, Clava R J and Caporaso A J ; *J. Crystal Growth* 74 (1986) 275
- [63] Barns R L, Laudise R A and Shields R M ; *J. Phys. chem.* 67 (1963) 835
- [64] Kolb E D, Wood D W and Laudise R A ; *J. Appl. Phys.* 38 (1967) 1027
- [65] Nelson H ; *RCA Rev.* 24 (1963) 603.
- [66] Lorenz M R and Pilkuhn M ; *J. Appl. Phys.* 37 (1966) 4094
- [67] Trumbore F A, Kowalchi K M, and White H G ; *J. Appl. Phys.*, 38 (1967) 1987
- [68] Logan R A, White H G and Trumbore F A ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 10 (1967) 206
- [69] Carruthers J R and Winegard W C ; *Crystal Growth* (Peiser H.S. ed) Pergamon Newyork (1966) 645
- [70] Hurle D T ; *Crystal Growth* (Peiser H.S. ed) Pergamon (1967) 659
- [71] Noggle T S ; *Rev. Sci. Instr.* 24 (1953) 184
- [72] Schmid F and Viechnicki D ; *J. Crystal Growth* 11 (1971) 345
- [73] Tachibana M, Tang Q, and Kojma K ; *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* 31 (1992) 2202
- [74] Tachibana M, Wang J S and Kojma K ; *J. Phys. D : Appl. Phys.* 26 (1993) B 145
- [75] Ryuji Morita and Vidakovic P V ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 61, 24, (1992) 2854

- [76] Baumert J C, Twieg R J and Dirk C W ; *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 51
J. Crystal Growth 93:
 (1987) 1484
- [77] Fukuda T, Sano T, Hosaya S and Yoon D H ; *Cryst. Res.
 Technical Journal* 40
Technol. 29, 7, (1994) 971
- [78] Aggarwal M D, Wang W S and Tambwe M ; *J. Crystal Growth*
 University Press),
 128, 1-4, (1993) 891
- [79] Fan S, shen G, Wang W and Le X ; *J. Crystal Growth* 99
 96 (1992) 141
 (1990) 811
- [80] Badan J , Hierle R and Vidakovic P ; in *Nonlinear Optical
 Appl. Phys.* 24, 2 (1977)
 Properties of Organic Molecules and Crystals ; Vol.1,
 Brouer B, Van Rossum
 ed. Chemla D S and Zyss J, Cha II-4, Academic Press, INC
Growth, 23 (1974) 246
 (1987)
- [81] Pfann W G ; *Zone melting* 2nd ed. Wiley. New York (1966).
 (1981) 379
- [82] Reed T B, Lafleur W J and Strauss A J ; *J. Crystal Growth*
 95
 Nakada I, Ishizuki
 3-4 (1968) 115
Appl. Phys., 15 (1974)
- [83] Utech H P and Flemings M C ; *Crystal Growth* (Peiser H. S.
 96
 Khan A B, Devore T C
 ed) Pergamon Press, oxford (1967) 651
 (1974) 337
- [84] Witt A F and Gatos H C ; *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 113 (1966)
 97
 Jagannatha N ;
 808
 characterization of
- [85] Carruthers J R and Nassau K ; *J. Appl. Phys.* 39 (1968)
 Submitted to Mangalore
 5205
- [86] Tiller W A, Jackson Ka, Rutter J W, and chalmers B ; *Acta
 (1967) 155
 Met.* 1 (1953) 428.
- [87] Zilko J L ; *Handbook of thin-film deposition process and
 (1978) 345
 techniques* (Schuegrap K K ed.) Park Ridge, Noyes, 7 (1988)
- [100] Rachel R, Stears R ;
 234
 (1978) 563

- [88] Mircea A, Daste P, Kazmierski C, Carencu A.
J. Crystal Growth 93(1988) 235.
- [89] Johnston W D, Digiuseppe M A and Wilt D A ; *AT and T Technical journal* 60 (1989) 53.
- [90] Henisch H ; *Crystal Growth in Gels*, (Pennsylvania State University Press), University Park P A (1970)
- [91] Lefauchaux F, Robert M C and Manghi E ; *J. Crystal Growth*, 56 (1982) 141
- [92] Jannot B, Benhmida M, Fahli M and Jannin M ; *Japan. J. Appl. Phys.* 24, 2 (1985) 753
- [93] Brouwer G, Van Rosmalen G M and Bennema P ; *J. Crystal Growth*, 23 (1974) 228
- [94] Garcia-Ruiz J M and Amoros J L ; *J. Crystal Growth*, 55 (1981) 379
- [95] Nakada I, Ishizuki H and Ishihara N ; *Japan. J. Appl. Phys.*, 15 (1976) 919
- [96] Khan A S, Devore T C and Reed W F ; *J. Crystal Growth*, 35 (1976) 337
- [97] Jagannatha N ; in his PhD Thesis on *Gel growth and characterization of doped cadmium oxalate single crystals*, Submitted to Mangalore University, 1993.
- [98] Gits S, Lefauchaux F and Robert M C ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 84 (1987) 155
- [99] Gits S, Lefauchaux F and Robert M C ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 44 (1978) 345
- [100] Rochel R, Steere R L and Erbe E F ; *J. Chromatogr.* 166 (1978) 563

- [101] Andreatza P , Lefauchaux F and Mutaftschiev B ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 92 (1988) 415
- [102] Stong C L ; *Sci. Am.* 206 (1962) 155
- [103] Vand V, Henisch H K and McCauley J W ; *Acta Crystallogr.* A16 (1963) 137
- [104] Banks E, Chianelli R and Pintchokshy F ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 18 (1973) 185
- [105] Brezina B and Havrankova M ; *Mater. Res. Bull.* 87 (1971) 537
- [106] Tornero J D and Fayos J ; *Ferroelectrics Lett.* 12 (1990) 85
- [107] Treadwell W D and Wieland W ; *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 13 (1930) 856
- [108] Madelay J D and Sing K S ; *J. Appl. Chem.* 12 (1962) 494
- [109] Thiele H and Micke H ; *Kolloid Z*, 111, (1948) 73
- [110] Lefauchaux F, Robert M C and Ganthier M B ; *Rev. Int. Hautes Temp. Refract*, 23 (1986) 57
- [111] Hurd C B and Letteron H A ; *J. Phys. Chem.* 36 (1932) 604
- [112] Alexander G B ; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 75 (1953) 5655
- [113] Plank C J and Drake L C ; *J. Colloid Sci.* 2b (1947) 413
- [114] Greenberg S A and Sinclair D ; *J. Phys. Chem.* 59 (1955) 435
- [115] Lloyed D J ; *Colloid Chemistry* (Ed. Alexander J), Chemical Catalog Co. New York (1926) 767
- [116] Warren B E ; *Chem. Reviews*, 26 (1940) 237
- [117] Plank C J and Drake L C ; *J. Colloid Science*, 2 (1947) 399
- [118] Arora S K ; *Prog. Crystal Growth Charact.* 4 (1981) 345

- [119] Patel A R, Venkateswara Rao A ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.* 4 (1982) 527
- [120] Glocker D A and Soest I F ; *J. Chem. Phys.* 51 (1969) 3143
- [121] Holmes H N ; *J. Phys. Chem.* 21 (1970) 709
- [122] O'Connor J J, Dipietro M A and Rubin B ; *Nature*, 212 (1966) 68
- [123] Armington A F and O'Connor J J ; Air Force Cambridge Research Laboratories, (Ref 67- 0.0445), *Physics Science Research Paper No. 334* (July) 1967
- [124] Armington A F and O'Connor J J ; Air Force Cambridge Research Laboratories, (Ref 67- 304), *Physics Science Research Paper No. 325* (May) 1976
- [125] Murray L A ; *Electronic Ind.* 23 (1964) 83
- [126] Halberstadt E S ; *Nature*, 216 (1967) 574
- [127] Blank Z, Speyer D M and Okamotoy ; *Nature* 216 (1967) 1103
- [128] Nicolau I F ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 48 (1980) 51
- [129] Nicolau I F ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 48 (1980) 45
- [130] Nicolau I F and Joly J P ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 48 (1980) 61
- [131] Brezina B and Havrankora ; *Mater. Res. Bull.* 87 (1971) 537
- [132] Joshi M S and Antony A V ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 2 (1980) 31
- [133] Perison J ; *Personal Communication* (1968)
- [134] Dancy E A ; *Westing house research laboratories, Personal Communication* (1969)
- [135] Hatschek E and Simson A L ; *Kolloid Z.* 10 (1912) 265
- [136] Hatschek E and Simson A L ; *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.* 31 (1912)

- [137] Krotochril P, Srusil B and Heyrovsky M ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 3/4 (1968) 360
- [138] Blank Z, Brenner W and Okamoto Y ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 3/4 (1968) 372
- [139] Liaw H M and Faust J W ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 13/14 (1972) 471
- [140] Kurtz P F ; *Ohio J. Sci.* 66 (1966) 349
- [141] Frank F C ; *Proc. Roy Soc.* 201A (1950) 586
- [142] Frank F C ; *J. Farady Soc.* 5 (1949) 48
- [143] Burton W K, Canbrera N and Frank F C ; *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc.* 243 (1951) 299
- [144] Ostwald W ; *Phys. Chem.* 27 (1897) 365
- [145] Halberstadt E S and Henisch H K ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 3/4 (1968) 363
- [146] Ostwald W ; *Phys. Chem.* 22 (1897) 289
- [147] Volmer M ; *Kinetic der Phasen Building*, Steickopff Dresden and Leipzig (1939)
- [148] Dharmaprakash S M ; *PhD Thesis*, submitted to Mangalore University, (1985)
- [149] Blank Z ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 18 (1973) 8
- [150] Liaw H M and Faust J W ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 8 (1971) 8
- [151] Patel A R and Arora S K ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 11 (1976) 846
- [152] Patel S M and George U J ; *Electron. Mater.* 6 (1977) 499

CHAPTER 3

GROWTH OF SINGLE CRYSTALS OF SILICA DOPED NaF, NH₄F
AND NaF - NH₄F MIXED CRYSTALS IN SILICA HYDRO GEL

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1. Introduction

The crystals with optical colour centers are potential candidates in optoelectronics and laser technology. The optical colour centers are simple point defects in crystal lattices, consisting of one or more electrons trapped at an ionic vacancy in the lattice. These point defects are common in many crystalline solids and have been studied rather extensively in alkali-halide crystals. The important types of colour centers in alkali-halides are F centers, F_A centers, F_B centers, F_2 centers, F_2^+ centers, $(F_2^+)_A$ centers, $(F_2^+)^*$ centers, $F_2^+ : O^{2-}$ centers, M centers and N_2 centers. The F centers are the most fundamental colour center defects in the alkali halide lattice, which consist of a single electron trapped at a +ve ion vacancy surrounded by an essentially undisturbed lattice. If one of the neighbouring alkali ions is a substitutional alkali impurity, the center is called an F_A center. Similarly the F_B center consists of an F center beside two substitutional impurities. Two adjacent F centers along a [110] axis of the crystal form the F_2 center. The ionized counter part of F_2 center is called the F_2^+ center, which is an F_2 center with only one electron. $(F_2^+)_A$ center consists of F_2^+ center adjacent to a substitution alkali ion. The colour center $(F_2^+)^*$ consists of F_2^+ center associated with an as yet unknown defect and $F_2^+ : O^{2-}$ center consists of F_2^+ with an oxygen ion. The M centers are quasi-molecules consisting of two F centers and the N_2 center consists of three F centers in a

trigonal arrangement. The important applications of these colour centers are in colour center lasers and in optical memory devices.

The colour centers namely F_A , F_B , F_2^+ , $(F_2^+)_A$, $(F_2^+)^*$ and $F_2^+ : O^{2-}$ in alkali halides can be used to create broadly tunable, optically pumped lasers in the near infrared region [1]. These lasers may be operated in a continuous wave mode with output powers of the order of one watt, or mode locked to yield pulses of less than 100 femto second duration. Operationally, colour center lasers are analogous to dye lasers, except that instead of operating in the visible region, colour center lasers cover the infrared tuning range from 0.8 to 4 μm . Their ability to generate tunable radiation in the near infrared has made colour center lasers unique and indispensable in the study of guided wave optical devices, narrow band gap semiconductors, molecular spectroscopy and various other specialized fields [2].

The laser active colour centers possess the following two characteristics ideal for efficient, tunable operation, viz; (i) their absorption and emission bands are homogeneously broadened : all the excited centers can contribute energy to a given laser mode, and all the centers will be equally well pumped by a single line laser operating within the pump absorption band. Homogeneous broadening allows efficient single mode operation over the entire tuning range of the laser; (ii) most of the transitions involved in laser emission are fully allowed, which leads to large gain, quiet continuous wave operation (cw) and the ability to generate ultra-short pulses. The single pass

power in a 2 mm crystal containing a reasonable density of centers can exceed 100 % gain. Such gains are in dramatic contrast to those obtained in solid state lasers that use transition metal ion impurities for the gain medium. Currently, there are no stable continuous wave colour center lasers that operate below $1.4 \mu\text{m}$, which is an important region for files of optics research.

Similarly, the optical properties of colour centers (both F and M) in alkali halides and alkaline earth halides are potentially interesting in the field of opto-electronics as memory devices. The F centers in alkali halide crystals show a dichroic property of optical absorption. These crystals can be used as a holographic recording medium using standard He - Ne laser light, because of their characteristics like high resolution, relatively high sensitivity for He - Ne laser, repeatable writing and erasing process over 30 times and ability of reading the written information by plane polarized light, using their anisotropy [3]. The memory was realized by pumping the crystal using He - Ne laser or ruby laser light, which is linearly polarized in the vertical direction. The reading of the information was performed with a spectrophotometer [4].

The storage properties of M-centers have been studied in pure and Mg^{++} , Ag^+ , Li^+ doped NaF by Y. Kishi et al. [5]. The growth and colour center phenomena of some pure, mixed and doped single crystals have been extensively studied by several investigators [6 - 15]. It is reported that the colour centers

mainly detected in case of pure NaF and pure NH_4F crystals are $(\text{F}_2^+)^*$ and F centers respectively [16]. In 1985, Kolyago et al [17] studied the characteristics of $[\text{F}_2^+]_A$ centers in NaF and used it to Q-switching for an alexandrite laser light. Pulses of 80 - 100 n sec duration with a spectral width of nearly 0.1 cm^{-1} and tuning range of $0.73 - 0.783 \mu\text{m}$ were obtained under pulse periodic condition. In 1991, Mounier et al [18] fabricated a flash lamp colour center laser at room temperature with $(\text{F}_2^+)^*$ center in NaF-Mg^{2+} . The laser is tuned from 1.05 to $1.27 \mu\text{m}$ for $(\text{F}_2^+)^*$. Krishnamurthy et al [19] have described the possibility of using colour centers for third harmonic generation (THG). They proposed 4 schemes which lead to THG in Nd:YAG fundamental beam at $1.064 \mu\text{m}$ using colour centers F, F_A , F_A^+ in NaF. The schemes are resonance at fundamental frequency (w_f), resonance at $3 \cdot w_f$, two photon resonance and wave-mixing.

The growth of silica doped NaF, silica doped NH_4F and silica doped NaF - NH_4F mixed crystals using silica hydro gel are described in this chapter. Growth of single crystals by gel technique is unique among the various methods for growing microscopic crystals of the highest perfection [20]. Until now, only single crystals of CaF_2 [21] KMnF_2 , NH_4MnF_2 [22] have been successfully grown by the gel technique.

3.2 Gel incorporation method

So far only 4 methods have been reported in the literature for growing crystals by gel technique. They are the chemical reaction method, chemical reduction method, complex dilution

method and solubility reduction method. For growing silica doped NaF and NH_4F single crystals, a new variation in gel technique named as gel incorporation method is evolved. This method is used for the first time to grow crystals which incorporate some ions or molecules from the gel. In this case, the gel not only serves as the medium for crystal growth, but it gives some ions or molecules to the product crystal as impurity. As a result, we can alter some properties of the crystals including the solubility in different solvents as well as the thermoluminescence property.

3.3 Experimental details:

The experiments were conducted in test tubes of 2.5 cm X 15 cm dimensions and in beakers (250 ml). Silica hydro gel was prepared by mixing pure sodium meta silicate solution (Na_2SiO_3) of specific gravity 1.03 g/cc with 1M glacial acetic acid (volume ratio of sodium meta silicate : acetic acid as 1:1 and 1:2 were used). The gel solution thus prepared were transferred to test tubes and allowed to set at constant temperature of 25°C . Gellation occurred in about 28 hours. After the gel was set, the 1M NaF or NH_4F solution in distilled water was added slowly over the gel without disturbing the gel structure. Completion of crystallization (with crystal size up to 3 mm x 2 mm x 2mm) took about 20 days. The chemicals used were (i) Acetic acid (analaR BDH) (ii) NaF and NH_4F (CDH).

3.4 Observations and discussion

The experiments were repeated with different gel densities (1.02 to 1.07 g/cc) and different gel pH (2 to 6.5). The optimum values of gel density and gel pH for growing good quality crystals were found to be 1.04 g/cc and 4 respectively. At low pH values less than 3 and low specific gravity less than 1.03 g/cc, the time for gellation was found to increase considerably [more than 6 weeks] and the resulting gel was unstable.

3.4.1 Growth of silica doped NaF crystals

In this case, the gel is prepared by mixing pure sodium meta silicate solution of specific gravity 1.04 g/cc with 1 molar glacial acetic acid. After setting the gel, 1 M NaF is added slowly over the gel without disturbing the gel structure. The single crystal of gel grown Si-doped NaF and the same crystal during the growth in test tube are shown in figures 3.1 and 3.2 respectively.

3.4.2 Growth of silica doped NH₄F crystals

In this case, the silica hydro gel is prepared in the similar way as above and after setting the gel, the solution of NH₄F in water is added over the gel without disturbing the gel structure. The single crystal of gel grown Si-doped NH₄F is shown in figure 3.3.

Fig. 3.1 : Silica doped NaF crystal.

Fig. 3.2 : In test tube.

Fig. 3.3 : Silica doped NH F crystals.

Fig. 3.4 : Mixed crystals.

3.4.3 Growth of silica doped NaF-NH₄F mixed crystals

In this case also, the silica hydro gel is prepared in the similar way as mentioned above and after gel setting, the mixture of NaF and NH₄F solutions (1:1) is added slowly over the gel without disturbing the gel structure. Nucleation occurs after 24 hrs. inside the gel medium due to the diffusion of feed solution through the gel structure. The single crystal of gel grown Si-doped mixed NaF - NH₄F is shown in figures 3.4.

3.4.4 Effect of various parameters on crystal growth

In gel growth, nucleation control can be achieved to some extent by changing a variety of gel parameters viz, concentration of feed solution, gel density, gel pH, intermediate neutral gel column and concentration programming. The effect of concentration of feed solutions on nucleation and growth of lead sulphide, alkaline earth ortho phosphates, rare earth double sulphates, and some pure and mixed oxalates [23-28] have been extensively studied.

Transparent single crystals of calcite have been obtained between pH values of 7 and 9 [29]. Blank et al [29,30,31] show that nucleation can be controlled using intermediate neutral gels. Nucleation control for various crystals by concentration programming has been described by Henisch et al [32]. Influence of gel aging and gel density on crystal growth have been studied by several workers [33-36].

3.4.3 Growth of silica doped NaF-NH₄F mixed crystals

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(i) *Effect of pH of gel*

It is generally known that initial pH value of the gel does not indicate the acidity of the gel after gellation. Even then, these pH values will have a profound effect on the gel structure, nucleation and growth of the crystals as observed during the present investigation.

It is found that the initial pH values of 3 to 4.5 give Si-doped NaF crystals and the initial pH values of 3 to 4 give Si-doped NH_4F crystals. In case of mixed NaF- NH_4F crystals, the permissible pH value is found to be 3.5 to 4.2. When the pH is increased above the upper limit, in all these cases irregularly shaped and opaque dendritic crystals are obtained. This is due to the contamination of crystals with silica gel because as the pH increases the box-like network structure of the gel changes to loosely bound platelet structure with cross linkages, the cellular nature becomes less distinct [37]. At low pH values, no crystal formation took place for any feed solution concentration. Instead of that, only dendritic rings were formed.

The optimum pH value for the good size and quality crystal is 4 in case of si-doped NaF and 3.4 in case of si-doped NH_4F and 3.6 in case of NaF- NH_4F mixed crystals.

(ii) *Effect of gel density*

The gels of different densities are obtained by mixing sodium meta silicate solution of specific gravity 1.02 to 1.07 with 1M acetic acid, keeping the pH constant at optimized value

as mentioned earlier. It is observed that the transparency of the gel decreases as the density increases. Figure 3.5 shows the variation of time of gellation with gel density. As a general rule, very dense gels produce poor crystals. On the other hand, gels of insufficient density take long time to form and are mechanically unstable.

The observations in the present study agree with the general rule. Generally, gel density from 1.03 to 1.05 can be used for growing crystals. It is observed that nucleation density decreases as the gel density increases (figure 3.6). A greater gel density implies smaller pore size and poor communication among the pores thus decreasing the nucleation density [38].

Figure 3.5 - Plot

(iii) Effect of Gel Aging

Aging of gels plays an effective role on the growth of crystals as reported by Henisch et al [38]. To investigate the effect of aging of gels, gels of same pH and density are allowed to age for various periods before adding the feed solution. It is found that the nucleation density decreases as the aging increases. Aging of gels decreases the pore size and hence decreases the diffusion and nucleation density. The longer a gel is set at room temperature, greater the amount of water evaporation out of the gel. The effect of evaporation of water should be considered before and after the formation of gel frame work. Before the gel is set, the evaporation of water causes an increase in gel density which in turn decreases the diffusivity of NaF or NH_4F molecules in the gel, thereby decreasing the

Figure 3.5 : Plot of gel density versus gellation time.

Figure 3.6 : Plot of gel density versus nucleation density.

number of nucleation sites. After the gel is set, evaporation of water causes not only the reduction of diffusion in the channel of gel frame work, but also discontinuities in the channel due to the shrinkage of the gel. Both these effects would adversely affect the diffusion of NaF or NH_4F and hence the number of nucleation sites.

(iv) Effect of concentration of feed solution

To investigate the effects of concentrations of feed solutions, gel of same pH and density are prepared (optimized value). Feed solution of different concentrations varying from 0.25 M to 2.5 M are put over the set gels. It is observed that as the concentration of the feed solutions increases, the nucleation density also increases. This may be due to the enhanced availability of NaF or NH_4F molecules for solubility reduction. For the growth of good quality crystals, suitable concentration of feed solution is found to be 0.7 M. Similarly, it is found that the optimum concentration of acetic acid for the growth of good crystals is 1.0 M. The figure 3.7 shows the plot of nucleation density versus the concentration of feed solution during the growth.

(v) Effect of different acids employed to prepare the gel on silica content of the grown crystals

The gels are prepared using different acids like hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid, acetic acid, formic acid and citric acid. In each case, after setting the gel, feed solutions are added above the gel. In case of HCl and H_2SO_4 no nucleation

Figure 3.7 : Plot of concentration of feed solution versus nucleation density. A \rightarrow Silica doped NaF, B \rightarrow Silica doped NH_4F and C \rightarrow Silica doped NaF - NH_4F mixed crystals.

is observed. But in case of acetic acid, formic acid and citric acid, crystals are formed after 36 hours. The crystals formed in citric acid medium are found to be more transparent than formic and acetic acid medium crystals, and acetic acid medium crystals are more brittle than other two. It is also observed that the nucleation density in acetic acid is larger than in formic acid, which in turn is larger than in the citric acid medium at same pH value. Even though the pH value is kept as same in all acid mediums, the nucleation density, the nature (morphology and brittleness etc.) of crystals and the percentage of silica doping is changed. This can be due to the fact that, even though the initial pH value of SMS + acid mixture is kept constant, the

Figure 3.7 : Plot of concentration of feed solution versus nucleation density. A \rightarrow Silica doped NaF, B \rightarrow Silica doped NH_4F and C \rightarrow Silica doped NaF - NH_4F mixed crystals.

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acidity of the gel after gellation may be different which might be affected on crystal formation. The chemical analysis showed that the silica percentage is more in case of NaF crystals grown in acetic acid gel media where as it is very less in case of formic acid and citric acid gel media. Similar effect was observed in case of NH_4F and mixed crystals.

3.5 Conclusions

- (1) The silica doped sodium fluoride, ammonium fluoride and sodium fluoride-ammonium fluoride mixed crystals are successfully grown by employing a new variation in gel technique named as gel incorporation method.
- (2) Optimization condition to grow the silica doped NaF, NH_4F and NaF- NH_4F mixed crystals are obtained by trial and error by varying the growth parameters.
- (3) The effect of organic acids for doping percentage of silica is studied. It is found that citric acid gel is ideal to grow pure NaF, NH_4F or mixed crystals with very small silica content, where as the formic acid gel and acetic acid gel successfully increase the percentage of doping.
- (4) Thus, silica impurities are incorporated into the lattice structure of NaF, NH_4F and NaF - NH_4F mixed crystals lattice in order to increase or to generate new types of colour centers.
- (5) Any other variation of gel technique as already reported are found to be not relevant to grow these crystals including solubility reduction method even though crystals are soluble in water.

References

- [1] Mollenauer L F ; in *Methods of Experimental Physics*, Vol. 15 B (C.L.Tang ed.) Academic Press New York (1979)
- [2] Pollock C R ; in *Encyclopedia of Laser and optical Technology* (Robert A M ed.) TRW Inc. (1989) 9
- [3] Shono Y ; *Optical characteristics of F_2 centers and applications* in International conference on colour centers in Ionic Crystals, Japan, Aug (1974) 187/2PP.
- [4] Luostarinen J, Silfsten P, and Ceiponen K E ; *Phys. States Solidi. A (Germany)* 137, 1, (1993) K57-60
- [5] Kishi Y, Imai T, and Yazaki T ; *Optical information element using M centre in doped NaF crystals* in International conference on Colour Centres in Ionic Crystals, Japan, August (1974) 189/2PP.
- [6] Jain S C and Mehendra P C ; *Phys. Rev.* 140, (1965) A957
- [7] Ratnam V V and Gartia R K ; *Indian J. Pure appl. Phys*, 13, (1975) 82
- [8] Rao D R and DAS B N ; *Crystal Lattice Defects*, 6, (1976) 243
- [9] Schulman J H and Compton W D ; *colour centers in solids*. (Pergamon Press. London) 1963.
- [10] Rao V and Sharma ; *J. Physica* 28 (1963) 653.
- [11] Grant R M Cameron J R ; *J. Appl Phys.*, 37 (1937) 3791
- [12] Wakde D G , Moharil S V and Deshmukh B T ; *Phys. Stat.sol.* (6) 100 (1980) K27
- [13] Gon H B and Veeraiah N ; *J. Mat. Sci.* 16 (1981) 2571

- [14] Gon H B, Gupta S and Rao V ; *Phys. Status Solidi. (a)* 91 (1985) 143
- [15] Selvarajan P, Das B N, Gon H B and Rao V ; *Indian J. Pure and Appl. Phys.* 31 (1993) 76
- [16] Farge Y and Fontana M P ; *Electronic and Vibrational properties of point defects in Ionic solids* North-Holland Publ. Amsterdam (1979)
- [17] Kolyago S S, Matrosov V N and Shkadarevich A P ; *Sov. J. Quantum Electron. (USA)* 15, 12 (1985) 1653
- [18] Mounier D, Girard S, Doulan J L and Magighi K ; *Journal de Physique iv*, 1 (1991) C7 - 339
- [19] Krishnamurthy C V and Murti Y V G S ; *Nonlinear Optics*, 7 (1994) 21
- [20] Henisch H K ; *Crystal Growth in Gels* (Pennsylvania state University Press, University Park P A (1970)
- [21] Leckebusch R and Recker K ; *J. Crystal Growth*, 13/14 (1972) 276
- [22] Leckebusch R ; *J. Crystal Growth*, 23 (1974) 74
- [23] Blank Z, Brenner W and Okamoto Y ; *Mater. Res. Bull.* 3 (1968) 555
- [24] Blanks B, Chianelli R and Pintchokshy F ; *J. Crystal Growth* 18 (1973) 185
- [25] Bloor D ; *J. Crystal Growth* 7 (1970) 1
- [26] Jagannatha N and Mohan Rao ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.* 16, 5 (1993) 365
- [27] Shedam M R and Venkateswara Rao ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.* 16, 4 (1994) 309

-
- [28] Kasthuri Bangera and Mohan Rao ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.* 15, 4
(1992) 339
- [29] Bandyopadhyay T and Ashok D ; *Indian J. Earth Sci.* 4 (1977)
95
- [30] Ranadive D, Blank Z, Brenner W and Okamoto Y ; *Nature* 223
(1969) 829
- [31] Blank Z and Brenner W ; *Nature* 222 (1969) 79
- [32] Henisch H K, Hanoka J I and Dennis J ; *J. Electrochem. Soc.*
112 (1965) 627
- [33] Brezina B and Havrankova M ; *Mater. Res. Bull.* 6 (1971)
537
- [34] Halberstadt E S, Henisch H K, Nickl J and White E W ;
J. Colloid and Interface Sci. 29 (1969) 469
- [35] Joshi M S and Antony A V ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 13 (1978) 929
- [36] Desai C C and Ramana M S V ; *J. Crystal Growth* 102
(1990) 191
- [37] Halberstadt E S, Henisch H K and White E W ; *J. Colloid and
Interface Sci.*, 29 (1969) 469
- [38] Henisch H K, Hanoka J I and Dennis J ; *J. Electrochem.
Soc.*, 112 (1965) 627

CHAPTER 4

GROWTH OF BARIUM META BORATE AND STRONTIUM META BORATE :
NONLINEAR SINGLE CRYSTALS IN SILICA HYDRO GEL

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4.1 Introduction

Barium meta borate (BBO), the low temperature form of BaB_2O_4 is a very interesting nonlinear optical crystal which has been shown to be useful for harmonic generation including SHG, THG and FHG in laser systems. Its SHG efficiency is found to be 6 times that of KDP [1]. Its important properties like phase matching from 410 - 3500 nm, optical transparency above 200 nm, very high laser damage threshold, large birefringence, large temperature acceptance, large nonlinear coefficient and excellent mechanical and chemical properties have made it unquestionably the material choice for ultra-violet frequency conversion of visible light [2-5] and ultra-violet pumped parametric oscillation (OPO) [7-14] as well as for high average power electro-optic switching [15].

A BBO crystal OPO serves as the tunable source of coherent radiation for linear and nonlinear spectroscopic applications : Photo acoustic absorption, optical double resonance and coherent Raman spectroscopy. The BBO OPO is used spectroscopically either as a frequency broad band device with single shot multiplex detection or as a continuously tunable narrow band device controlled by injection seeding.

A BBO single crystal offers a wide fundamental OPO tuning range (0.41 - 2.7 μm) that can be extended further in to the UV and IR regions by additional nonlinear optical stages. Bhar et al successfully obtained tangentially phase matched efficient difference generation in BBO crystal [16].

The barium borate exists in two forms, α and β phase [17] with a transition temperature at $925 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ [18]. The α -phase is centrosymmetrical in its crystal structure and exhibits no NLO effect at all. On the other hand, the β -phase crystallizes in a noncentrosymmetrical space group and is therefore ideal for UV NLO applications. Thus the growth of BBO using melt is difficult [19]. The β -phase of BBO is first synthesized in 1874 through the reaction of NaB_2O_4 and BaCl_2 , giving the crystals of BBO in solid mass of NaCl [20].

In 1982, Lu et al [21] reported its space group as $R\bar{3}$, very close to $R3C$, with cell dimensions $a = 12.532 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 12.717 \text{ \AA}$. But in 1983, Liebertz and Stahr [22] reported its space group as $R3C$ with practically same unit cell dimensions. In 1984, Frohlich [23] re-examined the BBO structure and confirmed its trigonal structure belonging to $R3C$. The main difference between $R3C$ and $R\bar{3}$ of BBO crystal structure, in so far as its NLO effects is concerned, lies in whether the SHG coefficient d_{22} should vanish or not. Using Maker fringe measurements, Chuangtian Chen et al [24] showed that the d_{22} coefficient is very small, certainly smaller than $(1/20)d_{11}$. It is therefore concluded that $R3C$ is most likely the correct space group. The major advantages of BBO for NLO applications are as follows.

- (1) A wide transparency range and high transmittance from 190 nm up to $2.6 \mu\text{m}$. Preliminary measurements [25] showed that in the region of transparency, the absorption of small samples can be made rather small, below $0.1 \% / \text{cm}$.
- (2) Larger birefringence and relatively small dispersion [26]

allow the crystal to possess a very wide phase matching range from 1.5 μm to 189 nm (for SHG). Its refractive indices measured at 12 wavelengths from 0.2288 μm to 1.079 μm and the Sellmeier equations are given [24].

- (3) A wide temperature acceptance (55°C) and high damage threshold (as high as 13.5 J/cm^2 at $\lambda = 1.064 \mu\text{m}$) suggest that this material is a good choice for harmonic generation of high average intensity and high power density lasers.

The major disadvantages of BBO are its low angular acceptance (only 1 m rad cm for SHG) and small z-components of SHG coefficients [24], thus limiting its applications for laser systems possessing larger divergence and thus using focussing, to increase the power density.

Single crystal fibres of 0.1 to 1 mm diameter and 0.5 to 1 cm in length have been grown from Na_2O and B_2O_3 fluxes with laser heated pedestal growth method [27]. A number of different solution growth techniques including top-seeded-solution growth (TSSG), immersion seeding growth and flux growth (Na_2O , B_2O_3 , $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_4$, BaCl_2 , NaCl , BaF_2 , $\text{NaCl-B}_2\text{O}_3$) [28-34] have been used to grow BBO crystals. Combining the TSSG technique with the Na_2O flux has yielded best results so far. Onishi et al [35] reported Czochralski growth of fibrous single crystals of BBO from the melt without any flux. Itoh et al [19] have grown highly pure single crystals of BBO from BaB_2O_4 stoichiometric melt with the direct Czochralski method. In 1993, Kouta et al [36] reported the growth of BBO single crystals by Czochralski method using

α -BaB₂O₄ and β -BaB₂O₄ single crystals as starting material.

Recently, Perlov et al [37] reported the isothermal growth of BBO crystals by continuous feeding in the top seeded solution growth configuration.

Similarly, strontium meta borate (SBO) is a new nonlinear material in borate series. It crystallizes in orthorhombic with space group P_{nca}. Its nonlinear efficiency is comparable with that of BBO [38]. It has been prepared by flux melt method from a melt contg. SrB₂O₄ with a flux of Na₂B₂O₄ in 25 - 50 mol % SrB₂O₄.

Until now a large variety of single crystals have been grown using gel method [39 - 44], but there is no report about the growth of BBO and SBO crystals in gel. In this chapter, for the first time the growth of BBO and SBO crystals using gel technique has been described. The influence of various growth parameters to obtain the optimization conditions for the growth of these single crystals are also discussed.

4.2 Experimental details.

The chemical reaction method in gel technique is used to grow these crystals. The technique involves growing of single crystals by allowing the reaction of two solutions of soluble salts by diffusion through a gel with subsequent nucleation and the crystal growth which continues due to the gradual precipitation of the insoluble product phase of the reaction within the gel. Crystal growth experiments were carried out in one open end corning glass tubes of length 20 cm and inner

diameters 2.5 cm. The chemicals used were commercial water glass solutions (sodium meta silicate), boric acid (analaR BDH), barium chloride (analaR BDH), and strontium chloride (analaR BDH).

The commercial water glass solution is diluted with distilled water in 1 : 5 ratio and centrifuged at 1500 rpm to separate out the floating and suspended impurities. The centrifuged solution is further diluted with requisite quantity of distilled water to get sodium meta silicate (SMS) of varying specific gravity. The gel is set by mixing sodium meta silicate solution of specific gravity 1.04 with aqueous 2M boric acid solution in the proper ratio such that the pH of the resulting solution lies between 3.2 to 4.8. Care is taken to see that SMS solution is added drop by drop to the acid with constant stirring to avoid excessive local ion concentrations which, otherwise, causes premature local gelling and makes the final medium inhomogeneous and turbid. The pH is measured using a digital pH meter, immediately after mixing and agitating. The gel is usually found to set after 7 days.

4.2.1 Growth of barium meta borate.

The following chemical reaction is employed for the growth of BBO crystals

In this case after setting the gel, the aqueous solution of BaCl_2 (2M) is added over the set gel, down the walls of the experimental tubes with the help of a pipette in order to prevent

the breaking of the gel surface and the inner structure. A continuous band is precipitated just below the gel interface as soon as the top solution is poured over the set gel in the experimental tubes. Below this band micro crystals are observed. These micro crystals grow until they reach the optimum size. After their growth, the crystals are collected by washing with distilled water.

4.2.2 Growth of strontium meta borate.

In this case after setting the gel, the aqueous solution of SrCl_2 (1M) is added over the set gel without disturbing the gel structure. The following chemical reaction is employed for the growth of SBO crystals

In this case also a continuous band is precipitated just below the gel interface as soon as the top solution is poured over the set gel in the experimental tubes. Below this band small crystals of SBO are observed.

4.3 Observations and discussion.

The single crystals of the size up to $1 \times 0.7 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^3$ were obtained in both the cases (figures 4.1 & 4.2). The BBO and SBO crystals within the gel during the growth are shown in figures 4.3 & 4.4 respectively. The growth experiments are repeated by varying gel density, gel pH, gel aging, concentration of boric acid, concentration of feed solution, and temperature in order to

Fig. 4.1 : BBO single crystal.

Fig. 4.2 : SBO single crystal.

Fig. 4.3 : BBO crystal in test tube.

Fig. 4.4 : SBO in test tube.

determine the best experimental conditions for the growth of good quality crystals.

4.3.1 Effect of gel density.

Henisch [45] has suggested the proper range (1.03 to 1.06) of specific gravity of the SMS solution to grow good quality single crystals. The gel of different densities are obtained by mixing SMS solutions of specific gravity 1.03 - 1.06 with 2M boric acid, keeping the pH value a constant. The transparency of the gel increases as the gel density decreases.

It is known that there is distribution of pore sizes within each gel, and that one gel is distinguished from another by this nature of distribution. One of the operative parameters for diffusion is the size of the particle relative to the pore size of the gel. Another is the amount of interaction between solute and internal gel surfaces. Bechhold et al [46] showed that diffusion coefficient become distinctly smaller as gel densities increase and indeed nothing else could have been expected. There is no evidence that the diffusion constant of small atoms and ions are greatly influenced by the silica gel density as long as the density is low. Thus, the diffusion constants are not greatly influenced by the presence of dilute gel.

It is observed that the nucleation density decreases as the gel density increases. A greater gel density implies smaller pore size and poor communication among the pores and thus decreasing the nucleation density [47]. Sodium meta silicate solution of specific gravity 1.04 and boric acid (2M) with 2:5 ratio is ideal

to grow both BBO and SBO single crystals. Below and above this range, poor quality crystals are observed.

4.3.2 Effect of gel pH.

The effect of pH on gel setting time is studied by mixing the SMS solution (1.04 specific gravity) and boric acid (2M) in various ratios. The mixed solution of SMS and boric acid with 2:5 ratio forms the gel (pH 4.9) immediately after mixing. The gelling time increases if the acidity of the solution is increased by increasing the volume of boric acid. The results are in agreement with those given by other workers [48] and suggest convincingly that the reaction is ionic in character.

It is known that during the formation of silica gel, there are two types of ions produced (H_3SiO_4^- and $\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_4^{2-}$) in relative amounts which depend on the hydrogen ion concentration. In principle, latter is more reactive which is associated with high pH values but the higher charge implies a greater degree of mutual repulsion. H_3SiO_4^- is favoured by moderately low pH values and is held responsible [49,50] for the initial formation of long chain polymerization products. Very high as well as very low pH values evidently lead to high surface charges which inhibit gellation.

The pH of gelling solutions does not remain constant even in the absence of other reagents which may probably be due to syneresis [51]. In the presence of other ions the pH variation can be very different.

From above considerations, we may conclude that the initial pH value of the gel does not indicate the acidity of the gel after gellation. But even then these pH values will have a profound effect on the gel structure and the nucleation and growth of crystals in these gels, as is seen during the present investigation.

In the case of both BBO and SBO single crystals the gel with pH 4.9 gives the good quality crystals. When the pH is increased above 4.9, only a few small size crystals are observed. On the other hand, below pH 4.9, no crystals were observed except a few dendrites.

4.3.3 Effect of gel aging.

To investigate the effect of aging of gels, gels of same pH and density are allowed to age for various periods before adding the feed solution. For studying the effect of aging of gels on nucleation density, 0.5 M feed solution is added to differently aged gel of the same pH. It is found that the number of BBO and SBO crystals decreases as the aging of the gel increases.

Aging of gels decreases the pore size and decreases the diffusion and nucleation density. It is observed that longer the time for a gel to set at room temperature, greater is the amount of water that evaporates out of the gel. The effect of water evaporation should be considered before and after the formation of the gel frame work. Before the gel set, the evaporation of water causes an increase in gel density which in turn decreases

the diffusivity of Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} in the gel thereby decreasing the number of nucleation sites. After the gel is set, evaporation of water causes not only the lack of ionic carriers in the channel of gel frame work, but also discontinuities in the channel due to the shrinkage of gel. Both these effects would adversely affect the diffusion of Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} ions hence the observed decrease in the number of nucleation sites.

4.3.4 Effect of concentration of boric acid.

To investigate the effect of concentration of boric acid solution, gels are prepared with different concentrations of H_3BO_3 (0.5 M to 3 M) and allowed to set. When the concentration of H_3BO_3 is less than 0.2 M, the gel takes longer time to set and for concentrations greater than 2 M, the gel is set immediately after mixing the SMS solution and boric acid. For the growth of good quality crystals, suitable concentration of boric acid is found to be 2 M.

4.3.5 Effect of concentration of feed solution.

By keeping other conditions optimum, the concentration of feed solution is varied between 0.5 M to 2 M. With increase in concentration of feed solutions, it is found that the number of nucleation sites increased which decreases the size of the crystals. The optimum concentration of feed solution to get pure crystals of considerable size is 1 M. The plot of concentration of feed solution with nucleation density is shown in figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5 : Plot of concentration of feed solution versus nucleation density

4.4 Conclusions

Figure 4.6 : Plot of temperature versus time for nucleation.

4.3.6 Effect of temperature.

By keeping other conditions optimum, the temperature of the system is varied between 30°C to 50°C (figure 4.6). With increase in temperature, the time for nucleation is decreased and there is no drastic effect on size of the crystals observed.

In order to prove the noncentrosymmetric structure of these grown crystals, the crystals are placed in front of Nd-YAG laser beam of wavelength 1.064 μm . The intense green light is emitted from these crystals.

4.4 Conclusions

- (1) The BBO and SBO crystals are successfully grown by employing gel technique.
- (2) The optimization conditions to grow the BBO and SBO crystals are obtained by trial and error method by varying the growth parameters.
- (3) Careful control of growth parameters is essential to the production of optically clear crystals.
- (4) The noncentrosymmetric structure is confirmed by placing these crystals in front of Nd-YAG laser.

References

- [1] David F Eaton ; *Nonlinear optical materials, the great and near great in materials for nonlinear optics - chemical perspective*, Symposium series, (1991) 455
- [2] Miyazaki K, Sakai H and Sato T ; *Opt. Letters* 11 (1986) 797
- [3] Chen D W and Yeh J J ; *Opt. Letters* 13 (1988) 808
- [4] Zimmermann C, Kallenbach R and Hansch T W ; *Opt. Commun.* 71 (1989) 229
- [5] Coutts D, Ainsworth M D and Piper J A ; *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* QE-25 (1989) 1985
- [6] Ferrand B, Chartier I, Aubert J J and Doizi D ; *J. de Physique.* iv, 1 (1991) C7-753
- [7] Cheng L K, Bosenberg W R and Tang C L ; *Appl. Phys. Letters* 53 (1988) 175
- [8] Bosenberg W R, Cheng L K and Tang C L ; *Appl. Phys. Letters* 54 (1989) 13
- [9] Komine H ; *Opt. Letters* 13 (1988) 643
- [10] Burdulis S, Grigonis R, Fix A and Wallenstein R ; *Opt. Commun.* 74 (1990) 398
- [11] Fan Y X, Eckardt R C, Byer R L and Wallenstein R ; *Appl. Phys. Letters* 53 (1988) 2014
- [12] Shiraishi T, Taniu Y and Shiozaki H ; *Rev. Laser Engg.* 21-2 (1993) 295
- [13] Suzuki H ; *JEE J. Electron Engg.* 30-319 (1993) 100
- [14] Haub J C, Johnson M J and Orr B J ; *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B: Opt. Phys.* (USA) 10-9 (1993) 1765
- [15] Ebberts C A ; *Proc. SPIE* 968 (1988) 66

- [16] Bhar G C, Dutta P K, Rudra A M and Chatterjee U ; *Opt. Growth 77* (1989)
Commun. (Netherlands) 105, 1-2 (1994) 95
- [17] Levin E M and Mc Murdie H F ; *Natl. Bur. Std. (US), J. Res.* (1988) 49
42 (1949) 131
- [18] Hubner K H and Neues Jahrb ; *Mineral. Monatsh* (1969) 335
Growth 77 (1989)
- [19] Itoh K, Maruma F and Kuwano Y ; *J. Crystal Growth* 106
(1990) 728
- [20] Benedikt R ; *Ber. Deut. Chem. Ges.* 7 (1874) 703
(1993) 238
- [21] Lu S F and Huang J L ; *Acta Phys. Sinica*, 31 (1982) 948
- [22] Liebertz I and Stahr S ; *Z. Krist.* 165 (1983) 91
- [23] Frohlich R ; *Z. Krist* 168 (1984) 109
(1991) 490
- [24] Chen C, Yicheng W U and Rukarg L I ; *J. Crystal Growth* 99
(1990) 790
Jach. 19 1 (1984)
- [25] Eimerl D, Davis L and Velsko S *J. Appl. Phys.* 62 (1987)
1968
- [26] Chen C T, Wu B C, Jiang A D and You G M ; *Sci. Sinica* B28
(1986) 511
(1985) 235
- [27] Tang D Y, Route R K and Feigelson R S ; *J. Crystal Growth*
(1986) 393
91 (1988) 81
- [28] Jiang A, Cheng F and Zheng Y ; *J. Crystal Growth* 79 (1986)
78) 60 3 (1988)
693
- [29] Cheng L K, Bosenberg W and Tang C L ; *J. Crystal Growth* 89
(1992) 527
(1988) 553
- [30] Bosenberg W R, Lane R J and Tang C L ; *J. Crystal Growth*
Cambridge Univer
108 (1991) 394
- [31] Ferrand B, Chartier I and Doizi D ; *J. de Physique* iv,
1 (1991) C7-753

- [32] Feigelson R S, Raymakers R J, and Route R K ; *J. Crystal Growth* 97 (1989) 352
- [33] Chai B H T, Gualtieri D M and Randles M H ; *Proc. SPIE* 968 (1988) 69
- [34] Gualtieri D M, Chai B H T and Randles M H ; *J. Crystal Growth* 97 (1989) 613
- [35] Onishi N ; *Ceramics (Japan)* 24 (1989) 319
- [36] Kouta H, Imoto S and Kuwano Y ; *J. Crystal Growth* 128 1-4 (1993) 238
- [37] Perlov D and Roth M ; *J. Crystal Growth* 137 1-2 (1994) 123
- [38] Fukuda and Katsuyoshi ; *Jpn. Kokai Tokkyo Koho JP*, 2-97 (1991) 490
- [39] Kibalczye W, Sokolowski T and Wiklorowska B ; *Crystal Res. Tech.* 19 1 (1984) 27
- [40] Venkateswara Rao A ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.* 7 2 (1985) 83
- [41] Dharmaprakash S M and Mohan Rao P ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.* 8 (1986) 511
- [42] Kotru P N, Raina K K and Koul M L ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 21 11 (1986) 393
- [43] Desai C C and Hanchinal A N ; *Indian Journal of Physics (A)* 60 3 (1986) 249
- [44] Patel A R and Venkateswara Rao A ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.* 4-5 (1982) 527
- [45] Henisch H K ; *Crystals in gels and Liesegang rings*, Cambridge University Press, New York (1986) 33
- [46] Bachhold H and Zeigler K ; *Ann. Phy.* 20 (1906) 900

- [47] Halberstadt E S, Henisch H K, Nickel J and White E W ; *J. Colloid and interface Sci.* 29 (1969) 469
- [48] Hurd C B, Raymond C L and Miller P S ; *J. Phys. Chem.* 38 (1934) 663
- [49] Plank C J and Drake L C ; *J. Colloid Sci.* 2 (1974) 399
- [50] Plank C J and Drake L C ; *J. Colloid Sci.* 2 (1974) 413
- [51] Greenberg S A and Sinclair D ; *J. Phys. Chem.* 59 (1955) 435

CHAPTER 5

GROWTH OF AMMONIUM OXALATE AND AMMONIUM TARTRATE : NONLINEAR
SINGLE CRYSTALS IN SILICA HYDRO GEL

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5.1 Introduction

Ammonium Oxalate Monohydrate (AOM) is a nonlinear optical material, which crystallizes in orthorhombic space group $P2_12_12_1$ with two molecules per unit cell [1]. It phase matches at room temperature and shows SHG efficiency comparable to KDP. It produces simultaneously the second and third harmonics for a given fundamental Nd:YAG laser beam with wavelength $1.06 \mu\text{m}$ [2].

So far only solution growth technique was used to grow AOM crystals. In 1972, Reimer et al [3] reported the growth of needle shaped crystals of AOM in aqueous solution. Since AOM has a tendency to crystallize in the form of needles, it is a challenge to grow single crystals of fairly good size.

Similarly, ammonium tartrate is another interesting nonlinear material which crystallizes in monoclinic space group $P2_1$ [4]. In 1973, Mitsui et al observed SHG in this crystal by phase matching technique at fundamental wavelength $1.153 \mu\text{m}$ [5]. Its nonlinear coefficients were found to be comparable in magnitude to those of KDP.

It is found that the nonlinear applications like surface acoustic wave devices need large diameter crystals without domains and sub grain boundaries, grown in special orientations whereas electro-optic modulators and nonlinear optic devices require high optical quality crystals. However, laser induced

refractive index inhomogeneties which have been labeled as "optical damage" impose limits on device performance. Investigations of these photorefractive effects have pointed to the involvement of a variety of impurities and intrinsic defects [6]. For this reason and because of the need for high quality larger crystals, new and improved crystal growth methods are being used.

It has been reported that a number of oxalates like barium oxalate [7], barium ammonium oxalate [8], cadmium oxalate [9], cobalt oxalate, manganous oxalate, sodium oxalate [10], lead oxalate [11] and doped cadmium oxalates [12] were grown using gel technique. But no successful attempts have been made for the growth of AOM using silica gel technique. This is because AOM is fairly soluble in water and hence the variation of gel technique, namely chemical reaction method can not be used. Thus, a new variation of gel technique named as solubility reduction cum chemical reaction method is used in the present investigation to grow AOM single crystals. This method includes the conventional solubility reduction and chemical reaction methods in gel techniques. In this new method, the initial nucleation for the growth of AOM is achieved by solubility reduction of ammonium oxalate and then the growth rate is increased by chemical reaction method.

Similarly, a large variety of tartrates like strontium tartrate [13], lead tartrate [14], manganese tartrate [15], rubidium hydrogen tartrate [16], calcium tartrate [17], barium tartrate [18] and some mixed tartrates [18,19] are grown.

In 1986, Saraf et al [20] reported the dendrite growth of ammonium tartrate single crystals in silica gel. They used the chemical reaction method in gel technique. But in this investigation, to grow the large size ammonium tartrate crystals the new method - solubility reduction cum chemical reaction method is used.

5.2 Crystal growth

5.2.1 Solubility reduction cum chemical reaction in gel technique

To grow highly water soluble crystals like ADP, KDP, TGS, NaCl in gel technique, solubility reduction method is used. In this method, the substance to be grown as crystals is dissolved in water and incorporated with the gel. After the gel setting, a solution which reduces the solubility of the substance is added over the set gel to induce crystallization. For example, KDP crystals have been grown by adding ethyl alcohol over the gel containing a saturated solution of KDP [21]. Similarly, for the growth of ADP, ammonium chloride is used for solubility reduction [22]. The drawback of this method is once the crystal grows to certain stage, the size of the crystal remains constant because of non availability of reactants at the vicinity of the growing crystal.

To overcome this problem, a new idea is used in which the initial nucleation is obtained by reduction of solubility and further growth is facilitated by means of chemical reaction

between the reactants added to the gel as well as in the form of feed solution. By controlling the optimum condition, the size of the crystals can be increased sufficiently by this new technique.

5.3 Experimental Procedure

For ADM single crystals, the growth process involved the diffusion of NH_4Cl solution into the gel which contains ammonium oxalate and oxalic acid. In case of growth of ammonium tartrate single crystals, NH_4Cl solution is diffused into the gel which contains ammonium tartrate and tartaric acid. Crystal growth experiments were carried out in corning glass tubes (length 200 mm and inner diameter 25 mm). The chemicals used were commercial sodium meta silicate (water glass) solution, oxalic acid (analaR), NH_4Cl , ammonium oxalate (analaR BDH) and ammonium tartrate (analaR BDH).

The sodium meta silicate solution (SMS) of specific gravity 1.04 was prepared as explained in earlier chapter. In case of ADM, the gel was prepared by mixing the saturated solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, oxalic acid (1M) and SMS with density 1.04 g/cc. In case of ammonium tartrate, the gel was prepared by mixing the saturated solution of ammonium tartrate, tartaric acid (1M) and SMS with density 1.04 g/cc. After the gel was set, the solution of ammonium chloride was slowly poured over the gel down the walls of the test tubes.

The following chemical reaction is expected in case of ADM during the growth.

In case of ammonium tartrate the following chemical reaction is excepted.

5.4 Observations and discussions

Ammonium oxalate is sparingly soluble in water and oxalic acid (1M). But it is interesting to note that when sodium meta silicate (1.04 g/cc) is added to this mixture, the solubility of ammonium oxalate is increased and a clear solution is obtained. After 30 hours, the solution got hardened in the form of gel. On the other hand, if ammonium oxalate alone is added to sodium meta silicate, this results in sudden gellation and is found useless for crystal growth. After adding supernatant NH_4Cl solution above the gel, the nucleation started between 20 - 25 hours. At higher concentration of feed solution, (above 2M) nucleation started within 2 - 3 hours.

It is expected that the solubility of ADM is reduced due to the diffusion of NH_4Cl in to the gel because of increase in NH_4^+ concentration. As a result, few nucleation sites are developed within the gel structure and grow with time due to increased diffusion. At the same time, the increased NH_4^+ concentration reacts with oxalic acid which is already inside the gel, resulting in the formation of ammonium oxalate and the size of these crystals increases further.

Similarly, in case of ammonium tartrate, initially, the solubility of ammonium tartrate is decreased by the diffusion of NH_4Cl into the gel, which contains saturated ammonium tartrate and tartaric acid. The nucleation created by solubility reduction grows into large crystals due to the chemical reaction between diffused ammonium chloride and tartaric acid. The maximum size obtained in case of AOM is $3.2 \times 2 \times 1.2 \text{ cm}^3$ and in case of ammonium tartrate is $2.8 \times 1.5 \times 0.8 \text{ cm}^3$. The gel grown single crystals of AOM and ammonium tartrate are shown in figure 5.1 and figure 5.2 respectively. The crystals within the gel, during the growth process are shown in figures 5.3 and 5.4 respectively.

5.4.1 Effect of various parameters on crystal growth

It is necessary to study the effect of various parameters on crystal growth rate in this solubility cum chemical reaction method. Accordingly, during the growth process the variable parameters which affect the growth process like, pH of gel, density of gel, addition of product material to gel, concentration of feed solution and temperature are studied.

(i) Effect of pH of gel

The experiment is repeated by keeping the amount of ammonium oxalate in the gel constant, the pH of the gel is varied by changing the composition of oxalic acid and sodium meta silicate

Fig. 5.1 : AOM single crystal.

Fig. 5.2 : AT single crystal.

Fig. 5.3 : AOM in test tube.

Fig. 5.4 : AT in test tube.

from 2.5 to 6.5. The optimum value of gel pH to get clear gel is found to be 3.5. At pH values less than 3.5, the gellation occurred very soon and the resultant gel was not transparent, and for pH values greater than 3.5, the time for gellation increased and the resultant gel was unstable.

(ii) Effect of density of gel

The experiment is repeated by keeping the pH of gel at 3.5 but by varying the density of sodium meta silicate from 1.01 to 1.06 g/cc. It is observed that the optimum value of SMS density is 1.03 g/cc. For densities less than 1.03, the solubility of ammonium oxalate in the initial mixture is decreased and as a result, the number of nucleation centers decreased drastically and are observed only close to the bottom of the test tube. At higher densities, the gel formed was not transparent and the grown crystals were found to be of poor quality. It can be argued that at lower density, because of lack of ammonium oxalate in the gel, the number of nucleation centers decreased. At higher density, because of excess of ammonium oxalate in gel, the diffusion of ammonium ions from feeding solution gets affected which results in the poor quality crystals.

(iii) Effect of addition of ammonium oxalate to the gel

Without mixing ammonium oxalate to the gel, no crystals were observed by means of chemical reaction method only. With increase in the amount of added ammonium oxalate to the gel, the nucleation density increased but the size of the crystals

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were found to be very small. This implies that the added ammonium oxalate to the gel produces necessary nucleation by providing NH_4^+ ions from feeding solution by means of solubility reduction due to increased concentration of NH_4^+ ions. Then the size of these nuclei increases continuously by means of chemical reaction of oxalic acid with feeding solution. This argument is further supported by the observed increase in crystal size with time (up to two months).

(iv) Effect of concentration of feed solution

The experiment is repeated by varying the strength of feed solution (NH_4Cl) from 0.5 M to saturated solution by keeping the other conditions constant (pH 3.5, gel density 1.03 etc). The resultant crystal size increased with increase in concentration of feed solution. It can be predicted that with increase in the concentration of feed solution, the reaction between oxalic acid and the diffused feed solution enhanced, which results in increased size of the crystals. The variation in the size of the ADM crystals with the concentration of feed solution during of 30 days after pouring the feed solution is shown in figure 5.5.

(v) Effect of aging of gel

The experiment is repeated by increasing the time for addition of feed solution after the gel formation. The initial nucleation of ADM or ammonium tartrate is not affected by increasing the time for addition of feed solution, but the size of these crystals gets affected due to decreased amount of

Figure 5.5 : Plot of concentration of feed solution versus size of the AOM crystals.

Figure 5.6 : Plot of temperature versus size of AOM crystals.

Figure 5.7 : Plot of temperature versus time required for initial nucleation for ADM crystals.

availability of NH_4Cl through the gel, because of its increased hardening.

(vi) Effect of temperature on growth

The experiment is repeated by keeping the system at different temperatures after the addition of feed solution using cryostat from 25°C to 40°C . The graph of maximum size of ADM crystal for fixed time verses the temperature of the system is shown in figure (5.6). This reveals that the nucleation rate and the size of the crystals increased with increase in temperature. It is also found that with increase in temperature, the time required for initial nucleation is increased. The plot of

temperature of the system with the time required for initial nucleation in both ADM and AT are shown in figure 5.7.

This is expected as, with increase in temperature, the rate of diffusion of feed solution increases, which results in the increase in size. Also, with increase in temperature, the solubility of ammonium oxalate gets affected, resulting in increase in the time of nucleation. The same type of effects are observed in case of AT.

5.5 Conclusions

- (1) Single crystals of ammonium oxalate and ammonium tartrate are grown for the first time using solubility reduction cum chemical reaction method.
- (2) This method gives single crystals of larger size as compared to crystals obtained by other variations of gel technique.
- (3) The optimum condition for growth of good quality, large size crystals is determined by varying different parameters during the growth process.

References

- [1] Pedersen B F ; *Acta Crystallogr. B* (Denmark), B28, 3 (1972) 746
- [2] Orlov Y R, Sukhorukov A P and Tomov I V ; *Annu. univ. Sofia. Fac. Phys.* (Bulgaria) 64-65 (1970) 283
- [3] Reimer H H and Kahlweit M ; *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem* (Germany) 76, 2 (1972) 138
- [4] Yadhava and Padmanabhan ; *Acta Crystall. B*, 29 (1973) 493
- [5] Mitsui T, Iio K, Hamano K and Sawada S ; *Opt. Commun.* (Netherlands), 9, 3 (1973) 322
- [6] Xu Dong, Zhang Nan and Jiang Min-hua ; *J. Phys. D ; Appl. Phys.* 26 (1993) B230
- [7] Darmaprakash S M and Mohan Rao P ; *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.* 5 (1986) 769
- [8] Kasthuri V B and Mohan Rao P ; *Indian J. of Pure and Applied Physics*, 32 (1994) 871
- [9] Shedam M R and Venkateswara Rao ; *Bull. Mater. Science*, 16, 4 (1991) 309
- [10] Khan A S, Devore T C and Reed W.F ; *J. Cryst. Growth* 35 (1976) 327
- [11] Madhava W G and Sreedharan K P ; *Indian J. of Pure and Applied Phys.* 32 (1994) 25
- [12] Jagannatha N; PhD Thesis on *Gel growth and characterization of doped cadmium oxalate crystal* Mangalore University 1993
- [13] Patel A R and Arora S K ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 11 (1976) 843
- [14] Abdulkhadar M and Ittyachen M A ; *J. Crystal Growth*, 39 (1977) 365

-
- [15] Ramakrishan V ; *Cryst. res. Technol.*, 24, 5 (1989) 513
- [16] Desai C C, Patel A H, Ramana M V S ; *Ferroelectrics* 102 (1990) 23
- [17] Henisch H K, Hanoka J I, and Dennis J ; *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 112 (1965) 627
- [18] Patil S N ; PhD thesis on *Growth and Characterization of some tartrate crystals using gel technique*, Kollapur University 1991.
- [19] Kotru P N, Raina K K and Koul M L ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 21 (1986) 3933
- [20] Saraf A G, Saraf K B, Wani P A and Bhorastar S V ; *Cry. Res. and Technol.* , 21, 4 (1986) 449
- [21] Brezina B, and Havrankova M ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 34, (1976) 248
- [22] Glocker D A and Soest I F ; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 51 (1969) 3143

CHAPTER 6

GROWTH OF ORGANIC NONLINEAR SINGLE CRYSTALS BY GEL - SOLUTION

TECHNIQUE

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1 Introduction

The search for new materials with large quadratic nonlinearities is mainly oriented towards applications in optical communications or optical signal processing, involving the generation of new frequencies, signal amplification, frequency mixing, electro optic modulation, optical parametric oscillation, optical bistability etc. As a part of nonlinear optical materials research, organic crystals present quadratic nonlinear properties in the visible and near infra-red regions, which surpass those of more classical inorganic nonlinear materials such as LiNbO_3 , KDP, BaB_2O_4 and challenging in some aspects, than those of more recent ones like KTP and Beryllium sulphate. This is because of their very large nonlinear optical susceptibilities, extreme structural diversity and flexibility for making them [1]. However, mainly owing to the great difficulty of making crystals of sufficient size and quality for practical use in devices, most of the organic crystals although selected after successful preliminary testing, finally failed to meet the required standards.

A molecular crystal suitable for use in a number of optically nonlinear devices requires atleast four basic qualities like a high molecular first order hyperpolarizability, a suitable crystallographic structure, sufficient optical quality including wide transmission range and a high optical damage threshold [2].

The high nonlinearity which is due to large delocalized and asymmetric π - electron system, when assisted by a charge transfer process [3,4] can be two or three order of magnitude above that of alliphatic molecules of same size. Such a situation is closely encountered in aromatic molecules with charge transfer occurring between a donor and acceptor substituent groups. A proper crystallographic structure is required for two reasons :

- (i) no odd ordered (second, forth etc) optical nonlinear effects happen when the crystal point group is centrosymmetric [5],
- (ii) there should be a high value of the excited state dipole moment with a small ground state dipole moment which is required for noncentrosymmetric molecules, to ensure a high value of β .

The third and fourth requirements (crystalline quality and a high optical damage threshold) are obvious prerequisites to the operation of an optical parametric oscillator (OPO) [6,7]. It should be noted that these requirements might play an important role than the two previous ones in the optimization of the parametric gain of an OPO [8]. From fabrication and exploitation point of view, some other criteria must be added, like (i) easy and inexpensive synthesis (ii) certain physicochemical properties, such as good radiation and thermal and chemical resistance, which will influence the crystal growth method to be used, and (iii) a tendency to crystallize easily. Moreover, the as-grown crystals should exhibit satisfactory mechanical properties, for further device processing operations among which cutting and polishing are essential.

In 1928, Wohler [9] first synthesized the organic molecule urea from the inorganic salt ammonium cyanate. It is particularly appropriate that urea, which then played such a pivotal role in the definition of organic chemistry, is today one of the most important and thoroughly studied nonlinear optical organic materials. After more than two decades of study of the theory of nonlinear optics crowned by the 1981 Nobel prize to Bloembergen [10], organic chemists assist today in the development of new NLO materials with a wide range of fascinating properties.

The usefulness of a nonlinear optical crystal often cannot be judged on the basis of the magnitude of its nonlinear optical coefficients alone. If a large nonlinear coefficients were the sole criterion, there would have been no reason to consider crystalline urea as a potential useful NLO material in the first place. Urea turned out to be a useful nonlinear optical crystal [11] because it is transparent down to 220 nm and has a fairly large birefringence so that phase matching for second harmonic and frequency mixing processes can be achieved well into the ultra-violet. In addition, it has a high optical damage threshold and its refractive index is relatively independent of temperature. Its main disadvantages are that it is very difficult to grow in the form of single crystal, and it is hygroscopic and mechanically relatively soft crystal [12]. Thereafter, a large number of organic NLO materials are investigated with very high SHG intensity compared to urea. But the main drawback of these crystals is their cut-off wavelength. For example, some of efficient organic crystals are tabulated in table 6.1 [12].

Table 6.1 : Some efficient organic crystals.

Material	SHG/urea	Cut-off wavelength (nm)
DAN	115	500
MNA	22	500
POM	13	450
PNP	150	470
NPP	75	500
COANP	50	470
MBANP	25	430
MMONS	750	510

This reveals that these crystals are useless for SHG conversion of diode laser beam into UV region.

The simple quantum mechanical two level model [13] indicating the intra molecular charge transfer stimulated by donors and acceptors in a conjugated system will dramatically increase the molecular hyperpolarizability according to the equation,

$$\beta_{ct} = \frac{(3 e^2 h^2) (w_{exp} f \Delta\mu_{ex})}{2m [w_{exp}^2 - (2hw)^2] [w_{exp}^2 - h^2]}$$

where f is the oscillator strength, $\Delta\mu_{ex}$ is the difference between excited and ground state dipole moments, w_{exp} is the energy gap between these two states. From this equation, we can see that β_{ct} increases as $\Delta\mu_{ex}$ increases and w_{exp} decreases, but at the same time, the corresponding absorption edge will be

dramatically red shifted. Therefore, a trade-off has to be found between nonlinearity and transparency. This problem may be solved by a careful selection of donors and acceptors in the conjugated system. The ability of some common substituents to donate and attract electrons are listed as follows [14].

donor : $(\text{Me})_2\text{n} > -\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3 > \text{O}^- > -\text{NH}_2 > -\text{OCH}_3 > -\text{OH} > -\text{Br} > -\text{Cl} > -\text{CH}_3$.

acceptor : $-\text{NO}_2 > -\text{CHO} > -\text{COOCH}_3 > -\text{COCH}_3 > -\text{COOH} > -\text{CN} > -\text{COH} > -\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2 > -\text{NH}_3^+$.

The carbonyl group is a strong electron absorber. When the para and/or ortho positions of an aromatic molecule has a relatively weak donor (e.g., methoxy, hydroxy, or halides), a charge transfer interaction can also be established and will increase the molecular hyperpolarizability. Furthermore, conjugate molecule containing carbonyl and weak donors usually have their cut-off wavelength dramatically blue shifted from those containing strong donors and acceptors (such as dimethylamino and nitro groups). This is very important in considering the trade off between efficiency and transparency.

The present work is more concentrated on the investigation of molecular crystals with favourable balance of optimum doubling efficiency and transparency properties. However, this is not to underestimate a variety of equally important issues such as synthetic accessibility, cost, crystal growth capability, toxicity, environmental stability, optical damage properties etc.

It is proposed that the large second order optical nonlinearities are associated with structures that have large difference between ground state and excited state dipole moments as well as large transition dipole moments. Hence, organic materials with electron donating and electron accepting groups separated by a delocalized π -electron system have been the focus of much of the research on organic nonlinear optical materials [15]. Such a situation is clearly encountered in aromatic molecules with charge transfer occurring between a donor and an acceptor substituent groups [16 - 18].

The appropriate functional group at the ends of π system can enhance the required asymmetric electronic distribution in either or both the ground state and excited state configurations. Functional groups are divided into two categories, based on their ability to donate electrons into or accept electrons from the π system. The common donor (D) groups are characterized by predominant 'p' character (Sp^3) bonding and often have available electron pairs on a 'p' orbital. The common acceptor groups are characterized by more 's' character (Sp^2 or Sp) bonding. Depending upon the σ substituent values, one can specify, donor and acceptor groups. In general, for D groups $\sigma < 0$; for A groups $\sigma > 0$ and hydrogen has $\sigma = 0$ by definition.

A-D para disubstituted benzenes are a text-book model for nonlinear optics. These molecules exhibit a strong asymmetric repartition of charge in the ground and excited state, often emerged as a typical electronic push-pull model as in figure

6.1, [19 - 21]. Here the excited state has generally a larger dipole moment so that the transition is accompanied by an Internal Charge Transfer (ICT).

Figure 6.1 : Electronic push - pull model.

6.2 Powder SHG Test

From this perspective, the author screened some of A-D para disubstituted benzenes for their powder SHG using Nd-YAG laser [22]. The following seven compounds have shown very good frequency conversion property compared to urea (table 6.2).

It is found that 4-amino benzoic acid crystal grown in this study is hygroscopic, reacts with atmosphere and turns in to whitish and becomes useless. The 4-nitro benzaldehyde is very difficult to grow and has high cut-off wavelength. Other materials (CMBF and BMBF) also show absorption at visible region and have very high cut-off wavelengths. Thus in this work, the detailed comparative study of growth and characterization of 4-Hydroxy acetophenone (HAP), Methyl-p-Hydroxy Benzoate (MHB), and Vanillin (MHBA) are considered. In addition, another A-D

para disubstituted benzene, Propyl-p-Hydroxy Benzoate (PHB) is also grown to examine its nonlinearity.

Table 6.2 : Powder SHG efficiency of some organic materials.

Material	SHG/urea	Cut-off wavelength
(1) p-Nitro benzaldehyde	5	410 nm
(2) p-Amino benzoic acid	8	360 nm
(3) p-Hydroxy acetophenone	12	220 nm
(4) Methyl-p-hydroxy benzoate	20	210 nm
(5) 4-Chloro nitro furyl chalcone (CNFC)	50	520 nm
(6) 4-Bromo nitro furyl chalcone (BNFC)	53	520 nm
(7) Vanillin	30	370 nm

The structural asymmetry and the earlier work on these 4 materials for nonlinearity are given below.

(i) p-Hydroxy Acetophenone (HAP)

This is a new nonlinear organic material reported first time in the present work. The material has a good balance between SHG efficiency, optical transparency and phase matching property. The crystal is transparent in UV region and expected to be potential candidate for UV up-conversion of GaAs diode lasers, argon lasers and even He-Ne laser light. The molecular formula of HAP is $C_6H_4COCH_3OH$ with molecular weight 136.15. The molecular structure is shown in figure 6.2. The benzene molecule with an electron donating group (-OH) and an electron accepting group (-COCH₃),

exhibits a strong asymmetric repartition of charge in the ground state and excited state so that the transition is accompanied by an internal charge transfer between para donor (hydroxy -OH) and (carbonyl $-COCH_3$) acceptor increasing the molecular hyperpolarizability. Moreover, the substituents force the molecule to crystallize in noncentrosymmetric space group. On the other hand, the same type compound, p-hydroxy benzophenone has a centrosymmetric structure [23] and null for microscopic SHG. No nonlinear and electro-optic properties of HAP is reported elsewhere.

(ii) Methyl-p-Hydroxy Benzoate (MHB)

This is relatively new nonlinear material [22] with low cut-off wavelength. It crystallizes in fairly good size and in natural crystal shape. But only few attempts were made to study its nonlinear properties and no attempts have been made to study its electro optic properties. The molecular formula of MHB is $C_8H_8O_3$ with molecular weight 152.1. Its molecular structure is given in figure 6.2. It has a benzene ring with an electron donating group (-OH) and an electron accepting group ($-COOCH_3$) substituted in opposite directions.

(iii) Vanillin (3-methoxy 4-hydroxy benzaldehyde)

Vanillin is also one of the very interesting nonlinear materials with low cut-off wavelength (370 nm). Comparatively large amount of work has been done on NLO properties of this material but there is no attempt on the study of electro optic

property of this crystal. The reason is due to vanillin tends to crystallize as long needles or thin plates. Thus the growth of vanillin single crystals of sufficient size to electro optic applications is very difficult and only plate type crystals are grown for characterization. Vanillin is a donor - acceptor substituted benzene derivative. Its molecular formula is $C_8H_8O_3$ with molecular weight 152.1. This is an isomer of MHB with same molecular formula and molecular weight. Its molecular structure is shown in figure 6.2. There exists a charge transfer between para substituted donor Hydroxy (-OH) and Carbonyl acceptor (-CHO). The meta substituted methoxy group (-OCH₃) provides a major contribution to the nonlinearity, and plays an important role in promoting the formation of noncentrosymmetric crystal structure, because the prototype compound of vanillin is 4-hydroxy benzaldehyde is centrosymmetric with the space group $P2_1/c$ [24] and shows no microscopic SHG.

Vanillin is one of the potential organic nonlinear materials which has powder efficiency 30 times that of urea. This was reported first time in 1977 by Davydov et al [25]. In 1992, Nan zang et al [26] reported the growth of plate like single crystals of vanillin as grown by solution method using acetic acid as solvent. Vanillin phase matches at room temperature and shows high SHG conversion efficiency of 58.94 % for laser light of wavelength 1064 nm to 532 nm [27]. Moreover, the crystal phase matches for diode laser at 830 nm [28] and also produced efficient frequency doubling of a pulsed Ti:Sapphire laser light [29]. Vanillin crystallizes in space group $P2_1$.

(iv) Propyl p-Hydroxy Benzoate (PHB)

This is also a A-D substituted benzene derivative with molecular formula $C_{10}H_{12}O_3$ and molecular weight 180.2. Its molecular structure is given in the figure 6.2. It has a benzene ring with (-OH) as an electron donating group and (-COOCH₂CH₂CH₃) as an electron accepting group. This material did not show second harmonic generation but third harmonic generation is expected from it.

Fig. 6.2 :Molecular structure of (a) HAP (b) MHB (c) MHBA (d) PHB

6.3 Crystal growth

Most of the organic crystals which are commonly used in nonlinear applications are reported as grown in solution method. But it is found that some defects are related to the presence of convection currents in slow evaporation solution growth [30]. The influence of growth defects on physical properties of the crystals has been studied in number of cases. In particular, direct correlation between the presence of growth sectors or bunches of dislocations and modifications of electro optic properties [31] or of laser damage threshold levels [32] have been seen in cases of KDP, KTP crystals. Similar behaviour can be expected in case of organic crystals.

6.3.1 Gel - solution technique

It has been observed that the gel growth of crystals from organic solutions decreases the number of growth defects and subsequently allows the identification of those altering the crystal properties [33]. But organic molecules are longer in size than inorganic materials and hence it is not so easy for these molecules to diffuse in to the gel cavities. In order to solve this problem, the author made an attempt to develop a suitable system to grow longer crystals to meet the device requirement, which includes the advantages of both the gel and the solution techniques. This is the report of a new technique named as "Gel - Solution technique" to grow organic crystals with fairly good size and purity. This technique includes both slow evaporation of solvent and diffusion of solvent through the gel

to provide nucleation on the surface of the gel for crystal growth. In this technique it is expected that the metallic impurities present in the sample diffuses through the gel and the resultant crystal formed above the gel will be free from these impurities compared to solution grown crystals.

In this technique, the silica hydro-gel is prepared by means of sodium meta silicate and any organic acid. After gel setting, the saturated solution of solute in appropriate solvent is poured over the gel. The crystals grow above the gel at the vicinity of gel - solute interface [figure 6.3]. This new technique is explored and used to grow organic single crystals of HAP, MHB, Vanillin and PHB.

Figure 6.3 : Schematic diagram of growth process in gel-solution technique.

6.3.2 Growth of HAP single crystals

HAP is insoluble in water like most of organic materials. Out of different solvents such as methanol, ethanol, ether and acetone, that only methanol and acetone are observed as suitable solvents for crystal growth. As with most of organic compounds,

the solubility of HAP increases linearly with respect to temperature within the considered temperature concentration boundary values. The solubility curves of HAP as a function of temperature in acetone and methanol is shown in figure 6.4. The following equations are derived from measurements.

$$\text{Acetone} \text{ -----} \rightarrow S = 3.933 t - 12.5$$

$$\text{Methanol} \text{ -----} \rightarrow S = 3.0 t + 50$$

with 't' corresponding to the temperature in Celsius degrees and 'S' is the solubility expressed in grams per solution litre.

The commercially available p-hydroxy acetophenone is purified thoroughly by means of recrystallizing several times. Silica hydro gel was prepared by mixing pure sodium meta silicate solution of specific gravity 1.04 g/cc with glacial acetic acid.

Figure 6.4 : Solubility curves of HAP. (M \rightarrow Methanol, A \rightarrow Acetone)

The gel solution thus prepared was transferred to the test tubes of 25 mm diameter and 20 cm length and allowed to set at constant temperature at 25°C. Gellation occurred after about 28 hours, depending upon gel pH of the mixture. After the gel were set, the saturated HAP solution in methanol is added slowly over the gel without disturbing the gel structure. The single crystals are observed within 3 days in case of methanol used as solvent. No good crystals are observed except plate like structure, in case where acetone is used as solvent. In case of methanol, single crystals up to 2 Cm^3 are observed with its own morphology.

6.3.3 Growth of MHB single crystals

MHB is also insoluble in water and the solvents like methanol, carbon tetra chloride, ethanol, ether and acetone are used for crystal growth. It is found that the solubility curve of MHB is not linear and it is observed that there is a decrease in increase in solubility at higher temperature as shown in solubility curve of MHB (figure 6.5). The gel-solution technique is used to grow the single crystals. The commercially available MHB is recrystallized several times using acetone as solvent. The saturated solution of MHB in both acetone and methanol are prepared. Silica hydrogel was prepared by mixing pure sodium meta silicate solution of specific gravity 1.04 g/cc with glacial acetic acid. The gel solution thus prepared is transferred to the test tubes and allowed to set at constant temperature at 25°C. After the gel were set, the MHB solution in acetone or methanol is poured over the gel without disturbing the gel structure. The

transparent, good single crystals are obtained when the solvent used was acetone and white translucent crystals are obtained when the solvent used was methanol. The crystals up to 2 Cm^3 in dimension are observed within 3 days after pouring the supernatant above the gel.

Figure 6.5 : Solubility curves of MHB.(M \rightarrow Methanol, A \rightarrow Acetone)

6.3.4 Growth of Vanillin single crystals

Vanillin is insoluble in water like most of organic materials. Out of different solvents such as methanol, ethanol, chloroform, acetone and benzene, it is observed that only the methanol and acetone are suitable solvents for crystal growth. The solubility curve of vanillin as a function of temperature (T)

in acetone and methanol are shown in figure 6.6. The following equations are derived from the measurements.

$$\text{Acetone} \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow \quad S = 12.546 \quad t - 60$$

$$\text{Methanol} \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow \quad S = 4.533 \quad t + 75$$

with 't' corresponds to the temperature in Celsius degrees and 'S' is the solubility expressed in grams per solution liter.

Silica hydrogel was prepared by mixing pure sodium meta silicate solution of specific gravity 1.03 g/cc with glacial acetic acid (volume ratio of SMS : acetic acid as 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 were used). The gel solution thus prepared were transferred to test tubes or beakers and allowed to set at constant temperature of 25°C. Gellation occurred in about 28 hours. After the gel were set, the Vanillin solution in methanol or acetone or acetone + methanol (1 : 1) was mixed with equiamount of water and added slowly over the gel without disturbing the gel structure. Transparent needle shaped crystals were obtained when solvent used was methanol and thin platelet crystals were obtained when the solvent used was acetone. On the other hand, when the solvent used was acetone + methanol (equivolume) good quality transparent large size crystals with dimensions up to 20 X 10 X 5 mm³ were obtained in three days after adding supernatant solution at the gel solution interface.

6.3.5 Growth of Propyl p-Hydroxy Benzoate single crystals

In this case, methanol is found to be the best solvent for crystal growth. The solubility of PHB is found to be

Fig. 6.6 : Solubility curves of MHBA. (M →Methanol, A →Acetone)

increasing linearly with respect to temperature. The solubility curve of PHB in methanol is shown in figure 6.7. The following equation is derived from the measurements.

$$S = 6.06 t + 90$$

To grow single crystals using gel-solution method, silica hydrogel was prepared in test tubes using sodium meta silicate and acetic acid as explained earlier. After gel was set, the saturated solution of PHB in methanol was added slowly over the gel without disturbing the gel structure.

In all these cases the chemicals used were spectroscopic analar grade with 99.9 % purity.

Figure 6.7 : Solubility curve of PHB. (M -> Methanol)

6.4 Observations and discussion

The experiments were repeated with different gel density (1.02 to 1.07 g/cc) and different gel pH (2 to 6.5). The optimum values of gel density and gel pH for growing good quality single crystals are listed in table 6.3. At low pH values (less than 3) and low specific gravity (less than 1.03 g/cc), the time for gellation was found to increase considerably (more than 6 weeks) and also the resulting gel was unstable. In this course of experiments, the effect of different parameters on the size and quality of crystal growth is determined.

Table 6.3 : Optimum values of gel density and pH.

Crystal	Gel density	Gel pH
HAP	1.04	4.2
MHB	1.04	4.2
MHBA	1.03	5.0
PHB	1.03	4.5

6.4.1 Effect of different parameters on crystal growth

(i) Effect of concentration of feed solution

The experiments are repeated by adding different concentrations of feed solutions from 0.5 M to saturated solution in all cases by keeping the other parameters at optimum values. It is found that the size of the crystals formed is first increased, attained a maximum value, at certain concentration and then decreased. In each case, with increase in concentration of feed solution, the number of nucleations also increased. The graph of concentration versus size of the crystals in all the four cases is shown in figure 6.8. In case of HAP, when the concentration of feed solution is 2.5 M, good quality rectangular shaped single crystals of size up to $2 \times 1.4 \times 0.8 \text{ cm}^3$ were obtained (figure 6.9) and at high concentration of feed solution, small plate like crystals with central hexagonal shaped rings are observed (figure 6.10). In case of MHB, when the concentration of feed solution is at 4.2 M, good quality hexagonal shaped single

crystals up to a size of $2.2 \times 2 \times 1.6 \text{ Cm}^3$ were observed (figure 6.11) and with increase in concentration, the size of crystals found to be decreased slightly till the concentration reaches the saturation point. Similar observation is found in PHB, but the maximum size of crystals is obtained when the concentration reaches to 3.7 M. In this case, the size of crystals are found to be larger than MHB and good quality single crystals up to size, $3.5 \times 2.7 \times 1.8 \text{ Cm}^3$ were also observed (figure 6.12).

Figure 6.8 : Plot of concentration of feed solution versus size of the crystals.

(A → PHB; B → HAP; C → MHB; D → MHBA)

In case of vanillin at low concentration, only thin plates of good crystals are observed and when the concentration increases to 5 M, the good quality single crystals up to dimensions 20×10

1.5 mm³ were obtained (figure 6.13) in three days after adding the feed solution above the gel. When the concentration is increased further, till the saturation level, the size of the crystals decreased and the crystals became needle shaped.

It may be argued that at low concentration, because of the lack of solute in solvent, smaller crystals are obtained. At high concentration, the size of the crystals decreased again because of increased supersaturation speed.

(ii) Effect of aging of gel

The experiment is repeated with gels aged for different periods. It is found that the older the gel slower the crystal formation. Figure 6.14 shows the plot of aging of gel versus size of HAP crystals at constant temperature. The size of crystals increased in the beginning, reached maximum value when the age of gel is 60 hours, then decreased. At low aged gels, the crystals of HAP, MHB and PHB are found to be translucent because of absorption of water present excess in gel. But at higher aged gels (at & above 60 hours), good transparent crystals are obtained.

It may be argued that when the age of gel is less than 60 hours, the solvent diffusion is more than solvent evaporation. When the gel age is 60 hours, there is an equilibrium between diffusion and evaporation. When the gel age is more than 60 hours, because of hardness of gel, the diffusion of solvent decreases compared to evaporation and hence again equilibrium is disturbed.

Fig. 6.9 : HAP single crystals grown in gel-solution technique.

Fig. 6.10 : HAP single crystal. Fig. 6.12 : PHB single crystal.

Fig. 6.11 : MHB single crystals grown in gel-solution technique.

Fig. 6.13 : Vanillin crystals grown in gel-solution technique.

Figure 6.14 : Plot of aging of gel versus size of HAP crystals.

(iii) Effect of pH of gel

By keeping the concentration of feed solution and aging of gel at constant optimum value, the pH of gel is varied by mixing different ratio of SMS and acetic acid. The optimum value of gel pH to get clear gel is found to be 4.2 in case of MHB, HAP and is 5 in case of MHBA and PHB. At lower pH values, the gellation occurred very soon and the resultant gel was not transparent. At higher pH values, the time for gellation was too high and the resultant gel was unstable.

(iv) *Effect of addition of feed solution after crystal formation*

During the crystal formation above the gel, the solute in feed solution diminishes continuously and after certain stage, the size of crystal becomes constant. By adding the feed solution again, it is found that the size of these crystals increased further. However, the quality of the resulting crystals suffer due to large dislocations and cracking. Hence, it is suggested that the size of crystals can be increased further by means of slow evaporation solution technique, by employing these crystals as seeds.

(v) *Effect of temperature*

By keeping other parameters constant at optimum values, the temperature of the system was varied using a cryostat from 25°C to 50°C. The graph of temperature versus size of the crystals is shown in figure 6.15. It is found that the size of crystals decreases with increase in temperature. This is due to the fact that the evaporation of solvent increases with increase in temperature, which disturbs the equilibrium of diffusion and evaporation.

(vi) *Effect of various acids used for gel formation*

The experiment is repeated using gels formed by different acids like acetic acid, formic acid, citric acid and malic acid. No significant effect on crystal quality is observed.

Figure 6.15 : Plot of temperature versus size of the crystals.
(A → PHB; B → HAP; C → MHB; D → MHBA)

(vii) *Effect of addition of water to the feeding solution*

In case of vanillin, when the solvent diffusion and evaporation is in progress the solute precipitates and forms crystals if water is present in the medium. If water is not there after evaporation of solvent, the vanillin appears as thin sheets above the gel. On the other hand, in case of HAP, PHB and MHB, the addition of water leads translucent crystals and thus is prohibited.

6.5 Conclusions

- (1) The proposed 'gel - solution method' is suitable for growing high quality transparent single crystals of HAP, MHB, vanillin and PHB.
- (2) Large crystals can be obtained by using methanol as solvent in case of HAP, acetone as solvent in case of MHB, both methanol + acetone (1:1) as solvent along with water in case of vanillin and methanol as solvent in case of PHB.
- (3) All the crystals are obtained at the gel - solution interface.
- (4) Experiments with the test tubes of different size showed that the size of these crystals may be increased if a large growth vessel is used.
- (5) This method can be also used for production of seed crystals and one can increase the size further by using the slow evaporation solution method.

References

- [1] Baumert J C and Gunter P ; *Appl. Phys. Letts.* 56 (1987) 554
- [2] Zyss J, Chemla D S and Nicoud J F; *J.Chem. Phys.* 74 (1981) 9
- [3] Hou Wenbo and Jiang Minhua; *J. Crystal Growth*, 133 (1993) 71
- [4] Twieg R, Azema A, Jain K and Cheng Y Y; *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 92 (1982) 208
- [5] Cassidy C, Halbout M and Tang C L ; *Opt. Commun.*, 29 (1977)
- [6] Halbout J M, Tang C L ; in *Nonlinear Optical Properties of Organic Molecules and Crystals* (Ed. Zyss J and Chemla D S) Academic Press :New York, (1987) Vol.1, CHA ii-6
- [7] Ledoux I and Zyss J ; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 73 (1982) 203
- [8] Dmitriev V G, Gurzadyan G G and Nikogosyan D N ; in *Hand book of Nonlinear Optical Crystals*, CH-4, Springer Series in Optical Sciences (1991)
- [9] Wohler F ; *Ann, Phys. (Leipzig)* 2, 12 (1928) 253
- [10] Bloembergen ; in *Nonlinear Behaviour of Molecules, Atoms and Ions in Electric, Magnetic or Electro-magnetic fields*, Elsevier Scientific Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1979.
- [11] Halbout J M, Donaldson W and Tang C L ; *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* QE-15 (1979) 1176
- [12] David F E ; *Nonlinear Optical Materials in Materials for Nonlinear Optics - Chemical Perspectives*, Ed. Marder S R, American Chemical Society, Washington (1991), Cha - 8, 128
- [13] Oudar J L and Zyss J ; *Phys. Rev.*, A-26 (1982) 2016
- [14] Huang L and Yu D Q ; in *The Application of UV Spectrum in Organic Chemistry* (Science Beijing) 1988
- [15] Levine B F and Bethea C ; *Appl. phys. lett.*, 24 (1974) 445

- [16] Oudar J L and Chemla D S ; *Opt. Commun.*, 13 (1975) 10
- [17] Oudar J L, Chemla D S and Batifol E ; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 67, 4 (1977) 1622
- [18] Carenco A, Jerphagnon J and Perigaud A ; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 66, 8 (1977) 3806
- [19] Ehooman J B, and Block D ; *J. De Physique iv*,1(1991) C7-541
- [20] Nicoud J F and Twieg R J ; in *Nonlinear Optical Properties of Organic Molecules and Crystals*, Vol.1, Ed. Chemla D S and Zyss J (Academic Press, N Y 1987) Chap-ii-3
- [21] Levine B F ; *Chem. Phys. Lett*, 37 (1976) 516
- [22] Li Zhengdong and Wu Baichang ; *Rengong Jingti Xuebao*, 18(4) (1989) 274
- [23] Cockerham P, Frazier C C and Chauchard E A ; *J. Appl. Phys.* B, 53 (1991) 275
- [24] Iwasaki F ; *Acta Cryst. Sect B*, 33 (1977) 1646
- [25] Davydov B L, Kotovshchikov S G and Nefedov V A ; *Sov. J. Quantum Electron.* 7,(1), (1977) 129.
- [26] Nan Zang, Yean, Xu Tang ; *J. Crystal Growth* 123 (1992) 255
- [27] Zang Nan, Yuan Duorong, Tao Xutang, Xu Dong ; *Chin. J. Lasers*, 20,(3), (1993) 194.
- [28] Nan Zang, Yuan Duorong, D Xu, and Jiang M H ; *Opt.Eng.* Bellingham (USA), 33, (9), (1994) 3038.
- [29] Nan Zang, Yuan Duorong, Tao Xutang, Jiang M H and Liu M G ; *Opt. Commun.(Netherlands)*, 99 (3-4) (1993) 247.
- [30] Gits-leon S and Robert M C ; *J. Cryst Growth*, 44 (1978) 345
- [31] Belouet C and Petroff J F ; *Mater. Res. Bull.* 11 (1976) 903
- [32] Endert H and Melle W ; *Cryst. Res. Tech.*, 16 (1981) 815
- [33] Andrezza P and Zyss J ; *J. Appl. Phys.*, 68 (1) (1990) 8

CHAPTER 7

COMPOSITION AND STRUCTURAL STUDIES

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7.1 Introduction

Well characterized single crystals are necessary for fundamental research as well as for any applications. In general, characterization of material is concerned with the determination of elemental composition, identification of crystalline phase, quantification of impurities and evolution of quality of atomic order. For an absolute characterization, one is required to identify all atoms or ions constituting a material, to measure these numbers and to determine their spatial positions. In practice one measures composition, specific impurities and structural features, which essentially control properties of interest and enable repeated preparation of the material with predictable behaviour.

This chapter contains observations and results of the composition and the structural studies of the crystals grown in earlier chapters.

Chemical analysis, atomic absorption spectroscopy are used to study the composition of inorganic crystals. Mass spectroscopy and NMR studies are employed for composition evaluation of organic crystals. Density of these crystals have been measured using specific gravity bottle. Structural characterization which generally involves identification of crystalline phase is carried out by powder X-ray diffractometry and infrared spectroscopy. The chapter also contains the complete solutions of the crystal structures of HAP and PHB.

7.2 Chemical analysis

The percentage of sodium, ammonia, silica, fluoride in silica doped NaF, silica doped NH_4F , silica doped NaF- NH_4F mixed crystals, the presence of ammonia, oxalate, tartarate in ADM and AT crystals and borate in BBO and SBO crystals are determined by chemical analysis. The results of chemical analysis using standard methods are given in table 7.1.

Table 7.1 : Chemical analysis of grown crystals.

Crystals	Percentage composition
Silica doped NaF	Silica = 5.2 %, Na = 53 %, F = 41.5 %
Silica doped NH_4F	Silica = 4.6 %, NH_4 = 47.6 %, F = 47.5 %
Silica doped NaF- NH_4	Silica = 8.1%, NH_4 = 19%, Na = 30%, F = 42.5%
BBO	Ba = 61.5 % ; B_2O_4 = 38.4 %
SBO	Sr = 50.4 % ; B_2O_4 = 49.4 %
ADM	NH_4 = 12.7 % ; C_2O_4 = 62 %
AT	NH_4 = 9.8 % ; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$ = 80%

Table 7.2 shows the chemical composition of silica doped NaF and silica doped NH_4F crystals grown in different acid media at constant pH of the gel. This reveals that the silica content is more in acetic acid medium crystals compared to formic and citric acid medium. For all future characterization, acetic acid medium crystals are used.

Table 7.2 : Chemical composition of fluoride crystals.

Acid medium	silica doped NaF			silica doped NH ₄ F		
	Na	F	SiO ₂	NH ₄	F	SiO ₂
Acetic	53%	41.5%	5.20	47.6%	47.5%	4.6%
Formic	53.95%	42.25%	3.75%	48%	48%	3.8%
Citric	55%	43%	1.90%	48.9%	48.9%	2.1%

7.3 Atomic absorption spectroscopy

Atomic absorption spectral analysis is used to determine the compositions of Ba²⁺ & Sr²⁺ in BBO and SBO single crystals. The percentage value of cations Ba⁺⁺ and Sr⁺⁺ are given in table 7.3.

Table 7.3 : Results of Atomic absorption analysis.

Crystal	Composition
BBO	Ba ²⁺ = 61.5 %
SBO	Sr ²⁺ = 50.5 %

The water of crystallization is estimated by thermogravimetry. The weight loss is taken as a function of temperature and is compared with the initial weight of the samples. The details of experimental technique & procedure are given in chapter 9. Only one water molecule is found in AOM molecule and no water of crystallization is observed in other crystals.

7.4 Mass spectroscopy

Mass spectroscopy is used by organic chemists to characterize organic molecules in two principal ways : (i) to measure exact molecular weights from which exact molecular formula can be determined, (ii) to indicate within a molecule the points at which it prefers to fragment ; from this, the presence of certain structural units in the organic compound can be recognized [1].

Mass spectroscopy technique has high sensitivity, capable of high accuracy measurements of elements at the ppm levels. In general, the analyte is ionized in the source of the instrument, the ion beam is focussed in the magnetic sector where ions are separated according to the mass and then collected using either a Faraday cup or an electron multiplier.

The graphical representation of the mass spectrum of a compound is constructed by plotting mass/charge ratio (m/z) versus relative abundance or percentage of base peak, where the base peak is the most intense peak in the spectrum. The base peak is assigned the arbitrary intensity value of 100, while all other peaks are given their proportionate values. The mass spectra of the grown HAP, MHB, MHBA and PHB crystals are obtained using Finnigan Mat 8230 and are given in figure 7.1 in the form of bar graph. The observed peaks are compared with standard peaks and are given in tables 7.4 and 7.5 respectively.

Figure 7.1 Mass spectra of grown organic crystals.

Table 7.4 : Mass spectral values of HAP and MHB.

Peak No.	HAP (M.wt. 136.15)			MHB (M.wt. 152.15)		
	Mass No. ob.	Mass No. st.	Intensity	Mass No. ob.	Mass No. st.	Intensity
1	43	43	10	39	39	11
2	51	51	3	63	63	5
3	63	63	5	65	65	17
4	65	65	23	93	93	22
5	93	93	33	121	121	100
6	121	121	100	122	122	8
7	122	122	8	152	152	37
8	136	136	35	153	153	3

Table 7.5 : Mass spectral values of MHBA and PHB

Peak No.	MHBA (M.wt. 152.15)			PHB (M.wt. 180.2)		
	Mass No. ob.	Mass No. st.	Intensity	Mass No. ob.	Mass No. st.	Intensity
1	15	15	50	28	28	18
2	18	18	95	121	121	40
3	29	29	39	138	138	42
4	51	51	32	150	150	90
5	52	52	30	151	151	68
6	81	81	42	163	163	65
7	151	151	100	180	180	100
8	152	152	96			

In mass spectroscopy, the last peaks obtained gives the molecular weight of the sample under examination. The molecular weight obtained from the graphs are perfectly in agreement with the standard values given in reference [2]. This confirms the identity and purity of these crystals. The peak obtained at mass number 43 in case of HAP is often an evidence for the presence of a methyl ketone group CH_3CO . The peaks at mass numbers 63, 51 in HAP, 63, 65 in MHB and 51, 52 in MHBA correspond to electron withdrawing and electron donating substituents respectively [3].

7.5 N.M.R. Spectroscopy

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) analysis confirms the purity of organic crystals. NMR spectroscopy involves the change of the spin state of a nuclear magnetic moment when the nucleus absorbs electromagnetic radiation in a strong magnetic field. Proton NMR spectrometer is used to measure the absorption of energy by hydrogen nuclei, which gives rise to resonance. This resonance causes a tiny electrical current. The amplified current is displayed as a signal on the chart paper. When the sample of an organic compound is put in a magnetic field, the difference in energy between two states (α and β) of protons produces resonance. At resonance, there is continuous excitation and relaxation [4,5]. The width of peak depends on the relaxation process. The chemical shift in NMR is the difference in ppm from reference signal to sample signal and is expressed in δ units. The δ unit is a proportionality and is thus dimensionless. The spacing between the peaks (as a result of spin splitting) is labeled J (in hertz). J is the coupling constant between two

protons and J value gives further information on molecular structure and stereo chemical features.

The ¹H NMR spectra of HAP, MHB, MHBA and PHB are recorded by using the instrument Variant E M 390, 90 MHz CW NMR spectrometer and are shown in figure 7.2. The NMR spectra of HAP and PHB are recorded in CdCl₂ as solvent and those of MHB and MHBA are recorded in acetone as solvent. The peaks observed in the spectrum are compared with standard values and are given in tables 7.6 and 7.7 respectively.

Table 7.6 : NMR values of HAP and MHB.

Peak No.	HAP		MHB	
	Observed (PPM)	Standard (PPM)	Observed (PPM)	Standard (PPM)
1	2.5	2.5	2.2	2.2
2	6.8	6.8	4.0	4.0
3	7.8	7.8	7.0	7.0
4	---	---	8.0	8.0

In NMR spectra of these compounds, the peaks corresponding to δ between 6 - 8.5 correspond to aromatic groups (Ar-H). The peak at 2.6 in HAP, at 2.2 & 4.0 in MHB and at 2.1 & 3.9 in MHBA indicate the presence of carbonyl substituents. The peak at 9.8 in case of MHBA shows the presence of aldehydic group (CHO). The peak at 1.7 in PHB proves the presence of allylic (C=C-CH₃) group. The observed peaks exactly match with the standard values.

Figure 7.2 NMR spectra of grown organic crystals.

Table 7.7 : NMR values of MHBA and PHB.

Peak No.	MHBA		PHB	
	Observed (PPM)	Standard (PPM)	Observed (PPM)	Standard (PPM)
1	2.1	2.1	1.0	1.0
2	3.9	3.9	1.7	1.7
3	7.0	7.0	4.3	4.3
4	7.5	7.4	6.9	6.9
5	9.8	9.8	7.9	7.9

and once again the study confirms the purity of the crystals.

7.6 Powder X-ray diffraction studies

The powder diffractometer is widely used for recording diffraction patterns from polycrystalline samples [6 - 10]. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of all the varieties of crystals are recorded with XRD - JDX - 8P JEOL X-ray diffractometer using Cu K_{α} radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm) at a speed of $2^{\circ}/m$ and the observed interplanar distance, d values are calculated. These observed ' d ' values of some varieties of grown crystals are compared with standard ' d ' values for particular system and are given in tables 7.8 to 7.16.

Table 7.8 : Powder XRD values of silica doped NaF.

Peak No.	2 θ (degrees)	d observed	hkl	I/I ₀
1	10	8.75	1 0 0	45
2	17.5	5.06	0 0 1	37
3	20	4.44	1 3 0	100
4	21	4.23	0 2 1	65
5	27	3.30	2 0 1	40
6	29.5	3.029	2 2 1	41
7	31	2.885	2 4 0	36
8	36	2.495	0 1 2	16
9	39.5	2.281	0 6 1	56
10	43	2.103	4 2 0	9
11	45	2.014	2 3 2	12
12	46.5	1.953	3 5 1	8
13	48	1.89	3 1 2	8
14	51	1.791	3 3 2	59
15	52	1.7588	3 7 0	15
16	55.5	1.656	5 3 0	11
17	58	1.59	5 4 0	21
18	59	1.5655	2 1 3	16
19	63	1.475	0 10 1	12
20	67	1.397	2 10 1	8

Table 7.9 : Powder XRD values of ADM.

Peak No.	2θ (degrees)	d observed	d standard	hkl	I/I ₀
1	14	6.325	6.320	1 1 0	95
2	17.15	5.170	5.150	0 2 0	35
3	23.25	3.825	3.800	0 0 1	70
4	27.15	3.284	3.256	1 1 1	60
5	28.90	3.089	3.057	0 2 1	95
6	30.90	2.894	2.858	1 2 1	60
7	33.1	2.706	2.666	2 1 1	100
8	33.9	2.644	2.606	2 3 0	50
9	34.0	2.636	2.592	3 1 0	45
10	36.0	2.494	2.453	1 4 0	35
11	36.4	2.468	2.429	1 3 1	25
12	37.2	2.416	2.374	3 2 0	25
13	41.25	2.185	2.142	3 1 1	25

Table 7.10 : Powder XRD values of AT.

Peak No.	2θ (degrees)	d observed	d standard	hkl	I/I_0
1	12.50	7.080	7.081	0 0 1	100
2	17.56	5.051	5.032	-1 1 0	45
3	19.04	4.661	4.649	0 1 1	75
4	20.00	4.432	4.408	2 0 0	65
5	21.30	4.173	4.158	-1 1 1	20
6	21.75	4.08	4.06	1 1 1	20
7	24.07	3.690	3.677	2 0 1	25
8	27.28	3.261	3.238	1 0 2	85
9	28.80	3.081	3.067	0 2 0	45
10	30.50	2.90	2.897	1 2 0	20
11	30.85	2.882	2.864	1 1 2	25
12	32.10	2.78	2.753	-3 0 1	25
13	32.7	2.73	2.704	2 0 2	40
14	33.50	2.662	2.668	1 2 1	45

Table 7.11 : Powder XRD values of HAP.

Peak No.	2θ (degrees)	d standard	d observed	hkl	I/I ₀
1	11.80	7.47	7.49	1 0 0	70
2	13.50	6.59	6.56	-1 0 1	50
3	16.00	5.57	5.54	-1 1 0	60
4	17.30	5.10	5.13	-1 1 1	80
5	18.25	4.84	4.86	1 1 1	40
6	19.00	4.64	4.67	0 1 2	80
7	20.50	4.33	4.33	1 0 2	100
8	21.50	4.11	4.13	0 2 0	100
9	22.50	3.924	3.95	0 2 1	100
10	23.20	3.809	3.83	0 0 3	70
11	23.70	3.723	3.75	2 0 0	90
12	25.00	3.522	3.56	-1 0 3	80
13	26.00	3.397	3.43	-2 1 0	90
14	27.00	3.287	3.30	-2 0 2	90
15	27.80	3.185	3.21	2 1 1	90
16	30.00	2.950	2.98	1 2 2	80
17	31.00	2.876	2.88	0 0 4	70
18	34.50	2.549	2.59	-1 3 0	50
19	39.70	2.226	2.27	0 0 5	40
20	40.00	2.208	2.25	-1 0 5	40
21	42.00	2.185	2.15	2 3 1	40

Table 7.12 : Powder XRD values of MHB.

Peak No.	2θ (degrees)	d observed	d standard	hkl	I/I ₀
1	9.22	9.57	9.529	0 0 1	8
2	10.10	8.757	8.852	1 1 0	8
3	14.05	6.300	6.334	0 2 0	16
4	15.50	5.716	5.701	1 1 2	8
5	17.10	5.185	5.189	2 0 0	45
6	17.45	5.06	5.092	1 3 1	4
7	17.83	4.955	4.964	1 3 0	8
8	18.60	4.745	4.764	0 0 2	65
9	20.10	4.396	4.426	2 2 0	6
10	21.50	4.114	4.118	3 1 1	20
11	25.20	3.506	3.519	3 3 2	100
12	26.17	3.376	3.389	3 1 0	55
13	27.53	3.209	3.154	3 3 3	25
14	31.40	2.814	2.826	0 6 0	8
15	36.0	2.455	2.464	2 4 4	20
16	37.32	2.367	2.363	5 3 4	8
17	41.26	2.141	2.138	6 0 5	6
18	50.34	1.755	1.755	5 5 6	12

Table 7.13 : Powder XRD values of MHBA.

Peak No.	2θ (degrees)	d observed	d standard	hkl	I/I ₀
1	13.0	6.810	6.79	0 0 2	100
2	14.5	6.109	6.13	2 0 0	9
3	17.0	5.21	5.19	2 1 -1	5
4	17.30	5.12	5.11	0 1 2	55
5	21.0	4.230	4.212	1 1 2	5
6	21.65	4.104	4.080	3 0 0	6
7	22.53	3.946	3.921	0 1 3	23
8	23.75	3.746	3.723	2 0 2	6
9	25.75	3.459	3.428	4 0 -3	16
10	26.65	3.345	3.342	1 1 3	13
11	26.90	3.314	3.317	2 2 -2	22
12	26.95	3.308	3.305	2 2 0	26
13	27.10	3.290	3.293	3 1 -4	14
14	28.6	3.121	3.116	1 2 -3	7
17	39.5				
18	40.2				
19	42				
20	43				
21	50				

Table 7.14 : Powder XRD values of PHB.

Peak No.	2θ (degrees)	d observed	d standard	hkl	I/I ₀
1	10	8.93	8.90	-1 1 0	50
2	11	8.04	8.00	-1 1 1	70
3	12.8	6.92	6.95	0 2 0	20
4	16.5	5.37	5.40	-1 1 2	100
6	18	4.92	4.85	1 2 1	16
7	19.5	4.55	4.55	2 0 1	40
8	20.5	4.33	4.30	2 1 1	30
9	21.2	4.19	4.18	-1 3 1	30
10	24	3.71	3.72	-3 1 0	50
11	25.5	3.49	3.50	2 0 2	100
12	27.0	3.30	3.30	-2 2 3	10
13	28	3.19	3.20	-3 1 3	20
14	30	2.98	2.98	-2 4 0	10
15	31	2.88	2.90	-1 1 4	10
16	33.5	2.67	2.67	-3 1 4	20
17	39.5	2.28	2.28	-3 0 5	10
18	40.2	2.24	2.24	2 0 4	10
19	42	2.15	2.15	-2 6 0	16
20	43	2.10	2.10	-2 3 5	8
21	50	1.82	1.82	2 2 5	8

Table 7.15 : Powder XRD values of BBO.

Peak No.	2θ (degrees)	d observed	d standard	hkl	I/I_0
1	14.10	6.28	6.281	1 1 0	15
2	24.40	3.64	3.618	3 0 0	40
3	25.15	3.54	3.513	1 1 3	100
4	28.20	3.16	3.131	2 2 0	16
5	28.95	3.08	3.050	1 0 4	26
6	35.07	2.54	2.520	2 2 3	37
7	35.20	2.51	2.513	2 1 4	18
8	37.34	2.40	2.366	1 4 0	11
9	41.67	2.15	2.120	0 0 6	16
10	42.74	2.10	2.067	1 4 3	28
11	43.95	2.05	2.010	1 1 6	11
12	48.27	1.86	1.830	0 3 6	24
13	62.00	1.49	1.487	3 3 6	9
14	67.00	1.39	1.379	1 1 9	17

In powder X-ray diffraction studies the h k l values of silica doped NaF, MHB, HAP and PHB crystals are computed by knowing their crystal system.

Table 7.16 : Powder XRD values of SBO.

Peak No.	2 θ (degrees)	d observed	d standard	hkl	I/I ₀
1	14.69	6.03	6.013	0 2 0	70
2	25.48	3.49	3.467	1 1 1	100
3	26.83	3.32	3.292	2 0 0	35
4	27.90	3.19	3.176	2 1 0	45
5	28.48	3.13	3.101	1 2 1	16
6	29.00	3.08	3.004	0 4 0	35
7	31.50	2.84	2.888	2 2 0	40
8	33.50	2.67	2.688	1 3 1	65
9	39.80	2.26	2.221	2 4 0	30
10	41.00	2.19	2.169	0 0 2	25
11	44.00	2.05	2.041	0 2 2	20
12	45.00	2.01	2.003	0 6 3	60
13	46.00	1.97	1.934	3 1 1	45
14	52.00	1.75	1.760	3 3 1	25
15	59.00	1.56	1.5518	1 7 1	20
16	77.00	1.23	1.203	5 3 1	16

7.7 Infra-red spectra and assignment of bands

This is one of the most widely used tools for the detection of functional groups in the pure compounds and mixtures and for compound comparison [11]. Infrared absorption spectra of these gel grown crystals are recorded on Shimadzu IR 408 (Japan) infrared absorption spectro photometer using KBr pallet

technique. The infrared absorption spectra of AOM and AT single crystals are shown in figure 7.3. The assignments of observed bands are given in tables 7.17 and 7.18.

The IR absorption spectra of organic crystals HAP, MHB, MHBA and PHB are depicted in figure 7.4 and the assignments of observed bands are given in tables 7.19 to 7.22 respectively.

In IR spectral analysis, all organic crystals produce bands at nearly 3300 cm^{-1} . This shows the presence of -OH functional groups in all 4 types of crystals. The frequency region from 4000 cm^{-1} to 1500 cm^{-1} is called functional group region. In this region, the peaks depend on functional groups present in each benzene ring. The frequency region corresponding to 1500 cm^{-1} to 600 cm^{-1} is considered as finger print region, in which all crystals show their unique absorptions. There is a good agreement between observed values and standard values. This study once again confirms the purity of the grown crystals.

Table 7.17 : IR bands and their assignments of ADM $[(\text{NH}_4)\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{H}_2\text{O}]$

Peak No.	Observed	Standard	Assignment
1	3100	3200	O - H Stretch
2	2150	2150	C = O Stretch
3	1680	1690	C = O A-stretch
4	1600	1600	HO - H Bend
5	1480	1480	N - H Stretch
6	1420	1420	N - H Stretch
7	1400	1400	N - H Stretch
8	1310	1315	C - O Stretch
9	810	810	N - O Stretch
10	750	750	CO_2 Bend

A-strech = Asymmetric stretch

Table 7.18 : IR bands and their assignments of AT $[\text{NH}_4\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CO}_2]_2$

Peak No.	Observed	Standard	Assignment
1	3200	3200	O - H Stretch
2	1650	1650	C = H Stretch
3	1480	1480	C - H Bend
4	1420	1420	NH_4 Stretch
5	1090	1090	C - O(H) Stretch
6	980	980	C - C Stretch
7	840	835	OH OOP bend
8	780	780	CO_2 Bend

OOP bend = Out of plane bend

Table 7.19 : IR bands and their assignments of HAP.

Peak No.	Observed (cm^{-1})	Standard (cm^{-1})	Assignment
1	3200	3130	O - H Stretch
2	2940	2940	C - H Stretch
3	1650	1640	C = O Stretch
4	1590	1590	C - C Stretch
5	1520	1520	C - C Stretch
6	1450	1450	C - H Bend
7	1370	1370	C - CH Bend
8	1280	1280	O - H Bend
9	1240	1240	C - H Bend
10	1160	1160	C - H Bend
11	970	970	C - H Bend
12	830	830	= C - H Bend

Table 7.20 : IR bands and their assignments of MHB.

Peak No.	Observed (cm^{-1})	Standard (cm^{-1})	Assignment
1	3300	3300	O - H Stretch
2	1670	1670	C = O Stretch
3	1610	1610	C = O Stretch
4	1590	1590	C - C Stretch
5	1520	1520	C - H Stretch
6	1430	1430	C - H Bend
7	1370	1370	C - CH Bend
8	1320	1320	C - O Stretch
9	1280	1280	O - H Bend
10	1240	1240	C - H Bend
11	1160	1160	C - H Bend
12	1120	1120	C - H Bend
13	950	950	C - H Bend
14	850	850	= C - H Bend
15	770	770	= C - H Bend

Table 7.21 : IR bands and their assignments of MHBA.

Peak No.	Observed (cm^{-1})	Standard (cm^{-1})	Assignment
1	3200	3200	O - H Stretch
2	2900	2940	C - H Stretch
3	1670	1670	C = O Stretch
4	1590	1590	C - C Stretch
5	1520	1520	C - C Stretch
6	1450	1450	C - H Bend
7	1430	1430	C - H Bend
8	1370	1370	C - CH Bend
9	1300	1300	C - O Stretch
10	1270	1270	O - H Bend
11	1210	1210	C - H Bend
12	1150	1150	C - H Bend
13	1120	1120	C - H Bend
14	1030	1030	C - H Bend
15	820	820	= C - H Bend
16	780	780	= C - H Bend
17	730	730	= C - H Bend

Table 7.22 : IR bands and their assignments of PHB.

Peak No.	Observed (cm^{-1})	Standard (cm^{-1})	Assignment
1	3200	3300	O - H Stretch
2	2940	2940	C = C Stretch
3	1670	1670	C = O Stretch
4	1560	1560	C - C Stretch
5	1450	1450	C - H Bend
6	1390	1390	C - CH Bend
7	1280	1280	O - H Bend
8	1240	1240	C - H Bend
9	1180	1180	C - H Bend
10	970	970	C - H Bend
11	850	850	= C - H Bend
12	780	780	= C - H Bend

Figure 7.3 : IR spectra of grown crystals.

Figure 7.4 : IR spectra of grown crystals.

Figure 7.4 : IR spectra of grown crystals.

7.8 Density measurements

The density of all the varieties of gel grown crystals are determined using a specific gravity bottle at ambient temperature. The average density of all crystals are listed in table 7.23 and are compared with the standard values.

Table 7.23 : Density and melting point of grown crystals.

Crystals	density (measured)	density (standard)	M.P.
Si - NaF	2.83	---	600°C
Si - NH ₄	1.46	---	465°C
BBO	1.012	1.0155	---
SBO	3.287	3.335	---
ADM	1.492	1.541	133°C
AT	1.597	1.599	142°C
HAP	1.209	1.266	109°C
MHB	1.361	1.382	131°C
MHBA	1.334	1.358	71°C
PHB	1.261	1.279	150°C

The bulk density observed in the grown crystals are compared with the X-ray density obtained from single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. It is observed that the value of X-ray density is greater than that of the bulk density. This discrepancy in the value of bulk density and X-ray density may be due to the lattice distortions induced by the presence of point

defects. The formation of Schottky defects in ionic crystals would increase the bulk volume of the crystal because of the formation of new atomic layer on the crystal surface and in which case the bulk density would decrease. Thus, the observations indicates the formation of Schottky defects in these crystals.

7.9 Etching studies

Etching technique is a powerful tool for studying the nature of dislocations present in the crystals. The studies of identification, origin and characterizations of defects such as grain boundaries, slip lines, dislocations, stacking faults, volume defects, vacancies and other depends heavily on etching phenomena. The principle behind the selection of etchants and the mechanism of their actions are poorly understood in spite of many attempts made by Gilman and Johnston in LiF [12], Thyagarajan and Urusovskaya in CsI [13] and Baranoya and Nadgarnyi in NaCl [14] ionic crystals.

By choosing proper etchants, it is possible to investigate the kinetics of etching to the dissolution process at dislocations. The study of the etching of dislocations would provide additional information on the structural defects and the role of crystallographic polarity on the dissolution characteristics.

The damage and inclusion free crystals were selected and a number of analaR grade chemical reagents were examined for possible use as dislocation etchants. Crystals were etched at

temperature. Neither the crystals nor the etchants were agitated during the entire period of etching, to avoid any discrepancy that may arise due to stirring. The results are summarized in table 7.24, which contains the most suitable etchant, the type of etch pattern observed in each case and the time for producing these etch pattern.

Table 7.24 : Results of etching studies on grown crystals.

Crystals	etchant	etching pattern	time
Si - NaF	Ethyl alcohol	pyramidal pits	10 sec
Si - NH ₄	HCl (1M)	spike-like pits	5 sec
Si-NaF-NH ₄ F	HCl (1M)	spike-like pits	5 sec
ADM	oxalic acid (1M)	Tiny etch pits	5 sec
Si doped NaF	NaOH (1M)	Point bottomed pits	10 sec
AT	Oxalic acid (1M)	Rectangular pits	5 sec
	NaOH (1M)	Flat bottomed pits	10 sec
HAP	Acetic acid (2M)	General dissolution	15 sec
MHB	Acetic acid (2M)	Rough and smooth bands	8 sec
MHBA	Water	General dissolution	15 sec
PHB	Acetic acid (2M)	Rough and smooth bands	8 sec

The studies on the effects of various etchants, such as ethyl acetate, toluene and acetone on organic crystals (HAP, MHB, MHBA and PHB) indicate the polar nature of the crystals. It is known that the crystal having a positive polarization charge etches rapidly and appears uneven, compared with negative charge

regions, which appear smooth. It can be argued that the alternate rough and smooth bands can be associated with the domain nature of the polar crystals.

7.10 Single crystal X-ray diffraction studies

The crystal structures of HAP and PHB are not reported so far. Hence, a detailed structural analysis of HAP and PHB are carried out. The unit cell parameters obtained for the other crystals are listed in the form of table 7.26.

Table 7.26 : Unit cell parameters of grown crystals.

Crystal [Reference]	Lattice parameters (Å°)	Space group	Uniaxial / biaxial
Silica doped NaF	orthorhombic, $a = 8.8696$ $b = 15.352$, $c = 5.0451$	P_{222}	----
AT [15]	monoclinic, $a = 7.083$, $b = 6.128$, $c = 8.808$	$P2_1$	biaxial
ADM [16]	orthorhombic, $a = 8.035$ $b = 10.30$, $c = 3.801$	$P2_12_12_1$	biaxial
MHB [17]	orthorhombic, $a = 13.768$ $b = 11.939$, $c = 3.758$	C_c	biaxial
MHB [18]	orthorhombic, $a = 14.857$ $b = 11.875$, $c = 3.758$	$P2_1$	biaxial
BBO [19]	rhombohedral, $a = 12.53$ $c = 12.726$, $\tau = 1.015$	$R3_c$	uniaxial
SBO [20]	orthorhombic, $a = 6.589$ $b = 12.018$, $c = 4.337$	$Pnca$	uniaxial

The single crystal diffraction studies on silica doped NaF of both acetic acid and formic acid medium are used to calculate unit cell dimensions. The obtained unit cell dimensions are found to be same in both cases as $a = 8.8696 \text{ \AA}$; $b = 15.3522 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 5.0451 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = 90^\circ$; $\beta = 90^\circ$; $\gamma = 90^\circ$; and the space group is found to be P_{222} . This shows the crystal structure is changed from cubic system to orthorhombic system due to doping. This is due to the larger size of silicon atoms compared to sodium and fluorine atoms.

7.10.1 Crystal structures of HAP and PHB

(i) Introduction :

The object of a crystal structure determination is to locate the atomic positions within the unit cell and thus completely define the whole structure. The intensity of a sufficient number of X-ray diffraction maxima determine a crystal structure. The available intensity usually exceeds the number of parameters needed to describe the structure. Each measured intensity can be correlated to the magnitudes of the structure factors. However, the elucidation of the crystal structure requires also a knowledge of the phase of the structure factors. Thus the lack of knowledge of the structure factors prevents us from directly computing an electron density map and hence showing the positions of the atoms in the unit cell. The different methods of determination of crystal structures have been neatly explained by Wolfson [21].

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The crystal structures of p-hydroxy benzophenone and methyl p-hydroxy benzoate have been reported [17, 22]. The single crystals of p-hydroxy acetophenone [HAP] and propyl p-hydroxy benzoate have been grown by gel-solution technique as described in chapter 6. The complete structure determination of these crystals by X-ray single crystal diffraction study is described here.

(ii) Single crystal structure of HAP :

(a) Experimental :

The crystals chosen for data collection were small pieces of pure single crystals having dimensions as 0.30 X 0.12 X 0.10 mm. Three dimensional intensity data were collected on an ENRAF NONIUS CAD - 4 diffractometer with $\omega/2\theta$ scan mode of 2.66 to 24.92 degrees using $\text{MoK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.71069 \text{ \AA}$) radiation with scan angle $(0.7 + 2.10 \tan \theta)^\circ$ and scan width of $(0.35 + 1.05 \tan \theta)$ mm. The data were corrected by applying Lorentz, polarization and absorption corrections. Reflections in the hemisphere with index ranges $0 \leq h \leq 9$, $0 \leq k \leq 9$, $-13 \leq l \leq 13$ were measured. A total of 1417 reflections were measured of which 734 were unique and 802 significant reflections observed with $I \geq 3 \sigma(I)$.

(b) Observations and discussions :

The unit cell dimensions were obtained from least square fit of 25 well centred reflections having $(9^\circ \leq \theta \leq 14^\circ)$. Two standard reflections (1 3 0 ; 2 3 1) are monitored every 3600

secs of exposure time showed no significant variation in hydrogen coordinates and its displacement parameter intensity. The maximum time spent on any measurement is 60 secs as tabulated in table 7.30. Selected diffraction angles and the background count was half the scan time. Hydrogen atoms are listed in table 7.31.

The structure solution was carried out by direct methods, using the program SHELX 86 [23] and refined using full matrix least squares method using SHELXL 93. All the non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. All the hydrogen atoms could be located from different electronic density maps and were refined with isotropic thermal parameters. The convergence was achieved at a final $R_1 = 0.0319$, $wR_2 = 0.0840$ with individual weighting scheme based on counting statistics.

$$w = 1 / [\sigma^2 (f_o)^2 + (0.0629 \times P)^2 + 0.06 \times P]$$

$$P = (f_o^2 + 2f_c^2) / 3$$

$S = 1.072$ for 227 parameters. The maximum and minimum electron density in the final difference electron density map are 0.088 and $-0.146 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$.

The results on unit cell parameters and estimated standard deviations for HAP are tabulated in table 7.26. The observed and calculated structure factors of HAP are listed in appendix I, along with corresponding hkl values.

The atomic coordinates and their equivalent isotropic displacement parameters for all non-hydrogen atoms are listed in table 7.27. Table 7.28 contains the bond lengths and bond angles of all the atoms of HAP. The positional and anisotropic thermal parameters for the non-hydrogen atoms are given in table 7.29.

The hydrogen coordinates and isotropic displacement parameters are tabulated in table 7.30. Some selected torsion angles for non-hydrogen atoms are listed in table 7.31.

The ORTEP diagrams of both the molecules along with the numbering scheme are depicted in figure 7.5 (a) and 7.5 (b). The thermal ellipsoids are at 50 % probability level. The packing of the molecules in the unit cell along with the hydrogen bonding is shown in figure 7.6. The least square planes passing through all non-hydrogen atoms for both the molecules and deviations from them are listed in table 7.32.

It is found that HAP single crystals are monoclinic and belong to noncentrosymmetric space group $P2_1$. Both the molecules in a unit cell are found to be almost planar and no noticeable deviations are observed when compared to each other. It is also found that the two molecules are at an angle of 4.89° with each other. The intermolecular hydrogen bonding O - H - O between donor and acceptor in HAP single crystal is also noticed. The hydrogen bond distances are given in table 7.33.

Formula	$C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_2$	$C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_2$
Empirical formula	$C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_2$	$C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_2$
Molecular weight	204.23	204.23
Z	2	2
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1$	$P2_1$
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 10.121(3)$ Å	$a = 10.121(3)$ Å
	$b = 12.458(4)$ Å	$b = 12.458(4)$ Å
	$c = 13.121(4)$ Å	$c = 13.121(4)$ Å
Angles	$\beta = 109.87(2)^\circ$	$\beta = 109.87(2)^\circ$
Volume	1630.6 Å ³	1630.6 Å ³
Density (calculated)	1.273 g/cm ³	1.273 g/cm ³
Absorption coefficient	0.100 mm ⁻¹	0.100 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	1320	1320
Crystal size	0.12 x 0.12 x 0.12 mm	0.12 x 0.12 x 0.12 mm
Theta range for data collection	2.49 to 24.92 deg	2.49 to 24.92 deg
Theta ranges	0 to 25.00 deg	0 to 25.00 deg
Reflections collected	1000	1000
Independent reflections	[Int] = 0	[Int] = 0
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²
Rs/restraints/parameters	0.022/0/227	0.022/0/227
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.000	1.000
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	R = 0.019, wR = 0.040	R = 0.019, wR = 0.040
Extinction coefficient	0	0
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.144 and -0.144 e/Å ³	0.144 and -0.144 e/Å ³

Table 7.26 : Unit cell parameters and standard deviations for HAP.

Specifications	Parameters
Empirical formula	$C_8H_8O_2$
Formula weight	136.14
Temperature	300 K
Wavelength	0.71069 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1$
Unit cell dimensions (7)	$a = 7.692(2) \text{ Å}; \alpha = 90^\circ$
	$b = 8.2956(7) \text{ Å}; \beta = 94.99^\circ$
	$c = 11.239(3) \text{ Å}; \tau = 90^\circ$
Volume	714.4(3) Å ³
Z	4
Density (calculated)	1.266 Mg / m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.091 mm ⁻¹
F (000)	288
Crystal size	0.30 X 0.12 X 0.10 mm
Theta range for data collection	2.66 to 24.92 deg.
Index ranges	$0 \leq h \leq 9; 0 \leq k \leq 9; -13 \leq l \leq 13$
Reflections collected	802
Independent reflections	734 [R (int) = 0.0150]
Refinement method	Full-matrix-block least-squares on F ²
Data/ restraints /parameters	734 / 1 / 227
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.072
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)	$R_1 = 0.0319, wR_2 = 0.0840$
Extinction coefficient	0.015(4)
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.088 and -0.146 e.Å ⁻³

Table 7.12. Atomic coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and equivalent isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for HAP. $U(\text{eq})$ is defined as one third of the trace of the orthogonalized U_{ij} tensor.

	x	y	z	$U(\text{eq})$
C(1)	2109(6)	1900(6)	1857(3)	68(1)
C(2)	2466(5)	3166(4)	2521(4)	50(1)
C(3)	3370(5)	3013(5)	3640(4)	63(1)
C(4)	3809(5)	1416(5)	4053(4)	60(1)
C(5)	3318(6)	114(5)	3356(4)	62(1)
C(6)	2468(6)	343(5)	2255(3)	67(1)
O(1)	3768(5)	-1296(4)	3846(3)	92(1)
C(7)	2121(6)	4884(6)	2073(5)	74(1)
O(2)	2504(5)	6038(4)	2647(5)	110(1)
C(8)	1241(7)	5131(7)	845(5)	92(2)
C(1')	3411(7)	8334(6)	8642(4)	64(1)
C(2')	2581(6)	8029(5)	7520(4)	62(1)
C(3')	2057(6)	9468(5)	6798(4)	57(1)
C(4')	2494(7)	10974(5)	7240(4)	65(1)
C(5')	3371(6)	11138(5)	8387(4)	61(1)
C(6')	3758(7)	9766(6)	9071(4)	70(1)
O(1')	3774(5)	12659(4)	8817(3)	88(1)
C(7')	2163(7)	6445(5)	7100(5)	72(1)
O(2')	2616(6)	5287(4)	7794(4)	99(1)
C(8')	1292(11)	6127(7)	5913(6)	94(2)

C(4')-H(3') 1.09
 C(5')-O(1') 1.15
 C(5')-C(6') 1.36
 C(6')-H(4') 1.09
 O(1')-H(5') 0.84
 C(7')-O(2') 1.16
 C(7')-C(8') 1.39
 C(8')-H(6') 1.09
 C(8')-H(7') 0.73
 C(8')-H(8') 0.91
 C(2)-C(1)-C(6) 122.81
 C(2)-C(1)-H(1) 122.5
 C(6)-C(1)-H(1) 117.5
 C(1)-C(2)-C(3) 124.31
 C(1)-C(2)-C(7) 122.41
 C(3)-C(2)-C(7) 114.41
 C(2)-C(3)-C(4) 117.61
 C(2)-C(3)-H(2) 120.5
 C(4)-C(3)-H(2) 122.5
 C(5)-C(4)-C(3) 115.41
 C(5)-C(4)-H(3) 117.5
 C(3)-C(4)-H(3) 121.5
 O(1)-C(5)-C(4) 114.5

Table 7.13. Bond lengths [Å] and angles [deg] for HAP.

C(1)-C(2)	1.304(5)
C(1)-C(6)	1.387(6)
C(1)-H(1)	0.93(6)
C(2)-C(3)	1.389(6)
C(2)-C(7)	1.527(6)
C(3)-C(4)	1.434(6)
C(3)-H(2)	1.02(11)
C(4)-C(5)	1.368(6)
C(4)-H(3)	1.07(6)
C(5)-O(1)	1.326(5)
C(5)-C(6)	1.362(6)
C(6)-H(4)	1.01(5)
O(1)-H(5)	0.992(3)
C(7)-O(2)	1.177(6)
C(7)-C(8)	1.497(8)
C(8)-H(6)	0.932(5)
C(8)-H(7)	0.969(6)
C(8)-H(8)	1.029(5)
C(1')-C(6')	1.301(6)
C(1')-C(2')	1.386(7)
C(1')-H(1')	0.94(5)
C(2')-C(7')	1.424(7)
C(2')-C(3')	1.479(6)
C(3')-C(4')	1.376(7)
C(3')-H(2')	1.03(4)
C(4')-C(5')	1.408(6)
C(4')-H(3')	1.01(5)
C(5')-O(1')	1.377(5)
C(5')-C(6')	1.391(6)
C(6')-H(4')	0.99(5)
O(1')-H(5')	1.150(4)
C(7')-O(2')	1.267(6)
C(7')-C(8')	1.464(9)
C(8')-H(6')	1.04(4)
C(8')-H(7')	0.74(5)
C(8')-H(8')	1.08(4)
C(2)-C(1)-C(6)	122.7(4)
C(2)-C(1)-H(1)	123(4)
C(6)-C(1)-H(1)	113(4)
C(1)-C(2)-C(3)	120.6(3)
C(1)-C(2)-C(7)	122.8(4)
C(3)-C(2)-C(7)	116.3(4)
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	117.6(4)
C(2)-C(3)-H(2)	120(5)
C(4)-C(3)-H(2)	123(5)
C(5)-C(4)-C(3)	119.9(4)
C(5)-C(4)-H(3)	117(3)
C(3)-C(4)-H(3)	121(3)
O(1)-C(5)-C(4)	114.2(4)

O(1)-C(5)-C(6)	126.0(4)
C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	119.8(4)
C(5)-C(6)-C(1)	119.3(4)
C(5)-C(6)-H(4)	113(3)
C(1)-C(6)-H(4)	127(3)
C(5)-O(1)-H(5)	115.6(3)
O(2)-C(7)-C(8)	117.7(5)
O(2)-C(7)-C(2)	123.4(5)
C(8)-C(7)-C(2)	118.9(5)
C(7)-C(8)-H(6)	114.6(6)
C(7)-C(8)-H(7)	111.6(4)
H(6)-C(8)-H(7)	111.1(5)
C(7)-C(8)-H(8)	109.3(4)
H(6)-C(8)-H(8)	106.1(4)
H(7)-C(8)-H(8)	103.4(6)
C(6')-C(1')-C(2')	124.5(4)
C(6')-C(1')-H(1')	116(3)
C(2')-C(1')-H(1')	120(3)
C(1')-C(2')-C(7')	122.9(4)
C(1')-C(2')-C(3')	115.7(4)
C(7')-C(2')-C(3')	121.3(4)
C(4')-C(3')-C(2')	119.2(4)
C(4')-C(3')-H(2')	123(2)
C(2')-C(3')-H(2')	118(2)
C(3')-C(4')-C(5')	120.0(4)
C(3')-C(4')-H(3')	118(3)
C(5')-C(4')-H(3')	121(3)
O(1')-C(5')-C(6')	121.7(4)
O(1')-C(5')-C(4')	119.0(4)
C(6')-C(5')-C(4')	119.3(4)
C(1')-C(6')-C(5')	121.0(5)
C(1')-C(6')-H(4')	119(2)
C(5')-C(6')-H(4')	118(2)
C(5')-O(1')-H(5')	106.3(3)
O(2')-C(7')-C(2')	117.0(5)
O(2')-C(7')-C(8')	120.3(5)
C(2')-C(7')-C(8')	122.7(5)
C(7')-C(8')-H(6')	106(2)
C(7')-C(8')-H(7')	126(4)
H(6')-C(8')-H(7')	110(4)
C(7')-C(8')-H(8')	116(2)
H(6')-C(8')-H(8')	117(3)
H(7')-C(8')-H(8')	82(4)

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms:

3719(59)	51)	143(47)
1289(52)	43)	131(36)
2397(71)	45)	371(49)
4532(52)	47)	33(41)
4020		30
1218(46)	47)	10(33)
1538(69)	55)	16(40)
169(51)	52)	15(32)

Table 7.14 Anisotropic displacement parameters ($\text{Å}^2 \times 10^3$) for HAP.
 The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form:
 $-2 \pi^2 [h^2 a^2 U_{11} + \dots + 2 h k a^* b^* U_{12}]$

	U11	U22	U33	U23	U13	U12
C(1)	85(3)	68(3)	50(2)	10(2)	-5(2)	20(2)
C(2)	46(2)	39(2)	66(2)	-2(2)	0(2)	2(2)
C(3)	45(2)	65(3)	81(3)	-11(2)	14(2)	1(2)
C(4)	51(2)	70(3)	57(2)	4(2)	-9(2)	7(2)
C(5)	79(3)	47(2)	61(2)	0(2)	8(2)	-5(2)
C(6)	86(3)	60(3)	50(2)	-9(2)	-21(2)	-19(2)
O(1)	140(3)	58(2)	72(2)	-7(2)	-25(2)	2(2)
C(7)	55(3)	60(3)	108(4)	2(3)	11(2)	15(2)
O(2)	97(3)	46(2)	187(4)	-26(2)	13(3)	-1(2)
C(8)	81(3)	96(4)	104(4)	40(3)	28(3)	24(3)
C(1')	80(3)	57(3)	55(3)	21(2)	2(2)	17(2)
C(2')	60(3)	60(3)	69(3)	5(2)	22(2)	15(2)
C(3')	60(3)	56(2)	55(2)	15(2)	1(2)	19(2)
C(4')	89(3)	44(2)	64(3)	4(2)	17(2)	-5(2)
C(5')	59(2)	68(3)	54(2)	2(2)	-7(2)	1(2)
C(6')	79(3)	71(3)	57(2)	19(2)	1(2)	18(3)
O(1')	112(3)	66(2)	83(2)	-25(2)	-4(2)	-9(2)
C(7')	77(3)	61(3)	80(3)	-2(2)	24(3)	13(2)
O(2')	135(3)	66(2)	97(3)	9(2)	19(2)	15(2)
C(8')	133(6)	56(3)	92(4)	-6(3)	10(4)	-2(4)

Table 7.15. Hydrogen coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{Å}^2 \times 10^3$) for HAP.

	x	y	z	U(eq)
H(1)	1872(74)	1955(66)	1035(49)	64(16)
H(2)	3771(125)	4024(108)	4107(88)	159(37)
H(3)	4147(74)	1190(57)	4982(50)	74(16)
H(4)	1968(63)	-686(62)	1882(46)	65(18)
H(5)	3221	-2255	3440	52(11)
H(6)	1100	6206	618	246(48)
H(7)	144	4552	736	200(39)
H(8)	1979	4608	229	141(33)
H(1')	3719(59)	7472(51)	9163(43)	28(10)
H(2')	1289(52)	9292(43)	6010(36)	37(11)
H(3')	2397(71)	11922(63)	6667(44)	51(15)
H(4')	4552(52)	9875(47)	9805(41)	34(11)
H(5')	4020	13434	8000	50
H(6')	1218(46)	4877(47)	5840(33)	50
H(7')	1538(69)	6483(55)	5346(40)	50
H(8')	107(51)	6807(52)	5685(32)	50

Table 7.16. Selected torsion angles for HAP.

5.55 (0.66)	C6 - C1 - C2 - C3
178.22 (0.41)	C6 - C1 - C2 - C7
-3.13 (0.57)	C1 - C2 - C3 - C4
-176.26 (0.34)	C7 - C2 - C3 - C4
-0.75 (0.58)	C2 - C3 - C4 - C5
-178.73 (0.40)	C3 - C4 - C5 - O1
2.27 (0.65)	C3 - C4 - C5 - C6
-178.97 (0.41)	O1 - C5 - C6 - C1
-0.10 (0.69)	C4 - C5 - C6 - C1
-3.94 (0.71)	C2 - C1 - C6 - C5
-176.71 (0.49)	C1 - C2 - C7 - O2
-3.75 (0.62)	C3 - C2 - C7 - O2
3.65 (0.60)	C1 - C2 - C7 - C8
176.62 (0.37)	C3 - C2 - C7 - C8
-177.49 (0.49)	C6' - C1' - C2' - C7'
-0.78 (0.71)	C6' - C1' - C2' - C3'
3.39 (0.59)	C1' - C2' - C3' - C4'
-179.85 (0.45)	C7' - C2' - C3' - C4'
-2.42 (0.63)	C2' - C3' - C4' - C5'
-179.16 (0.47)	C3' - C4' - C5' - O1'
-1.14 (0.66)	C3' - C4' - C5' - C6'
-2.86 (0.82)	C2' - C1' - C6' - C5'
-178.17 (0.49)	O1' - C5' - C6' - C1'
3.87 (0.73)	C4' - C5' - C6' - C1'
-1.32 (0.67)	C1' - C2' - C7' - O2'
-177.85 (0.42)	C3' - C2' - C7' - O2'
-179.71 (0.52)	C1' - C2' - C7' - C8'
3.76 (0.70)	C3' - C2' - C7' - C8'

Table 7.17. Least-squares planes (x,y,z in crystal coordinates) and deviations from them (* indicates atom used to define plane)

$$1.072 (0.005) x + 0.348 (0.007) y - 5.276 (0.014) z = 0.578 (0.007)$$

*	0.000	(0.004)	C1
*	-0.054	(0.004)	C2
*	-0.010	(0.003)	C3
*	-0.026	(0.004)	C4
*	0.001	(0.004)	C5
*	-0.011	(0.004)	C6
*	-0.002	(0.004)	C7
*	0.031	(0.003)	C8
*	0.006	(0.003)	O2
*	0.013	(0.003)	O1

Rms deviation of fitted atoms = 0.022

$$-7.083 (0.006) x - 0.360 (0.008) y - 5.237 (0.018) z = 2.416 (0.015)$$

Angle between two planes (with approximate esd) = 4.89 (0.16)

*	-0.006	(0.004)	C1'
*	-0.016	(0.004)	C2'
*	0.028	(0.004)	C3'
*	0.005	(0.004)	C4'
*	-0.010	(0.004)	C5'
*	0.024	(0.004)	C6'
*	0.003	(0.004)	C7'
*	-0.014	(0.005)	C8'
*	0.004	(0.004)	O2'
*	-0.016	(0.004)	O1'

Rms deviation of fitted atoms = 0.015

Table 7.18 : Hydrogen bond distances in HAP.

15	0.00	0.3221	-0.2255	0.3440	1.000	1.8	0 01	0.992
							3 02	1.738 172.9
3 02	0.2504	-0.3962	0.2647	1.9	0.0000+X	-1.0000+Y	0.0000+Z	
15'	0.00	0.4020	1.3434	0.8000	1.000	2.4	0 01'	1.150
							4 02'	1.881 115.0 43.4
4 02'	0.2616	1.5287	0.7794	3.0	0.0000+X	1.0000+Y	0.0000+Z	

ORTEP DIAGRAM OF HAP

ECULE

ORTEP DIAGRAM OF HAP MOLECULE A

Figure 7.5 (a) : ORTEP diagram for HAP.

ORTEP DIAGRAM OF HAP MOLECULE B

(iii) Single crystal structure

Experimental :-

The crystals chosen for study are single crystals having three dimensional intensity data collected on an Enraf CAD-4 diffractometer with a scan rate of 2.51 degrees using Moka tube (10.7 + 2.10 sin² θ)° and the data were corrected by absorption corrections. Reflections -14 ≤ h ≤ 14, -16 ≤ k ≤ 13, -10 ≤ l ≤ 10 of 3614 reflections with 200 significant reflections were observed and discussed.

The unit cell dimensions are a = 0.357 nm, b = 0.357 nm, c = 0.357 nm. The structure solution was carried out by direct method using the program SHELX 86 [2]. The structure was refined by full matrix least squares method using the program SHELX 86 [2]. The structure was refined by full matrix least squares method using the program SHELX 86 [2].

PACKING DIAGRAM OF HAP

Figure 7.6 : Packing of the HAP molecules in the unit cell along with the hydrogen bonding.

(iii) Single crystal structure of PHB

(a) Experimental :-

The crystals chosen for data collection were small pieces of pure single crystals having dimensions as 0.28 X 0.22 X 0.10 mm. Three dimensional intensity data were collected on an ENRAF CAD - 4 diffractometer with $\omega/2\theta$ scan mode of 2.31 to 14.94 degrees using MoK α ($\lambda = 0.71069 \text{ \AA}$) radiation with scan angle $(0.7 + 2.10 \tan \theta)^\circ$ and scan width of $(0.35 + 1.05 \tan \theta)^\circ$. The data were corrected by applying Lorentz, polarization and absorption corrections. Reflections in the hemisphere with index ranges $-14 \leq h \leq 14$, $-16 \leq k \leq 0$, $0 \leq l \leq 13$ were measured. A total of 3614 reflections were measured of which 1997 were unique and 2105 significant reflections observed with $I \geq 3 \sigma(I)$.

(b) Observations and discussions :

The unit cell dimensions were obtained from least square fit of 25 well centred reflections having $(9^\circ \leq \theta \leq 14^\circ)$. Two standard reflections (4 3 -2 ; 3 6 -1) are monitored every 3600 secs. of exposure time showed no significant variation in intensity. The maximum time spent on any measurement is 60 secs and the background count was half the scan time.

The structure solution was carried out by direct methods, using the program SHELX 86 [23] and refined using full matrix least squares method on I using SHELXL 93. All the non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. All the hydrogen atoms could be located from different electronic

density maps and were refined with isotropic thermal parameters. The convergence was achieved at final $R_1 = 0.0357$, $wR_2 = 0.0970$ with individual weighting scheme based on counting statistics.

$$w = 1 / [\sigma^2 (f_o)^2 + (0.0612 \times P)^2 + 0.39 \times P]$$

$$P = (f_o^2 + 2f_c^2) / 3$$

$S = 1.064$ for 332 parameters. The maximum and minimum electron density in the final difference electron density map are 0.168 and $-0.105 \text{ e}/\text{Å}^3$.

The results on unit cell parameters and estimated standard deviations for PHB are tabulated in table 7.34. The observed and calculated structure factors of PHB are listed in appendix II, along with corresponding hkl values.

The atomic coordinates and their equivalent isotropic displacement parameters for all non-hydrogen atoms are listed in table 7.35. Table 7.36 contains the bond lengths and bond angles of all the atoms of PHB. The positional and anisotropic thermal parameters for the non-hydrogen atoms are given in table 7.37. The hydrogen coordinates and isotropic displacement parameters are depicted in the table 7.38. Some selected torsion angles for non-hydrogen atoms are listed in table 7.39.

The ORTEP diagrams of both the molecules along with the numbering scheme are depicted in figure 7.7 (a) and 7.7 (b). The thermal ellipsoids are at 50 % probability level. The packing of the molecules in the unit cell along with the hydrogen bonding is shown in the figure 7.8. The least square planes passing through

Table 7.34 : Unit cell parameters and standard deviations for PNB.

Specifications	Parameters
Empirical formula	$C_{10}H_{12}O_3$
Formula weight	180.20
Temperature	300 K
Wavelength	0.71069 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/C$
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 12.0782(9) \text{ Å}; \alpha = 90^\circ$ $b = 13.8440(7) \text{ Å}; \beta = 108.53^\circ$ $c = 11.8025(3) \text{ Å}; \gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume	1871.2(2) Å ³
Z	8
Density (calculated)	1.279 Mg /m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.094 mm ⁻¹
F (000)	768
Crystal size	0.28 X 0.22 X 0.10 mm
Theta range for data collection	2.31 to 24.94 deg.
Index ranges	$-14 \leq h \leq 14; -16 \leq k \leq 0; 0 \leq l \leq 13$
Reflections collected	2103
Independent reflections	1997 [R (int) = 0.0145]
Refinement method	Full-matrix-block least-squares on F ²
Data / restraints / parameters	1997 / 0 / 332
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.064
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	$R_1 = 0.0357, wR_2 = 0.0970$
Extinction coefficient	0.0018(6)
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.168 and -0.105 e.Å ⁻³

Table 7.35. Atomic coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and equivalent isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for PHB. $U(\text{eq})$ is defined as one third of the trace of the orthogonalized U_{ij} tensor.

	x	y	z	$U(\text{eq})$
0(1)	5715(2)	8852(1)	2202(2)	79(1)
0(2)	5896(1)	4263(1)	1689(2)	64(1)
0(3)	6867(1)	4815(1)	503(1)	55(1)
0(1)	6122(2)	5966(1)	1511(2)	43(1)
0(2)	6507(2)	6695(2)	921(2)	55(1)
0(3)	6367(2)	7646(2)	1158(2)	65(1)
0(4)	5837(2)	7899(2)	2005(2)	54(1)
0(5)	5450(2)	7183(2)	2603(2)	52(1)
0(6)	5591(2)	6224(2)	2355(2)	49(1)
0(7)	6266(2)	4937(1)	1260(2)	45(1)
0(8)	7091(2)	3831(2)	211(2)	52(1)
0(9)	7674(3)	3888(2)	-727(3)	59(1)
0(10)	7955(3)	2888(2)	-1102(3)	70(1)
0(1')	9741(2)	-4730(1)	-1760(2)	71(1)
0(2')	9064(1)	-153(1)	-1705(2)	66(1)
0(3')	8203(1)	-695(1)	-425(1)	54(1)
0(1')	9040(2)	-1849(1)	-1345(2)	44(1)
0(2')	9574(2)	-2115(2)	-2178(2)	52(1)
0(3')	9812(2)	-3073(2)	-2339(2)	52(1)
0(4')	9517(2)	-3778(1)	-1655(2)	50(1)
0(5')	8982(2)	-3523(2)	-822(2)	60(1)
0(6')	8741(2)	-2569(1)	-676(2)	51(1)
0(7')	8787(2)	-823(1)	-1196(2)	46(1)
0(8')	7873(2)	287(2)	-238(2)	57(1)
0(9')	7091(3)	231(2)	521(3)	72(1)
0(10')	6662(4)	1205(2)	747(4)	90(1)
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0(97)				
0(98)				
0(99)				
0(100)				

Table 7.36. Bond lengths [Å] and angles [deg] for PHB.

C(4)-O(1)-H(5)	113(2)	5(3)
C(7)-O(3)-C(8)	117.5(2)	(3)
C(2)-C(1)-C(6)	118.5(2)	3(2)
C(2)-C(1)-C(7)	121.4(2)	8(2)
C(6)-C(1)-C(7)	120.1(2)	1(2)
C(3)-C(2)-C(1)	121.0(2)	8(3)
C(3)-C(2)-H(3)	121.6(13)	1(3)
C(1)-C(2)-H(3)	117.4(13)	8(3)
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	120.2(2)	8(3)
C(2)-C(3)-H(4)	123(2)	(2)
C(4)-C(3)-H(4)	117(2)	2(3)
O(1)-C(4)-C(5)	122.5(2)	(3)
O(1)-C(4)-C(3)	117.8(2)	1(3)
C(5)-C(4)-C(3)	119.7(2)	2(3)
C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	119.7(2)	(2)
C(4)-C(5)-H(1)	119.8(12)	(2)
C(6)-C(5)-H(1)	120.4(12)	2(3)
C(5)-C(6)-C(1)	120.9(2)	(2)
C(5)-C(6)-H(2)	119.5(14)	(2)
C(1)-C(6)-H(2)	119.6(14)	(2)
O(2)-C(7)-O(3)	122.4(2)	5(3)
O(2)-C(7)-C(1)	125.1(2)	(2)
O(3)-C(7)-C(1)	112.4(2)	5(3)
O(3)-C(8)-C(9)	107.1(2)	4(3)
O(3)-C(8)-H(6)	107.8(12)	(3)
C(9)-C(8)-H(6)	114.3(13)	(3)
O(3)-C(8)-H(7)	107.3(12)	9(2)
C(9)-C(8)-H(7)	109.9(12)	(4)
H(6)-C(8)-H(7)	110(2)	59(2)
C(8)-C(9)-C(10)	111.6(2)	27(2)
C(8)-C(9)-H(8)	110.0(13)	3(2)
C(10)-C(9)-H(8)	110.0(13)	6(3)
C(8)-C(9)-H(9)	110(2)	89(3)
C(10)-C(9)-H(9)	108(2)	76(3)
H(8)-C(9)-H(9)	108(2)	84(3)
C(9)-C(10)-H(10)	110(2)	5(2)
C(9)-C(10)-H(11)	109(2)	84(3)
H(10)-C(10)-H(11)	110(2)	5(2)
C(9)-C(10)-H(12)	111(2)	82(3)
H(10)-C(10)-H(12)	107(2)	76(3)
H(11)-C(10)-H(12)	110(2)	(4)
C(4')-O(1')-H(5')	113(2)	4(3)
C(7')-O(3')-C(8')	117.4(2)	7(2)
C(2')-C(1')-C(6')	118.5(2)	96(3)
C(2')-C(1')-C(7')	120.1(2)	0(3)
C(6')-C(1')-C(7')	121.4(2)	3(2)
C(3')-C(2')-C(1')	121.0(2)	99(4)
C(3')-C(2')-H(3')	118.4(14)	(3)
C(1')-C(2')-H(3')	120.5(14)	(3)
C(2')-C(3')-C(4')	119.5(2)	7(4)
C(2')-C(3')-H(4')	119.9(12)	(4)
C(4')-C(3')-H(4')	120.5(12)	(4)
O(1')-C(4')-C(5')	117.6(2)	
O(1')-C(4')-C(3')	122.4(2)	
C(5')-C(4')-C(3')	120.0(2)	
C(6')-C(5')-C(4')	120.0(2)	
C(6')-C(5')-H(1')	122(2)	
C(4')-C(5')-H(1')	118(2)	

Table 1.3c Bond lengths [Å] and angles [deg] for pphb

C(5')-C(6')-C(1')	2	(2)
O(1)-C(4)-H(2')	1	1.356(3)
O(1)-H(5)-H(2')	1	0.93(3)
O(2)-C(7)-O(3')	2	1.213(2)
O(3)-C(7)-C(1')	2	1.328(2)
O(3)-C(8)-C(1')	1	1.451(2)
C(1)-C(2)-C(9')	0	1.388(3)
C(1)-C(6)-H(6')	0	1.391(3)
C(1)-C(7)-H(6')	1	1.478(3)
C(2)-C(3)-H(7')	0	1.368(3)
C(2)-H(3)-H(7')	1	1.01(2)
C(3)-C(4)-H(7')	1	1.392(3)
C(3)-H(4)-C(10')	1	0.94(3)
C(4)-C(5)-H(8')	0	1.381(3)
C(5)-C(6)-H(8')	0	1.382(3)
C(5)-H(1)-H(9')	13	0.95(2)
C(6)-H(2)-H(9')	9	0.96(2)
C(8)-C(9)-H(9')	13	1.492(3)
C(8)-H(6)-H(10')	11	0.98(2)
C(8)-H(7)-H(11')	13	1.04(2)
C(9)-C(10)-H(11')	13	1.525(3)
C(9)-H(8)-H(12')	10	0.99(2)
C(9)-H(9)-H(12')	10	0.95(3)
C(10)-H(10)-H(12')	10	1.04(3)
C(10)-H(11)		1.00(3)
C(10)-H(12)		0.97(3)
O(1')-C(4')		1.359(2)
O(1')-H(5')		0.97(4)
O(2')-C(7')		1.209(2)
O(3')-C(7')		1.327(2)
O(3')-C(8')		1.453(2)
C(1')-C(2')		1.386(3)
C(1')-C(6')		1.389(3)
C(1')-C(7')		1.476(3)
C(2')-C(3')		1.384(3)
C(2')-H(3')		0.95(2)
C(3')-C(4')		1.384(3)
C(3')-H(4')		0.95(2)
C(4')-C(5')		1.382(3)
C(5')-C(6')		1.376(3)
C(5')-H(1')		0.94(3)
C(6')-H(2')		0.97(2)
C(8')-C(9')		1.496(3)
C(8')-H(6')		1.00(3)
C(8')-H(7')		1.03(2)
C(9')-C(10')		1.499(4)
C(9')-H(8')		0.95(3)
C(9')-H(9')		1.06(3)
C(10')-H(10')		1.07(4)
C(10')-H(11')		1.03(4)
C(10')-H(12')		1.15(4)

a 7.37 Anisotropic displacement parameters ($A^2 \times 10^3$) for PHB.
 The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form:
 $-2 \pi^2 [h^2 a^*^2 U_{11} + \dots + 2 h k a^* b^* U_{12}]$

U11	U22	U33	U23	U13	U12
106(1)	42(1)	116(2)	-6(1)	76(1)	3(1)
83(1)	44(1)	81(1)	3(1)	49(1)	-7(1)
70(1)	36(1)	71(1)	0(1)	42(1)	2(1)
43(1)	42(1)	49(1)	3(1)	19(1)	2(1)
67(2)	42(1)	73(2)	3(1)	45(1)	4(1)
81(2)	41(1)	95(2)	7(1)	59(2)	1(1)
57(1)	41(1)	73(2)	-5(1)	33(1)	2(1)
59(1)	51(1)	57(1)	-4(1)	33(1)	1(1)
56(1)	47(1)	51(1)	2(1)	27(1)	-1(1)
45(1)	44(1)	50(1)	2(1)	21(1)	-1(1)
59(1)	36(1)	67(2)	0(1)	29(1)	4(1)
69(2)	43(1)	74(2)	2(1)	38(2)	5(1)
83(2)	54(2)	88(2)	-7(2)	48(2)	11(2)
104(1)	36(1)	96(1)	-4(1)	65(1)	4(1)
85(1)	41(1)	90(1)	12(1)	56(1)	2(1)
71(1)	35(1)	69(1)	0(1)	41(1)	5(1)
48(1)	39(1)	51(1)	0(1)	23(1)	1(1)
64(1)	43(1)	60(1)	5(1)	37(1)	3(1)
63(1)	49(1)	58(1)	-1(1)	37(1)	3(1)
60(1)	36(1)	62(1)	-4(1)	31(1)	1(1)
80(2)	40(1)	76(2)	3(1)	49(1)	-1(1)
65(1)	42(1)	62(1)	-3(1)	41(1)	0(1)
48(1)	40(1)	55(1)	1(1)	25(1)	-1(1)
74(2)	38(1)	69(2)	-2(1)	35(1)	6(1)
102(2)	54(2)	77(2)	6(1)	53(2)	15(2)
125(3)	68(2)	102(2)	-1(2)	71(2)	21(2)

Table 7.39. Selected angles for PHB.

Table 7.38. Hydrogen coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and isotropic displacement parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for PHB.

	x	y	z	U(eq)
H(1)	5065(17)	7354(14)	3166(18)	49(6)
H(2)	5316(21)	5729(17)	2769(21)	73(7)
H(3)	6858(20)	6497(16)	290(21)	69(7)
H(4)	6637(22)	8154(18)	785(22)	78(8)
H(5)	5229(28)	8970(22)	2661(28)	110(11)
H(6)	6345(20)	3486(15)	-36(19)	55(6)
H(7)	7654(20)	3523(16)	981(20)	64(7)
H(8)	7172(20)	4244(16)	-1431(21)	64(7)
H(9)	8392(24)	4232(19)	-425(23)	82(9)
H(10)	7187(26)	2503(19)	-1466(25)	95(10)
H(11)	8369(25)	2960(20)	-1711(25)	94(9)
H(12)	8439(29)	2524(24)	-416(30)	116(12)
H(1')	8786(23)	-4019(19)	-380(23)	84(8)
H(2')	8381(19)	-2393(15)	-74(20)	65(7)
H(3')	9800(20)	-1637(17)	-2644(21)	69(7)
H(4')	10182(18)	-3241(14)	-2908(19)	55(6)
H(5')	10168(31)	-4848(24)	-2319(31)	131(12)
H(6')	8604(23)	656(19)	167(23)	84(8)
H(7')	7457(21)	589(17)	-1059(21)	68(7)
H(8')	7534(27)	-45(23)	1263(29)	112(11)
H(9')	6273(31)	-79(25)	37(30)	132(13)
H(10')	6157(35)	1135(29)	1337(36)	159(15)
H(11')	6251(38)	1552(31)	-43(40)	174(18)
H(12')	7486(39)	1649(30)	1209(36)	170(17)

Table 7.39. Selected torsion angles for PHB.

-0.24 (0.35)	C6 - C1 - C2 - C3
179.80 (0.23)	C7 - C1 - C2 - C3
0.36 (0.40)	C1 - C2 - C3 - C4
-179.76 (0.24)	C2 - C3 - C4 - C1
-0.21 (0.39)	C2 - C3 - C4 - C5
179.47 (0.22)	01 - C4 - C5 - C6
-0.06 (0.35)	C3 - C4 - C5 - C6
0.18 (0.34)	C4 - C5 - C6 - C1
-0.03 (0.32)	C2 - C1 - C6 - C5
179.93 (0.20)	C7 - C1 - C6 - C5
-1.04 (0.30)	C8 - C3 - C7 - C2
178.45 (0.19)	C8 - C3 - C7 - C1
-175.69 (0.22)	C2 - C1 - C7 - C2
4.35 (0.32)	C6 - C1 - C7 - C2
4.84 (0.29)	C2 - C1 - C7 - C3
-175.12 (0.19)	C6 - C1 - C7 - C3
174.88 (0.20)	C7 - C3 - C8 - C9
179.83 (0.24)	03 - C8 - C9 - C10
-0.46 (0.33)	C6' - C1' - C2' - C3'
-179.55 (0.21)	C7' - C1' - C2' - C3'
-0.17 (0.35)	C1' - C2' - C3' - C4'
-179.19 (0.22)	C2' - C3' - C4' - C1'
0.31 (0.34)	C2' - C3' - C4' - C5'
179.70 (0.23)	01' - C4' - C5' - C6'
0.18 (0.37)	C3' - C4' - C5' - C6'
-0.83 (0.37)	C4' - C5' - C6' - C1'
0.96 (0.34)	C2' - C1' - C6' - C5'
-179.96 (0.22)	C7' - C1' - C6' - C5'
1.86 (0.31)	C8' - C3' - C7' - C2'
-178.03 (0.20)	C8' - C3' - C7' - C1'
-4.30 (0.33)	C2' - C1' - C7' - C2'
176.63 (0.22)	C6' - C1' - C7' - C2'
175.58 (0.19)	C2' - C1' - C7' - C3'
-3.49 (0.29)	C6' - C1' - C7' - C3'
172.19 (0.23)	C7' - C3' - C8' - C9'
-178.31 (0.29)	03' - C8' - C9' - C10'

-0.010 (0.00)
 0.017 (0.00)
 0.014 (0.00)
 -0.074 (0.00)
 0.028 (0.00)

Table 7.40. Least-squares planes (x,y,z in crystal coordinates) and deviations from them (* indicates atom used to define plane)

$$1.467(0.011) x - 0.114 (0.014) y + 5.351 (0.011) z = 5.924 (0.011)$$

*	0.000	(0.002)	C1
*	0.002	(0.002)	C2
*	-0.002	(0.002)	C3
*	0.000	(0.002)	C4
*	0.001	(0.002)	C5
*	-0.001	(0.002)	C6
*	-0.008	(0.004)	O1
*	-0.001	(0.003)	C7

Rms deviation of fitted atoms = 0.001

$$3.213 (0.017) x + 0.131 (0.028) y + 5.654 (0.019) z = 5.960 (0.023)$$

Angle between two planes (with approximate esd) = 1.95 (0.25)

*	0.001	(0.001)	C1
*	-0.036	(0.002)	C7
*	0.028	(0.002)	O3
*	0.034	(0.002)	C8
*	-0.017	(0.002)	C9
*	-0.011	(0.002)	C10
*	0.106	(0.005)	O2

Rms deviation of fitted atoms = 0.025

$$1.137 (0.009) x - 0.131 (0.005) y + 5.743 (0.008) z = 5.785 (0.007)$$

Angle between two planes (with approximate esd) 1.19 (0.23)

*	0.014	(0.002)	C1
*	-0.049	(0.002)	C2
*	-0.040	(0.002)	C3
*	0.012	(0.002)	C4
*	0.051	(0.002)	C5
*	0.036	(0.002)	C6
*	-0.028	(0.002)	C7
*	0.056	(0.003)	C8
*	-0.010	(0.003)	C9
*	0.017	(0.003)	C10
*	0.014	(0.002)	O1
*	-0.074	(0.002)	O2
*	0.028	(0.002)	O3

Rms deviation of fitted atoms = 0.038

Table 7.41 : Hydrogen bond distances in PHB.

6	0.00	0.5229	0.8970	0.2661	1.000	2.0	0 01	0.932	
							2 02	1.806	170.2
2 02	0.4104	0.9263	0.3311	1.8	1.0000-X		0.5000+Y	0.5000-Z	
6	0.10	1.0168	-0.4848	-0.2319	1.000	2.2	0 01'	0.972	
							6 02'	1.745	175.
6 02'	1.0936	-0.5153	-0.3295	2.8	2.0000-X		-0.5000+Y	-0.5000-Z	

Figure 7.7 (a) : ORTEP Diagram PHB.

Figure 7.7 (a) : ORTEP diagram for PHB.

Figure 7.7 (b) : ORTEP diagram for PHB.

PACKING DIAGRAM OF PHB

Figure 7.8 : Packing of the PHB molecules in the unit cell along with the hydrogen bonding.

References

- [1] Biemann K ; *Mass Spectroscopy, Organic Chemical Applications*, McGraw - Hill, New York (1962)
- [2] Grasselli J G and Ritchey W M ; *CRC Atlas of Spectral Data and Physical Constants for Organic Compounds*, CRC Press Inc. 1975
- [3] Kalsi P S ; in *Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds*, New Age International Publishers, 1994
- [4] Roberts J D ; *Nuclear Magnetic Resonance : Application to Organic Chemistry*, McGraw - Hill, New York (1959)
- [5] Abraham R J and Loftus P ; *Introduction to NMR Spectroscopy*, 2nd ed., Wiley, London (1989)
- [6] Reddy V B and Mehrotra P N ; *Nat. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 2, 11 (1979) 411
- [7] Klevtsov P V and Sinkevich A V ; *Sov. Phy. Crystallogr.*, 25,3 (1980) 360
- [8] Hebbar K C and Mohan Rao P ; *J. Mat. Sci. Lett.*, 10 (1991) 1430
- [9] I'to ; *X-ray studies on Polymorphism*, Maruzen Co. Ltd. Tokyo (1950) 187
- [10] Willard H H and Settle F A ; *Instrumental methods of analysis*, CBS Publishers and Distributors, India (1986) 189
- [11] Longman ; *Vogel's text book of practical organic chemistry*, (1978) vol-ii
- [12] Gilman J J and Johnston W G ; *J Appl. Phys.*, 27 (1956) 1018

- [3] Thyagarajan R and Urusovskaya A A ; *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*,
28 (1907) 1251
- [4] Boranoya G K and Nadgornyi E M ; *Soviet Phys. Cryst.*, 13
STUDIES ON ELECTRICAL AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES
- [5] Yadhava and Padmanabhan ; *Acta Crystall. B*, 29 (1973) 493
- [6] Pedersen B F ; *Acta Crystallogr. B* (Denmark), B28, 3
(1972) 746
- [7] Lin Xianti ; *Jiegou Huaxue*, 2 (1983) 213
- [8] Nan Zang, Duorong Y and Xu Tang ; *J. Crystal Growth*, 123
(1992) 255 ical conductivity
- [9] Liebertz I and Stahr S ; *Z. Krist.* 165 (1983) 91
- [10] National Bureau of standards (U.S), Monograph 25, 3,
(1964) 53
- [11] Wolfson M M ; *Introduction to X-ray Crystallography*,
Cambridge University Press, (1970)
- [12] Iwasaki F ; *Acta Cryst. Sect B*, 33 (1977) 1646
- [13] Sheldrick G M ; *Program for the solution of the crystal
reference*
structure, University of Gottingen, Germany 1986

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Introduction

Insulators are characterized by large energy gap (about 5 eV above). Schottky defects (due to anion or cation), Frenkel defects (due to impurities), colour centers etc are different factors which are responsible for conductivity in such materials, explained by several investigators [1 - 7]. Due to the pairing of various defects, the lattice is electrically neutral at room temperature. Also some carriers are observed as trapped at defect sites, which account for the very low conductivity of ionic materials at room temperature. Similarly, heat energy to the lattice serves to thermally generate the charge carriers because of the breaking of the temporary bonds, thus enhancing conduction.

The electrical conductivity of nonlinear crystals required for nonlinear device applications must be low. It is found that high ionic or electrical conductivity of organic crystals can be very harmful for a variety of electro-optic devices. A waveguide device material may not be stable during device processing or under applied electric field if it possesses higher conductivity [1].

Similarly, a good insight into the electrical field distribution within crystalline materials can be gained by an investigation of their dielectric properties. Through a study of the dielectric constant as a function of frequency, dc bias,

temperature etc, the different polarization mechanisms in solids such as atomic polarization of lattice, orientation polarization of dipoles, space-charge polarization, electronic and ionic polarizations can be understood very easily. The study of dielectric properties also helps in understanding the defect concentration of crystalline materials. Considerable amount of work along these lines have been carried out on a variety of alkali halides [9-13], alkali earth halides [14] yielding valuable information. The dielectric behaviour of hydrated solids is due to orientation of permanent dipole moments of water molecules existing in the lattice [15-18]. The removal of these water molecules of crystallization at elevated temperatures and their subsequent dissociation into H^+ and OH^- ions results in larger polarization, thus influencing the value of dielectric constant of the material at the dehydration temperature.

The dielectric property of nonlinear materials is very important feature of their behaviour in various device applications. The low dielectric constant of organic materials has important applications for electro-optic devices in which a low frequency ac field is used to modulate the refractive index [19]. The small dielectric constant yields a small RC time constant, thus permitting a large operating band width (> 10 GHz) modulation. Further more, for organic materials the dielectric constants at low frequency are comparable to those at optical frequency, which leads to minimization of phase mismatch between electrical and optical pulses in high speed travelling wave devices [20].

The general theory of magnetism states that when a substance is placed in a magnetic field, the magnetic moment is induced in the external field direction for para and ferromagnetic materials. Thus the mass susceptibility χ is positive and is of the order of 10^{-2} for ferromagnetic and 10^{-2} to 10^{-6} for paramagnetic materials. In case of diamagnetic materials, the induced moment is antiparallel to the external field direction. Hence χ is negative and is of the order of 10^{-6} CGS units.

In the present investigation, a detailed study on electrical conductivity and dielectric properties of silica doped NaF, and electrical conductivity, dielectric properties along different directions and magnetic susceptibilities of nonlinear organic crystals including AOM and AT are carried out.

8.2 DC electrical conductivity

There are two commonly used methods by which the dc electrical conductivity of a solid is measured. They are (1) two probe method and (2) four probe method. The two probe method is commonly used for electrical conductivity measurement in case of insulators. It gives errors in case of conductors and semiconductors and thus four probe method is commonly employed for the purpose. In this investigation, two probe method is used for measurement.

(i) Specimen preparation :-

Good crystals of silica doped NaF grown by gel technique are selected to prepare pallets of 1 cm diameter and certain

thickness. A pressure of 8 tons is applied to prepare pallets using universal testing machine press and a suitable die. Silver paste is applied on both the surfaces to ensure perfect electrical contact. In case of nonlinear crystals, the crystallographic directions are determined by means of polarizing microscope and the crystals are cut along different directions using a solvent saw. The silver paste is applied on both faces of x, y, z-cut crystals.

(ii) Experimental technique :-

The conductivity cell [21] consists of two copper electrodes (figure 8.1), one of size 2 cm X 4 cm and thickness 0.4 cms and other a circular plate of diameter 1.5 cms and thickness 0.4 cms. Perfect insulation between the two electrodes is ensured by means of fibre glass insulation. The opposite faces of electrodes are made mechanically flat and highly polished. Proper arrangements are made for good electrical contact between the sample and the electrodes. A heating coil is wound over a copper tube of length 20 cms with thin mica sheets placed in between. The terminals of the heating coil are connected to an ac source. The temperature of the cell is measured directly by means of chromel - alumel thermocouple connected to digital temperature measurement meter.

The electrical connections are made as shown in figure 8.2. The conductance (current I) of the sample is measured by Keithley current meter at different temperature range with an accuracy of measurement about $\pm 1\%$ by applying constant potential difference ($V = 30$ Volts) across the electrodes.

- | | |
|---------------------------|------------------------|
| 1,2-COPPER ELECTRODES | 7-RESISTANCE COIL |
| 3-SAMPLE | 8-WHITE CEMENT PACKING |
| 4-SPRING | 9-WOODEN BOX |
| 5-INSULATED NUT AND SCREW | 10-THERMO COUPLE |
| 6-COPPER TUBE | 11-TOP COVER |

Fig. 8.1 : Conductivity cell with resistance furnace

Fig. 8.2 : Electrical connections of the conductivity cell

Hence the value of conductivity is computed using the relation

$$\text{Conductivity } \sigma = (I d) / (A V)$$

where A is the area of the pallet, d is the thickness, V is the applied potential difference and I is the measured current flow.

(iii) Observations and discussion :-

The measured values of dc electrical conductivity of silica doped NaF grown in acetic acid medium and same crystal grown in formic acid medium is compared with pure NaF crystal and is given in table 8.1. The dc electrical conductivity of AOM and AT crystals at different temperatures are also given in table 8.1. The dc conductivity of all grown organic crystals along z-axis is measured at different temperatures till their melting point and is tabulated in table 8.2. In all these crystals the variation of electrical conductivity with temperature is plotted in figures 8.3 and 8.4.

The electrical conductivity of insulating crystals [21] with different impurity ions have been studied. When pure crystals of CuI is doped with different amounts of SrCl_2 , it has been observed that the induced conductivity increases in proportion to the concentration of the divalent metal Sr^{2+} [11]. On the other hand, Takahashi et al [22] and Bright-well et al [23] have found a decrease in the conductivity value of AgI due to the addition of CuI .

Table 8.1 : DC electrical conductivity of grown crystals.

Temperature (°C)	dc conductivity (S/cm)				
	NaF (pure)	silica NaF (acetic)	silica NaF (formic)	AOM	AT
30	8.32 E-6	1.72 E-7	7.91 E-7	7.30 E-8	2.76 E-9
60	9.68 E-6	3.86 E-7	9.10 E-7	9.05 E-9	9.37E-10
90	2.71 E-5	5.69 E-7	9.99 E-7	2.61 E-9	5.02E-10
120	2.05 E-5	8.21 E-7	2.17 E-6	3.17E-10	2.91E-10
140	3.89 E-5	9.78 E-7	3.89 E-6	1.02E-10	--
160	4.65 E-5	2.03 E-6	6.63 E-6	--	--

Table 8.2 : DC electrical conductivity of grown crystals.

Temperature (°C)	dc conductivity (S/cm)			
	HAP	MHB	MHBA	PHB
30	2.25 E-11	2.22 E-11	2.9 E-9	4.83 E-12
60	2.37 E-11	2.77 E-11	3.5 E-10	8.05 E-12
90	6.00 E-11	4.71 E-10	---	4.94 E-10
120	---	1.19 E-9	---	6.72 E-10

Table 8.3 : Plot of dc electrical conductivity vs temperature.

Figure 8.3 : Plot of dc electrical conductivity with temperature.

Figure 8.4 : Plot of dc electrical conductivity with temperature.

8.3 Dielectric property and ac electrical conductivity

(i) Experimental :-

The capacitance, dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$) and ac conductivity of these crystals were measured as a function of frequency and temperature, at a signal strength of $0.5 V_{rms}$, using a Hewlett Packard Model 4194 A Impedance / gain - phase analyzer in conjunction with a self designed temperature variable furnace. The furnace assembly is shown schematically in figure 8.5. The lanthal winding was made uniformly with a constant pitch on a quartz tube (dia : 40 mm) to achieve uniform temperature zone at the centre of the furnace. The furnace was given enough thermal insulation using ceramic wool and fire brick to minimize thermal conduction and heat loss. The bottom of the furnace was closed with a fine brick and its top was covered with a pyrophyllite disk with a provision to insert the sample and the thermocouple. The thermocouple was kept close to the sample and the temperature was monitored using a digital thermometer. The stray capacitance introduced due to the leads etc. was nullified by calibrating the LCR meter before starting the measurements. The samples are heated uniformly at the rate of $1^\circ K / \text{min}$.

The dielectric constant ϵ_r is calculated from the measured capacitance C using the relation

$$\epsilon_r = (C_p d) / (\epsilon_0 A)$$

where d is the thickness and A the area of cross-section of the sample surface. The ac conductivity is calculated using the

- (1). Quartz tube, (2). Kanthal winding, (3). Metal casing, (4). Ceramic insulation, (5). Fire brick, (6). Stainless steel tube, (7). Sample, (8). Chromel-Alumel thermocouple, (9). Copper leads, (10). Pyrophyllite disk.

Figure 8.5: Schematic diagram of furnace used for dielectric measurements.

relation case of AOM, AT and AT along all the three axes.

It is found to be almost identical with the case in AT.

$$\sigma_{ac} = 2\pi f \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r \tan \delta$$

In case of organic crystals the dielectric constant, dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$) and ac conductivity measurements at different frequencies from 100 KHz to 10 MHz and is carried out over a temperature till their melting point.

variation with frequency.

(ii) Results and discussion :-

variation in its value with frequency.

The dielectric constant, dielectric loss and ac electrical conductivity of pure NaF, silica doped NaF grown in acetic acid medium and silica doped NaF grown in formic acid medium are given

In case of AT also, the dielectric constant is given

in tables 8.3 and 8.4. It is observed that as silica content

increases, the dielectric constant of the crystal increases. In

all cases, the dielectric constant decreased slowly with increase

in input frequency. On the other hand the ac conductivity of

these crystals increased with increase in silica content.

Furthermore, in all cases, the ac conductivity increased with

increase in input frequency. In all three cases, the dielectric

loss found to be decreased with increase in input frequency. This

shows the crystals are insulators and the losses are only due to

electrical conduction [24].

It is also observed that the dielectric constant of

The frequency response of dielectric constant, dielectric

loss and ac conductivity of AOM and AT along all the three axes

at room temperature (25°C) are given in tables 8.4 to 8.7.

In case of AOM, the x and y axis dielectric constants are found to be almost constant with increase in frequency and the z-axis dielectric constant shows some variations. In all cases, it is found that the dielectric constants decrease with increase in frequency. The ac conductivity is observed to be different along different axes and are increased with increase in frequency. The dielectric loss along x-axis has not shown any steady variation with frequency. Instead of that it has shown fluctuation in its value with increase in frequency. The dielectric loss along y & z axis decreased continuously with increase in input frequency.

In case of AT also, the dielectric constants are found to decrease with increase in frequency. The ac conductivity increases along all the three axes. But the dielectric loss has shown a steady decrease with increase in applied frequency as compared to AOM.

The frequency response of dielectric constant, dielectric loss and ac conductivity of grown organic crystals viz. HAP, MHB, MHA and PHB along all the three axes are tabulated in tables 8.7 to 8.12. The dielectric constant and ac conductivity of all the crystals except PHB is found to be different among different axes. It is also observed that the dielectric constants of all the crystals are almost constant with increase in applied input frequency. This is the most important required result in case of any nonlinear crystals [25].

Table 8.3 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	Pure NaF			Silica - NaF (acetic)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$	σ_{ac}
10 K	4.69	0.21	1.17 E-7	14.39	0.7493	6.00 E-6
50 K	4.37	0.029	3.52 E-7	10.57	0.3855	1.13 E-5
100 K	4.31	0.017	4.07 E-7	9.72	0.2979	1.61 E-5
500 K	4.29	0.007	8.73 E-7	8.29	0.1592	3.67 E-5
1 M	4.25	0.004	6.41 E-7	7.88	0.1249	5.47 E-5
5 M	4.21	0.0027	3.16 E-6	7.29	0.0638	1.29 E-4
10 M	4.16	0.0019	4.39 E-6	7.18	0.0439	1.75 E-4

Table 8.4 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	Silica - NaF (formic)			AOM (x-axis)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	4.84	0.077	2.08 E-7	5.762	1.36	4.35 E-9
50 K	4.70	0.024	3.14 E-7	5.420	4.79	7.23 E-8
100 K	4.69	0.016	4.17 E-7	5.396	5.06	1.52 E-7
500 K	4.66	0.007	8.55 E-7	5.374	8.27	1.24 E-6
1 M	4.62	0.005	1.31 E-6	5.377	9.40	2.82 E-6
5 M	4.59	0.0043	5.49 E-6	5.348	10.31	1.53 E-5
10 M	4.58	0.0032	8.11 E-6	5.375	18.168	5.43 E-5

Table 8.5 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	ADM (y-axis)			ADM (z-axis)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	5.824	61.52	1.99 E-7	6.713	310.03	1.16 E-7
50 K	5.607	37.48	5.85 E-7	5.567	13.55	2.10 E-7
100 K	5.593	11.18	3.48 E-7	5.478	11.786	3.59 E-7
500 K	5.586	9.329	1.45 E-6	4.396	9.233	1.12 E-6
1 M	5.607	7.716	2.41 E-6	4.381	7.998	1.95 E-6
5 M	5.552	2.481	3.83 E-6	4.359	7.694	9.29 E-6
10 M	5.574	1.972	6.11 E-6	4.394	8.030	1.96 E-5

Table 8.6 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	AT (x-axis)			AT (y-axis)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	7.23	38.97	1.56 E-7	5.92	164.37	5.41 E-7
50 K	6.79	26.03	4.92 E-7	6.37	108.91	1.93 E-6
100 K	6.64	19.15	7.07 E-7	6.41	87.06	3.10 E-6
500 K	6.62	8.40	1.55 E-6	6.38	41.98	7.45 E-6
1 M	6.61	5.17	1.90 E-6	6.32	23.29	8.19 E-6
5 M	6.62	2.38	4.38 E-6	6.30	9.07	1.59 E-5
10 M	6.59	1.70	6.23 E-6	6.29	5.20	1.83 E-5

Table 8.7 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	AT (z-axis)			HAP (x-axis)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	10.71	206.59	1.23 E-6	1.19	372.56	2.46 E-7
50 K	9.93	115.23	3.18 E-6	2.91	35.54	2.87 E-7
100 K	9.47	76.71	4.41 E-6	2.95	33.19	5.45 E-7
500 K	9.41	31.28	8.18 E-6	2.83	36.63	2.88 E-6
1 M	9.35	18.04	9.38 E-6	2.78	33.56	5.19 E-6
5 M	9.32	5.73	1.48 E-5	2.69	21.82	1.63 E-5
10 M	9.17	2.64	1.34 E-5	2.68	17.17	2.56 E-5

Table 8.8 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	HAP (y-axis)			HAP (z-axis)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	3.17	182.30	3.22 E-7	5.30	109.31	3.22 E-7
50 K	4.32	124.47	1.49 E-6	5.29	79.87	1.17 E-6
100 K	4.34	98.20	2.37 E-6	5.29	52.73	1.55 E-6
500 K	4.37	75.91	9.23 E-6	5.28	23.10	3.39 E-6
1 M	4.38	62.38	1.52 E-5	5.27	12.19	3.57 E-6
5 M	4.41	32.60	3.99 E-5	5.25	4.38	6.39 E-6
10 M	4.44	19.73	4.87 E-5	5.21	2.45	7.10 E-6

Table 8.9 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	MHB (x-axis)			MHB (y-axis)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	2.16	76.58	9.17 E-8	3.99	16.07	3.56 E-8
50 K	3.74	11.24	1.17 E-7	4.36	12.23	1.48 E-7
100 K	3.66	18.19	3.70 E-7	4.34	7.02	1.69 E-7
500 K	3.61	8.22	8.23 E-7	4.29	2.42	2.88 E-7
1 M	3.60	6.92	1.39 E-6	4.28	1.82	4.33 E-7
5 M	3.58	4.02	4.00 E-6	4.30	1.46	1.75 E-6
10 M	3.61	2.04	4.09 E-6	4.33	1.32	3.18 E-6

Table 8.10 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	MHB (z-axis)			MHBA (x-axis)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	6.16	20.73	7.10 E-8	4.80	2.24	5.98 E-9
50 K	6.30	8.173	1.43 E-7	5.39	3.78	5.67 E-8
100 K	6.26	6.977	2.43 E-7	5.36	4.82	1.43 E-7
500 K	6.23	3.048	5.28 E-7	5.30	4.59	6.76 E-7
1 M	6.23	2.214	7.67 E-7	5.31	4.76	1.41 E-6
5 M	6.32	1.980	3.41 E-6	5.28	2.04	4.94 E-6
10 M	6.34	1.94	6.84 E-6	5.30	2.04	6.02 E-6

Table 8.11 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	MHBA (y-axis)			MHBA (z-axis)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	6.81	46.21	1.75 E-7	3.17	3.79	6.68 E-9
50 K	7.27	38.03	7.67 E-7	4.32	10.27	1.23 E-7
100 K	7.29	20.78	8.42 E-7	5.31	11.48	3.39 E-7
500 K	7.34	18.31	3.74 E-6	5.33	12.37	1.84 E-6
1 M	7.41	14.67	6.04 E-6	5.38	13.52	4.05 E-6
5 M	7.67	9.36	1.99 E-5	5.57	29.34	4.55 E-5
10 M	7.42	7.19	2.97 E-5	5.82	79.57	2.58 E-4

Table 8.12 : Frequency response of dielectric properties.

Frequency (Hz)	PHB		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
10 K	2.03	350.95	3.95 E-7
50 K	2.74	10.08	7.67 E-8
100 K	2.87	4.29	6.85 E-8
500 K	2.86	2.15	1.71 E-7
1 M	2.86	1.96	3.12 E-7
5 M	2.86	1.67	1.33 E-6
10 M	2.85	1.05	1.67 E-6

Table 8.13 : Temperature response of dielectric properties of HAP

Temp. (°C)	100 K Hz			1 M Hz		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
30	5.31	37.17	1.09 E-6	5.30	50.43	1.48 E-5
50	5.37	32.80	9.79 E-7	5.32	41.07	1.21 E-5
70	5.40	12.96	3.89 E-7	5.36	34.89	1.04 E-5
90	5.41	8.60	2.59 E-7	5.41	28.20	8.48 E-6
110	5.45	52.71	1.59 E-6	5.46	47.76	1.45 E-5

Table 8.14 : Temperature response of dielectric properties of MHB

Temp. (°C)	100 K Hz			1 M Hz		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
30	6.30	15.69	5.49 E-7	6.31	11.32	3.97 E-6
50	6.36	15.46	5.46 E-7	6.34	13.81	4.87 E-6
70	6.38	7.63	2.70 E-7	6.36	12.71	9.58 E-7
90	6.42	5.75	2.05 E-7	6.38	22.05	7.83 E-6
110	6.38	3.96	1.40 E-7	6.43	18.58	6.65 E-6

Table 8.15 : Temperature response of dielectric properties of MHBA

Temp. (°C)	100 K Hz			1 M Hz		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
30	5.31	11.48	3.39 E-7	5.38	13.52	4.05 E-6
40	5.24	4.74	1.38 E-7	5.29	8.89	2.62 E-6
50	5.25	6.99	2.04 E-7	5.32	12.50	3.69 E-6
60	5.38	0.683	2.04 E-8	5.40	8.47	2.54 E-6
70	6.54	53.3	1.94 E-6	6.38	9.88	3.51 E-6

Table 8.16 : Temp. response of dielectric properties of HAP & MHB

Temp. (°C)	10 M Hz (MHB)			10 M Hz (HAP)		
	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$ (10^{-3})	σ_{ac}
30	6.38	1.55	5.50 E-6	5.20	2.48	7.17 E-6
50	6.43	1.36	4.86 E-6	5.18	1.72	4.96 E-6
70	6.51	1.17	4.23 E-6	5.17	0.93	2.67 E-6
90	6.60	0.87	3.19 E-6	5.15	0.58	1.67 E-6
110	6.68	0.71	2.64 E-6	5.27	3.34	9.79 E-6

Figure 8.6 : Plot of variation of dielectric constant and $\tan \delta$ with temperature in HAP (z-cut) at 1 MHz.

Figure 8.7 : Plot of variation of dielectric constant and $\tan \delta$ with temperature in MHB (z-cut) at 1 MHz.

Figure 8.8 : Plot of variation of dielectric constant and $\tan \delta$ with temperature in MHBA (z-cut) at 1MHz.

The temperature variation of dielectric properties are carried out on z-cut crystals of HAP, MHB and MHBA. The results are tabulated in table 8.13 to 8.16. The plot of variation of dielectric constants and dielectric loss with temperature at 1 MHz frequency are shown in figures 8.6 to 8.8. Since in all these three crystals there is no phase transition before melting point, the variation in dielectric constant and dielectric loss with temperature and frequency is not significant.

8.4 Magnetic susceptibility measurements

The magnetic susceptibility (moment) of powdered samples of some of grown crystals were measured using vibrating sample magnetometer PAR - VSW - 155, at room temperature, with magnetic

field range 2 to 10 kilo gauss and is depicted in table 8.17. The magnetic moment of HAP is found to be negative and is almost decreased with increase in magnetic field. The magnetic moment of MHB is found to be surprising in which it fluctuated either side of zero, both positive and negative with increase in applied magnetic field. The magnetic moments in all other crystals are found to be positive and are increased with increase in applied field. This shows HAP behaves as diamagnetic and other crystals except MHB behaves as paramagnetic under intense magnetic field. MHB changes its magnetic property with increase in applied magnetic field and can become a potential candidate in magneto-optic applications.

Table 8.17 : Magnetic moments of the grown crystals.

Field	Magnetic moment (e.m.u) X 10 ⁻²						
	HAP	MHB	MHBA	PHB	ADM	AT	si-NaF
Weight(g)	0.015	0.016	0.007	0.015	0.016	0.016	0.021
2	- 0.022	+ 0.006	+ 0.016	+ 0.026	- 0.01	+0.007	+ 0.005
4	- 0.014	+ 0.006	+ 0.054	+ 0.038	+ 0.009	+0.013	+ 0.009
6	- 0.021	+ 0.000	+ 0.081	+ 0.037	+ 0.007	+0.020	+ 0.014
8	- 0.015	- 0.002	+ 0.108	+ 0.053	+ 0.021	+0.028	+ 0.017
10	- 0.014	+ 0.000	+ 0.145	+ 0.062	+ 0.032	+0.034	+ 0.023

References

8.5 Conclusions

- (1) The dc conductivity of NaF is decreased with silica doping whereas the ac conductivity is increased along with increase in dielectric constant. The dc conductivity of grown nonlinear crystals are found to be low.
- (2) The dielectric constant values of nonlinear crystals are found to be low and they are almost independent on input frequency of ac signal.
- (3) The phase angle ($\tan \delta$) is found to decrease with increase in applied frequency almost for all the crystals.
- (4) The ac conductivity is also found to increase with increase in applied frequency.
- (5) Further, the magnitude of ac conductivity is found to be low.
- (6) There is no anomaly of dielectric constant with increase in temperature in all the cases till their melting point.
- (7) The magnetic moment of HAP is found to be negative and other nonlinear crystals except MHB are found to be positive. But in case of MHB, it oscillated on both side of zero.

References

- [1] Rao K C and Colderwood J H ; *J. Appl. Phys.*, 39 (1968) 3955
- [2] Harris L B ; *J. Phys. Chem. Solids.*, 32 (1971) 59
- [3] Somiah K and Haribabu V ; *Cryst. Res. and Technol.*, 19 (1984) 127
- [4] Abdel - Kader A ; *J. Mater. Sci., Materials in electronics*, 2 (1991) 7
- [5] Pandit A K and Singh R A ; *J. Mat. Sci.*, 26 (1991) 6759
- [6] Arrora R and Kumar A ; *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, 9 (1990) 348
- [7] Sharma S V and Singh R K ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.*, 14 (1991) 76
- [8] Morris P A ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 106 (1990) 76
- [9] Lehfeldt W ; *Z. Phys.*, 85 (1933) 717
- [10] Wanger G and Hantemann P ; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 18 (1950) 72
- [11] Kelting H and Witt H ; *Z. Phys.*, 126 (1949) 697
- [12] Govinda S and Rao K V ; *Phys. Status Solidi* 27 (1975) 639
- [13] Desai C C and Rai J L ; *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, 17 (1982) 3249
- [14] Compton W D and Schalman J H ; *Colour Centers in Solids*, Pergamon Press, London (1962)
- [15] Arrora S K and Lakshminarayana D ; *J. Mater. Sci.*, 18 (1983) 57
- [16] Dharmaprakash S M and Mohan Rao P ; *Cryst. Res. Technol.*, 24 (1989) 693
- [17] Nandi P N and Deshpande D A ; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 88A (1979) 113
- [18] Karl N ; *J. Cryst. Growth*, 99 (1990) 1009

- [19] Kaminow P and Turner E H ; *Applied Optics*, 5 (1966) 1612
- [20] Prasad P N and David J W ; *Introduction to Nonlinear Optical effects in molecules and Polymers.* John Wiley and Sons Inc. Newyork. 1991
- [21] Hebbar K C and Mohan Rao P ; *Cryst. Res. Technol.*, 17 (1992) 273
- [22] Takahashi T and Yamamoto O ; *J. Solid State Chem.*, 21 (1977) 73
- [23] Brightwell J W and Ray B ; *Solid State Ionics*, 15 (1985) 331
- [24] Tareev B ; *Physics of dielectric materials*, Mir Publishers, Mascow (1979) 140

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CHAPTER 9

STUDIES ON THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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9.1 Introduction

Good thermal stability and mechanical strength of both optoelectronic and nonlinear crystals are the main requirement for device fabrication. The decomposition or dehydration at or very close to operating temperature may lead to the malfunction of the device. Similarly, if the crystals are too soft, then the polishing and handling of the crystals become cumbersome. Thus any crystal to be used for device fabrication must be thermally and mechanically stable at room temperature. This chapter includes the study of thermal properties of grown crystals by means of their dehydration and decomposition analysis and the mechanical properties by means of microhardness studies.

The dehydration and decomposition of various oxalates like magnesium oxalate dihydrate [1], zinc oxalate dihydrate [2], cobalt oxalate dihydrate [3], calcium oxalate monohydrate [4] have been studied by means of dynamic TG - DSC data, recorded simultaneously under various measuring conditions. Dollimore [5] has reviewed extensively the thermal decomposition and dehydration of metal oxalates along with their useful analytical applications.

Similarly, Alferd et al [6] have reported the decomposition and dehydration of various hydrated metal tartrates. The decomposition of manganese tartrate trihydrate [7], sodium tartrate dihydrate [8], potassium hydrogen tartrate [9] and calcium tartrate [10] have been studied extensively.

The thermal behaviour of nonlinear organic single crystals are important for material characterization. The thermal behaviour of POM [11], AMA [12], PPNA [13], EMC [14] are extensively studied.

The first part of the present chapter reviews the studies on the thermal behaviour of gel grown silica doped NaF, ADM, AT, MHB, HAP, MHBA and PHB single crystals. Thermogravimetry and differential scanning calorimetry are employed for the thermal studies.

The second part contains the study of mechanical properties of these grown nonlinear crystals by determining their microhardness along different crystallographic directions.

9.2 Thermal analysis

(i) Experimental details :-

A Mettler TA - 4000 (Switzerland) thermal analyzer was employed to obtain TG, DTA traces of some of the grown crystals. The heating rates used in TG and DTA are $20^{\circ}/\text{m}$ and $10^{\circ}/\text{m}$ respectively. Both were carried out under static air atmosphere. The phase transition temperatures of the samples have been confirmed by using a Perkin Elmer DSC-2 differential scanning calorimeter. The samples (50-60 mg) were heated uniformly at a rate of $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ in a gold cup in dry air atmosphere. The change in enthalpy or heat flow ($\text{m Cal}/\text{sec}$) as a function of temperature was recorded using a strip chart recorder.

(ii) Observations and discussion :-

The TG and DTG curves of silica doped NaF and silica doped NH_4F crystals are reported in figure 9.1. By taking the initial weight as standard the course of decomposition of these crystals are analyzed by comparing the molecular weights.

Figure 9.1 : TG and DTG of (a) silica doped NaF, (b) silica doped NH_4F crystals.

Figure 9.2 : DSC curves of (a) silica doped NaF, (b) silica doped NH_4F crystals.

The TG of NaF shows the weight loss as a function of increasing temperature and the transition (derivative) curve (DTG) with a downward peak, representing the decomposition of the sample (NaF) as a function of sample temperature. Both the curves show that the decomposition of the sample starts at nearly 600°C. The decomposition step starts at 560°C and is completed at 675°C. If the coordinated water molecules are present in the compounds, then the corresponding peak should be between 80°C to 200°C. The analysis of the TG curve gives the information regarding the water molecules present in the sample crystal. The absence of peaks in between 80°C to 200°C proves the absence of any water of hydration in gel grown silica doped NaF single crystals. The temperature corresponding to the peak in DTG curves of silica doped NaF is 650°C which is the average melting point of the crystal. Compared with the melting point of pure NaF which is 990°C, the melting point of silica doped NaF is decreased.

The DSC curve of silica doped NaF (Fig 9.2) shows a prominent exothermic peak at 360°C, which is assumed to be change in phase of the crystal without any weight loss.

The TG and DTG curves of silica doped NH_4F crystals also indicate the absence of water of crystallization in the sample. The sample decomposes i.e., the average melting point of the crystal is found to be 480 °C. No phase transition is observed in DSC curve (figure 9.2).

The TG and DTG of AOM is shown in Figure 9.3. The DTG peaks are observed at 103°C, 238°C and 280°C. The TG curve shows 3 steps in the temperature range 80°C to 120°C, 205°C to 250°C and 260 to 285°C. From the weight loss analysis, it is found that the crystal structure contains one molecule of water, liberating during first step. The second peak around 238°C in the DTG curve must corresponding to the decomposition of AOM in to $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$.

On the basis of TG and DTG studies, the following tentative mechanisms may be proposed for thermal dehydration and decomposition of AOM crystals [15].

The DSC curve for AOM crystal is illustrated in figure 9.4 shows an endothermic peak in the temperature range 90 to 150°C (peak temperature is around 102°C) and two exothermic peaks at around temperatures 235°C and around 280°C. The endothermic peak must correspond to the dehydration of AOM crystals. The corresponding TG shows the liberation of water molecule. The exothermic peak at 235°C and 280°C may be due to the formation of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ and NH_3 during the decomposition of AOM.

The TG and DTG of AT single crystals are shown in figure 9.3 and the DSC curve is depicted in figure 9.4. The DTG peaks are observed at 215°C, 240°C and 282°C. From weight loss analysis it is found that the crystal structure contains no water molecules

Figure 9.3 : TG and DTG of (a) ADM and (b) AT crystals.

Figure 9.4 : DSC curves of (a) ADM and (b) AT crystals.

as water of hydration. This is also proved by the absence of peak point below 200°C in DTG .

The first peak around 215°C in DTG curve must correspond to the decomposition of AT into $(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$ [16]. The second peak around 240°C in DTG curve must correspond to the decomposition of ammonium oxalate into ammonium carbonate and the third peak at 282°C must correspond to the decomposition of ammonium carbonate.

On the basis of TG and DTG studies, the following tentative

Figure 9.7 : TG and DTG of (a) HAP and (b) H crystals.

mechanisms may be proposed for thermal decomposition of AT crystals.

The TG, DTG, and DSC of HAP, MHB, MHBA and PHB are recorded from room temperature to their decomposition point and are depicted in figures 9.5 to 9.10. In case of non-linear organic crystals, any phase transition before melting point drastically affects the nonlinear properties, electrical conductivity, dielectric properties and electro-optic properties. In all these organic crystals, the DSC curves show no phase transition before melting. The TG and DTG curves show there is no weight loss before melting and all the organic materials lose weight only after their boiling point. The DTA curves (figure 9.11) of HAP and MHB also confirm the same result. The temperature corresponding to peak in DSC shows the melting point of the organic crystals, whereas the peak in DTG shows the boiling point of them. In DTA curves, the first peak represent the

Figure 9.5 : TG and DTG of (a) HAP and (b) MHB crystals.

Figure 9.6 : TG and DTG of (a) MHBA and (b) PHB crystals.

Figure 9.7 : DSC of HAP (a) heating curve, (b) cooling curve.

Figure 9.8 : DSC of MHB (a) heating curve and (b) cooling curve.

Figure 9.9 : DSC of MHBA (a) heating curve, (b) cooling curve.

Figure 9.10 : DSC of PHB (a) heating curve, (b) cooling curve.

Figure 9.11 : (a) DTA curve of HAP and (b) DTA curve of MHB.

melting point and the second peak represent the boiling point.

The melting point obtained by these studies confirms the results

given in chapter 7.

9.3 Microhardness studies

Microhardness studies find wide applications in the study of mechanical properties of solids [16 - 19]. Point indentation techniques like Vicker's pyramid test and Knoop hardness test have been extensively used in the study of mechanical strength of a material and its correlation with other mechanical properties. Detailed studies have been reported on the observations of slips and cracks around the indentation marks and these have been explained on the basis of dislocation theory [20 - 25].

The indentation is generally carried out using sharp indenters like a cone or pyramid because of the geometrical similarity of the residual impression, the contact pressure with such a geometry is independent of the indent size and thus affords a convenient measure of hardness [26]. Several investigators [27 - 33] have used the indentation technique to study hardness, glide, deformation, anisotropy etc., of various crystals. It appears from the literature that little study of crack pattern and hardness variation have been made for non cubic crystals.

This part contains the results of studies on the microhardness characteristics of gel grown nonlinear crystals like AOM, AT, HAP, MHB, MHBA and PHB. In case of HAP and MHB crystals, the hardness values are studied along three crystallographic directions.

(i) Experimental:-

The gel grown crystals with smooth surfaces are selected after examining them under optical microscope for indentation study. In case of HAP and MHB, the crystals are cut perpendicular to crystallographic axes by means of solvent saw and polished smoothly. The samples were prepared for observation by cold setting the crystals cut along different directions. The samples were mechanically polished carefully to remove protruding portions of the cold setting material and to obtain free access to the crystal surface for the indentation experiment. Indentations are made with a Vicker's diamond using Reichart Microhardness tester (M/S Vicker's Ltd UK). Diagonal length of the indented impressions obtained at various applied loads are measured using the filar micrometer of Vicker's projection metallurgical microscope. Loads varying from 10 to 100 g were applied for a fixed interval of time to determine the variation in diagonal length of indentation mark with load. A second set of observations was taken at constant load to determine the effect of indentation time.

(ii) Results and discussion :-

For each crystal, several trials of indentation with each load were made and the average value of the diagonal length 'd' of the indentation marks was calculated. This value was used to calculate the Vicker's hardness number (VHN) using the formula [34].

$$\text{VHN} = 1.8544 (P/d^2) \text{ Kg.mm}^{-2}$$

Where P is the applied indenter load (Kg) and d is the diagonal length of the indentation mark (in mm).

Table 9.1 lists the average value of the diagonal length of the indentations for different applied loads along the z-axis of grown crystals and table 9.2 gives the variation in average value of diagonal length with applied load along three crystallographic directions of HAP and MHB. The hardness variation with indenter load on crystals is listed in table 9.3.

Table 9.1 : Variation of indentation length with applied load.

Load (g)	Diagonal length of indentation (mm)					
	ADM	AT	HAP	MHB	MHBA	PHB
5	63	38	168	107	160	96
10	77	90	193	143	211	122
20	89	116	213	190	266	153
30	109	137	231	229	317	174
40	132	152	246	258	342	190
50	146	171	254	276	371	207
75	188	189	273	341	441	227

Table 9.2 : Diagonal length of MHB and HAP along 3 axes.

Load (g)	Diagonal length of indentation (mm)					
	MHB x-axis	MHB y-axis	MHB z-axis	HAP x-axis	HAP y-axis	HAP z-axis
5	190	225	107	202	173	168
10	262	254	143	249	237	193
20	356	351	190	287	268	213
30	408	388	229	331	312	231
40	433	398	258	392	371	246
50	454	412	276	408	414	254
75	487	674	341	427	486	273

Table 9.3 : Variation of Vicker's hardness number with load.

Load (g)	Vicker's hardness numbers in Kg/mm ²					
	ADM	AT	HAP	MHB	MHBA	PHB
5	82.75	227.45	11.63	28.68	12.82	35.63
10	110.80	81.09	17.64	32.12	14.75	44.13
20	165.90	97.63	28.95	36.38	18.56	56.12
30	165.80	104.99	36.93	37.57	19.61	65.08
40	150.80	113.72	43.41	39.47	22.46	72.78
50	154.00	112.32	50.90	43.12	23.86	76.65
75	139.40	137.92	66.10	42.36	25.33	95.61

Table 9.4 : Variation of log of diagonal with log of load.

log P	Log of diagonal length (log d)					
	ADM	AT	HAP	MHB	MHBA	PHB
0.7	1.025	0.805	1.450	1.255	1.43	1.207
1	1.120	1.179	1.510	1.381	1.55	1.312
1.3	1.165	1.290	1.554	1.504	1.65	1.410
1.48	1.263	1.362	1.589	1.585	1.73	1.466
1.60	1.346	1.407	1.616	1.637	1.759	1.504
1.69	1.390	1.458	1.630	1.666	1.759	1.541
1.875	1.499	1.498	1.661	1.758	1.87	1.581

Table 9.5 : Work hardening exponent of grown crystals

ADM	AT	HAP	MHB	MHBA	PHB
4.14	2.62	5.13	2.34	2.69	3.15
1.69					

The Vicker's hardness number for some grown crystals with applied load along z-axis is listed in table 9.3. It is observed that the variation of microhardness with load is not linear. This type of nonlinear variation of microhardness with the applied load has been reported for other crystals by many authors [33,35,36].

Figure 9.12 : Plot of $\log d$ versus $\log P$.

According to Meyer's law, $P = ad^n$, where n is Meyer index or the work-hardening exponent and 'a' is a constant for a given material. Table 9.4 contains the variation of $\log d$ with $\log P$ and figure 9.12 shows the plot between them.

The work hardening exponent (n) has been calculated by measuring the slope of the plots and was found to be more than 2 for nonlinear organic crystals.

According to Onitsch [37], n is greater than 2 if the hardness increases with increase in load and is less than 2 when the hardness decreases with increasing load. The values of n obtained in these experiments are listed in table 9.5.

9.4 Conclusions

- (1) The TG, DTG, DSC and DTA studies prove that the grown crystals are thermally stable at or near room temperature.
- (2) In case of nonlinear crystals, there is no phase transition observed before melting point.
- (3) The melting point of HAP and MHB are more than 100°C compared to the melting point of MHBA (70°C).
- (4) The microhardness studies confirm that all the grown crystals have good mechanical properties for device applications.
- (5) In case of all nonlinear crystals, the hardness increases with increase in indentation load.

References

- [1] Tanaka H and Tokumitsu M ; *J. Thermal Analysis*, 29 (1984) 87
- [2] Krishnan K and Ninan K N ; *ibid.*, 89 (1985) 295
- [3] Venkataraman A and Arabinda Ray ; *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 53-5 (1992) 681
- [4] Tanaka H and Negita H ; *Thermochimica Acta*, 48 (1981) 137
- [5] Dollimore D and Mason J ; *Thermochimica Acta*, 24 (1978) 307
- [6] Alferd C and Rubin B ; *Analytical Calorimetry*, vol.2, Plenum Press New York (1970) 255
- [7] Ramakrishan V ; *Cryst. Res. Technol.* 24, 5 (1989) 513
- [8] Abdul-Kader M M and S Taha ; *J. Mater. Sci.: Materials in electronics*, 1 (1990) 201
- [9] Verdaguer S V ; *J. Cryst. Growth* 99 (1990) 211
- [10] Gon H B ; *J. Cryst. Growth* 102 (1990) 501
- [11] Hierle R, Badan J and Zyss J ; *J. Cryst. Growth* 69 (1984) 545
- [12] Badan J and Zyss J ; in *Nonlinear Properties of Organic and Polymeric Materials*, American Chemical Society, Washington, DC (1983) cha-4
- [13] Eich M and Yoon D Y ; *J. Appl. Phys.* 66 (1989) 2559
- [14] Shankar M and Varma K B R ; *Proceedings of symposium on optoelectronics*, IISc, 1991
- [15] Kasthuri V B ; in *PhD Thesis*, submitted to Mangalore University, 1994
- [16] Kotru P N and Koul M L ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 21 (1986) 3933
- [17] Buckle H ; *Mater. Rev.* 4 (1959) 49

- [18] Smakula A and Repucci A ; *J. Appl. Phys.* 33 (1962) 453
- [19] Haribabu V and Subba Rao V ; *Prog. Cryst. Growth Charact.* 8 (1984) 189
- [20] Meyer K and Berger U ; *Z. Phy. Chemie.* 223 (1963) 207
- [21] Meyer K and Gragert E ; *Phys. Stat. Solids*, 6 (1964) 803
- [22] Meyer K and Bruckner U ; *Kristall. U Technik*, 1 (1966) 477
- [23] Doerschel J ; *Kristall. U Technik*. 6, 5 (1971) 663
- [24] Rossberg M and Brockner U ; *Kristall. U Technik*. 5 (1979) K1
- [25] Shukla M and Bansigir K G ; *J. Phys. D (GB)*, 9 (1976) L49
- [26] Tabor D ; in *The hardness of metals*, (Clarendon Press Oxford) 1951
- [27] Brookes C A and Green P ; *Nat. Phys. Sci.* 246 (1973) 119
- [28] Dekker E H and Reick G D ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 9 (1974) 1839
- [29] Brookes C A and Moxley B ; *J. Phys. CEE Sci. Instrum.* 8 (1975) 456
- [30] Kumashri Y T and Sobajina M ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 12 (1977) 595
- [31] Arora S K and Godbole R S ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 17 (1982) 2825
- [32] Dharmaprakash S M and Mohan Rao P ; *J. Crys. Res. Technol.* 21 (1986) 1567
- [33] Irusan T and Ramaswami P ; *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.* 12 (1993) 405
- [34] Mott B W ; in *Micro indentation hardness testing*, Butterworths, London (1956) 9
- [35] Pratap K J and Haribabu ; *Bull. Mater. Sci.* 2 (1980) 43
- [36] Kotru P N and Wanklyn B M ; *J. Mater. Sci.* 19 (1984) 2582
- [37] Onitsch E M ; *Mikroskopie*, 2 (1947) 13

CHAPTER 10

STUDIES ON OPTICAL PROPERTIES

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10.1 Introduction

It is well known that analysis of atomic and molecular spectra made possible an understanding of the structure and properties of atoms and molecules. In case of nonlinear crystals, the cutoff wavelength depends on the molecules absorption of different wavelength of light. In order to get SHG in diode lasers, (i.e. to produce UV laser beam) one of the main requirements is the transparency of the material in UV region.

In recent years, much work has been done in studying the behaviour of impurity particles in crystals with respect to their influence on lattice dynamics and optical absorption. Both change considerably on introducing defects in crystals mainly because they destroy the translational symmetry.

In addition, it is also known that certain impurities when present in amounts ranging from a few parts per million to several percent, can confer luminescent properties on the host or matrix compounds. These impurities are called activators.

Similarly, small amounts of other impurities called poisons or quenchers can inhibit or destroy the luminescence.

Studies on the optical absorption (UV-VIS and near IR), laser Raman spectroscopy of organic compounds and thermoluminescence property of silica doped NaF, silica doped NH_4F and their mixed crystals are described in this chapter.

10.2 UV-VIS-NIR Spectral studies

Molecular spectra appearing in ultra violet and visible region arise due to transitions from one electronic state to another. UV - VIS - NIR spectrophotometer Cary 2390 was employed to obtain the spectra of grown crystals between 200-3150nm. The UV-VIS-NIR spectra of various grown crystals are depicted in figures 10.1-10.7. All varieties of grown crystals are found to be transparent in the visible region. This is naturally so, because the energy gap separating the valance band from the conduction band in these crystals is quite large. The energy of incident photons is too small, therefore, to excite any electrons from quantum states in the valance band to the higher energy states in the conduction band and hence the photons are not absorbed by the crystals.

The optical transparency range of some grown crystals at room temperature are listed in table 10.1.

The absorption peak obtained at 270 nm in the case of HAP, at 258 nm in the case of MHB, at 384 nm for MHBA and at 296 nm for PHB is due to $n - \pi^*$ transition. This $n - \pi^*$ transition is forbidden by symmetry consideration, thus the intensity of the band due to this transition is low [1,2]. The cut-off wavelength in case of HAP is found to be 220 nm which is due to $n - \sigma^*$ transition. Similarly, the cut-off wavelength of MHB is found to be 210 nm, which is again due to $n - \sigma^*$ transition. The σ^* transitions are sensitive to hydrogen bonding [3], and require greater energy.

Table 10.1 : Optical transparencies of some grown crystals.

Crystal	Transparency range
ADM	0.3 μm to 1.1 μm
AT	0.235 μm to 1.5 μm
Silica NaF	0.2 μm to 1.4 μm
HAP	0.22 μm to 2.3 μm
MHB	0.21 μm to 2.8 μm
MHBA	0.37 μm to 1.7 μm
PHB	0.28 μm to 2.1 μm

Figure 10.1 : Optical transmission spectrum of Silica doped NaF.

Table 10.1 : Optical transparencies of some grown crystals.

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MHB	0.21 μm to 2.8 μm
MHBA	0.37 μm to 1.7 μm
PHB	0.28 μm to 2.1 μm

Figure 10.1 : Optical transmission spectrum of Silica doped NaF.

Figure 10.2 : Optical transmission spectrum of ADM.

Figure 10.3 : Optical transmission spectrum of AT.

Figure 10.4 : Optical transmission spectrum of HAP.

Figure 10.5 : Optical transmission spectrum of MHB.

Figure 10.6 : Optical transmission spectrum of MHBA.

Figure 10.7 : Optical transmission spectrum of PHB.

Since MHB and HAP are having relatively weak donor and acceptors at opposite positions, as compared to MHBA, the cut-off wavelength is drastically reduced and hence they are expected to be efficient molecular nonlinear optical materials.

10.3 Laser Raman Spectroscopy

Laser Raman Spectroscopy can effectively be used for structural, chemical and vibrational (optical) analysis of materials. Each scattering species gives its own characteristic vibrational Raman spectrum, which can be used for its qualitative identification. This method in no way disturbs chemical equilibrium and thus gives information about labile species which could not be apprehended by ordinary chemical analytical methods. Above all, because it gives distinct information about the individual species present, the Raman method is more powerful than colligative methods which measure only some property of the system as a whole.

In the present study, a DILOR Z-24 laser Raman spectrophotometer is used to study the Raman spectra of organic nonlinear crystals.

The laser Raman spectra of HAP, MHB, MHBA and PHB are depicted in figures 10.8 to 10.11. The observed bands and their assignments [4,5] are tabulated in tables 10.2 to 10.5. It is found that more vibrational bands are observed as compared to infrared vibrational spectra of these compounds.

R.S.I.C
I.I.T
MADRAS

DILOR Z24 RAMAN
Spectrometer

OPERATOR CJG EXCITATION (nm) 488 SPECT. SLIT WIDTH (cm-1) 4.31
DATE 01-25-1995 LASER POW. (mW) 100 STEP (cm-1) 1.66
SAMPLE HAP SPECTRUM FROM 20 FILTER y
MODE SINGLECHANNEL TO (cm-1) 4000.7 INTEGRATION TIME (s) 1
continuous SLIT WIDTH (um) 400/450 NUMBER OF ACCUMULATIONS 1
REMARK: P.MOHAN RAD 20-4000CM-1

Chapter 10 : Studies on Optical properties.
Figure 10.8 : Laser Raman spectrum of HAP.

R.S.I.C
I.I.T
MADRAS

DILOR Z24 RAMAN
Spectrometer

OPERATOR	CJG	EXCITATION (nm)	488	SPECT. SLIT WIDTH (cm ⁻¹)	4.31
DATE	01-25-1995	LASER POW. (mW)	200	STEP (cm ⁻¹)	1.67
SAMPLE	MHB	SPECTRUM FROM	20	FILTER	Y
MODE	SINGLECHANNEL	TO (cm ⁻¹)	4029.6	INTEGRATION TIME (s)	1
	continuous	SLIT WIDTH (um)	400/450	NUMBER OF ACCUMULATIONS	1
REMARK:	P.MOHAN RAO 20-4000CM-1				

Figure 10.9 : Laser Raman spectrum of MHB.

Figure 10.10 : Laser Raman spectrum of MHBA.

R.S.I.C I.I.T MADRAS		OPERATOR CJG DATE 01-25-1995 SAMPLE MHBA MODE SINGLECHANNEL continuous REMARK: P.MOHAN RAO 20-4000CM-1	EXCITATION (nm) 488 LASER POW. (mW) 200 SPECTRUM FROM 20 TO (cm-1) 3997.3 SLIT WIDTH (um) 400/450	SPECT.SLIT WIDTH (cm-1) 4.31 STEP (cm-1) 1.66 FILTER y INTEGRATION TIME (s) 1 NUMBER OF ACCUMULATIONS 1
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Table 10.2 : Laser Raman Bands and their assignments of HAP.

Observed bands (μm)	Assignment
61.5 to 458.2	C - OH deformation
591	C - CO - C bend
652.4 to 742.1	O - H O.O.P. deformation
830.1 to 855	C - H O.O.P deformation
981 to 1017.6	Ring breathing
1095.7 to 1291.5	C - O stretch
1319.8	CH ₃ bend
1450.9	CH ₃ deformation
1527.3	aromatic ring stretch
1558.8	C - C stretch
1593.7	C - H stretch
1650.1	C = O stretch
2095	overtone & combination stretch
2554.8 to 2807.1	C - H stretch
2931.6	C = C stretch
3064.4 to 3169	O - H stretch

Table 10.3 : Laser Raman Bands and their assignments of MHB.

Observed bands (μm)	Assignment
58.3 to 519.2	C - OH deformation
532.6 to 641.1	O - C - O bend
656.2 to 716.3	O - H O.O.P. deformation
794.8 to 975.1	C - H O.O.P deformation
1031.9	Ring breathing
1138.8 to 1297.4	C - O - C symmetric stretch
1327.5 to 1471.1	CH ₃ deformation
1532.9 to 1644.8	aromatic ring stretch
1688.2 to 1699.9	C = O stretch
2855.5 to 3082.7	C - H stretch
3199.6 to 3578.7	O - H stretch

Table 10.4 : Laser Raman Bands and their assignments of MHBA.

Observed bands (μm)	Assignment
46.5 to 549.4	C - OH deformation
600.9	C - CO - C bend
642.4	C - C - CHO bend
743.7	O - H O.O.P. deformation
823.3 to 969.4	C - H O.O.P deformation
1037.5	Ring breathing
1135.4 to 1274.9	C - O - C symmetric stretch
1306.4 to 1474.1	CH ₃ deformation
1517.2	aromatic ring stretch
1600.2	C = C stretch
1669.9 to 1699.8	C = O stretch
2330.6 to 3076	C - H stretch
3162.3 to 3175.6	O - H stretch

Table 10.5 : Laser Raman Bands and their assignments of PHB.

Observed bands (μm)	Assignment
59.7 to 466.4	C - OH deformation
552.7 to 635.7	O - C - O bend
654	O - H O.O.P. deformation
791.8 to 932.8	C - H O.O.P deformation
1029.1	Ring breathing
1059 to 1361.1	C - O - C symmetric stretch
1374.4 to 1446	CH ₃ deformation
1532.1 to 1641.7	aromatic ring stretch
1676.5	C = O stretch
2880 to 3067.6	C - H stretch
3192.1 to 3271.8	O - H stretch

10.4 Thermoluminescence studies on opto-electronic crystals

Thermoluminescence refers specially to the luminescence appearing as the temperature of the material is steadily increased and is attributed to its previous exposure to ionizing radiation. Many solids contain one or more types of centers that can trap electrons or holes. If the solid is exposed to light of sufficiently short wavelength or to x-rays, free electrons and holes are produced in the solid, and some of these charge carriers may be trapped. Very commonly, the hole is trapped at the luminescent centre itself while the electron is trapped at different site, but the reverse situation is also quite possible. If the temperature of the sample is raised slowly, the electron will receive increasing amounts of thermal energy and will eventually escape the trap. An electron thus freed from a trap may go over a luminescence centre and recombine with the hole trapped at or near the center. The energy liberated by the recombination excites the center, causing it to luminescence. For a single type of trap, the glow curve (plot of Thermoluminescence intensity as a function of temperature) first rises, reaches a maximum and then decreases to zero, when all the traps become emptied [6-9]. When more than one type of trap is present, the glow curve comprises of a corresponding number of peaks which often may be used to secure information about the properties of the traps in solids.

10.4.1 Experimental details

The circuit connections are made as shown in the figure 10.13. The crystal is irradiated with X-rays for about one hour using X-ray source (30KV, 15 amperes generator). The X-ray irradiated crystal is placed in the sample holder inside the oven. Emitted radiations from the crystal is fed to a photo multiplier tube. A thermometer (0 - 400°C) is inserted in to the oven to measure the temperature of the crystal. The output voltage in millivolts is measured by using a digital multimeter which is taken as thermoluminescence intensity in arbitrary units.

Rough estimates of activation energies (E_g) for the glow peaks have been made using the method of Halperin and Braner [10] who showed that glow peak activation energy can be written as

$$E_g = \frac{1.51 k T_g T^1}{T_g - T^1}$$

where T_g is the peak temperature, T^1 is the temperature on the low temperature side at which the emission is one-half of its peak value and k is Boltzman's constant.

10.4.2 Results and discussion

The defects and impurities responsible for thermoluminescence introduce localized electronic states into the crystal lattice [11-13]. Qualitatively such centers are easily understood.

Figure 10.12 : Experimental setup for thermoluminescence study.

If normal lattice atom is replaced substitutionally by an atom whose valency is either more or less than the replaced atom, a local charge unbalance is created.

In the present investigation, the thermoluminescence measurements are made with an apparatus in which a fraction of the light emitted by the sample is impinged directly on the photodetector. The thermoluminescence data consists of a plot of photodetector current (or voltage) versus sample temperature. When the photodetector current is not proportional to number of light emitting processes occurring per unit time, such data are not suitable for kinetic determination.

The transparent silica doped single crystals of NaF, NH_4F and their mixed crystals are irradiated with X-rays using X-ray source. After 30 minutes of continuous irradiation, the crystal turned to deep violet colour and is placed in the sample holder inside the oven of TL apparatus. Emitted radiations from the crystal is fed to a photo-multiplier tube. The temperature of the sample is increased slowly ($2^\circ\text{C}/\text{m}$), the output current is measured and is taken as thermoluminescence intensity in arbitrary units.

Figure 10.13 shows the TL glow curves of pure NaF, and silica doped NaF single crystals. Both pure and silica doped NaF crystals showed TL glow peaks at temperatures 25°C , 102°C , whereas the doped crystals produced two new glow peaks at around 180°C and 300°C along with pronounced intensity of parent peaks.

The glow curves of pure and doped NH_4F crystals are depicted in figure 10.14. In this case, there are again two additional peaks at 190°C and 320°C are observed along with one parent peak of pure NH_4F with increased intensity. But the parent peak is shifted 4 degrees (296°C) to low temperature side as compared to the peak at 300°C in case of pure NH_4F .

Figure 10.13 : Glow curves of pure NaF and silica doped NaF.

Figure 10.15 shows the glow curves of silica doped $\text{NaF} - \text{NH}_4\text{F}$ mixed crystals. In this case, three TL peaks are observed at temperatures 100°C , 210°C and 323°C .

Figure 10.14 : Glow curves of pure NH_4F and silica doped NH_4F .

Figure 10.15 : Glow curve for mixed crystals.

Figure 10.16 : Variation of peak intensity of glow curves with irradiation time. (NaF \rightarrow 108°C peak; NH₄F \rightarrow 296°C peak)

All the glow peaks of both doped and undoped crystals increased with the increase of dose and attained saturation after 30 minutes of irradiation in case of pure and doped NaF and after 20 minutes in case of pure and doped NH₄F crystals (figure 10.16).

The increase in TL output due to silica doping can be understood on the basis that apart from the natural expected increase due to increase of concentration of impurity centers by the presence of Si⁺, O⁻ etc, some additional cation vacancies are likely to be produced for charge compensation. These additional cation vacancies may now give rise to some more stabilized trapped hole centers. The extra emission at other temperature region in TL spectra produced due to doping can be related to either F⁺, (F₂⁺)^{*}, M centers or to the impurity centers.

The results of the measurements of the activation energies for the various glow peaks are given in table 10.6. The values of

activation energies in the table 10.6 are only rough measures since more refined techniques for measuring activation energies are available [14-15].

Table 10.6 : Activation energies of doped flouride crystals.

Crystal and peak No.	Activation energy (eV)
Pure NaF : Peak 1	2.276
Peak 2	1.784
Silica doped NaF :	
Peak 1	2.276
Peak 2	1.173
Peak 3	5.287
Peak 4	1.708
Pure NH ₄ F : Peak 1	2.302
Silica doped NH ₄ F :	
Peak 1	1.802
Peak 2	6.957
Peak 3	6.468
Silica doped mixed crystal :	
Peak 1	2.217
Peak 2	2.470
Peak 3	2.815

This shows that the presence of silica not only activates the NaF or NH₄F but also helps to create extra impurity defects under X-ray irradiation. A systematic study of effect of different energy photons, on the TL glow curve shape, mostly in

relative intensities of the various peaks, would supply information on the kinds of defects formed in the material under bombardment with radiations of different energies. Such a study has not been carried out so far but is planned in near future. It can be tentatively concluded that the doping of silica into the crystal lattice of a crystal influence directly as well as indirectly resulting in the formation of additional glow peaks and increased enhancement of glow curve intensities respectively.

10.5 Conclusions

- (1) The cut-off wavelength and the transmission properties of grown crystals are determined by means of absorption spectra.
- (2) The organic nonlinear crystals HAP and MHB are transparent in UV region and hence can be used for UV nonlinear applications.
- (3) The Laser Raman spectra of all grown organic crystals are depicted along with their assignments.
- (4) The X-ray irradiation turned the colour of doped flouride crystals to deep violet.
- (5) The thermoluminescence studies on doped flouride crystals after X-ray irradiation show additional peaks along with increased intensity of parent peaks. This confirms the addition of impurity colour centers into the lattice sites of the crystals.

References

- [1] Friedel R A and Orchin M ; *Ultraviolet Spectra of Aromatic Compounds*, Wiley, Newyork (1951)
- [2] Denny R and Sinclair R ; *Visible and Ultraviolet Spectroscopy*, Wiley Chichester (1987) ACOL Text.
- [3] Kalsi P S ; *Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds*, 2nd ed., Wiley Eastern Limited. U K (1993) 15
- [4] Joseph B L and Graham C R ; *Introduction to Organic Spectroscopy*, Macmillian Publishing Company New York, Part II (1987) 159
- [5] Francis R D and Freeman F B ; *Characteristic Raman Frequencies of Organic Compounds*, Library of Congress Cataloging in Publication Data, USA (1973) 162
- [6] Garlick G F J ; *Luminescent Materials*, Oxford University Press, Oxford (1949)
- [7] Cameron J R and Kenney G N ; *Thermoluminescent Dosimetry*, University of Wisconsin Press, Madison (1968)
- [8] Curie D ; *Luminescence in crystals*, translated by Garlick G F J, Methuen and Co. London (1963)
- [9] Chen R and Kirsh Y ; *Analysis of thermally stimulated Processes*, Pergamon, Oxford (1981)
- [10] Halperin A and Braner A A ; *Phys. Rev.*, 117 (1960) 408
- [11] Braunlich ; *Thermally stimulated Relexation in solids*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin (1979)
- [12] Datta S and Hughens A E ; *Health Physics*, 29 (1975) 420

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- [13] Stoneham A M ; *Theory of defects in solids*, Electronic structure of defects in Insulators and Semiconductors, Oxford University Press , Oxford (1975)
- [14] Fong F K ; *Bull. Am. Phys. Soc.*, 10 (1965) 306
- [15] Fong F K ; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 41 (1964) 245